

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D4.4: Report on data and sources documentation and quality assessment

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1 Introduction

Task 4.4 produced data and sources documentation (metadata) for a representative sample of datasets and printed serial sources from the data and sources inventory (D4.2). The data and sources documentation was produced according to the metadata standard (Data Documentation Initiative) and with the application (Colectica Designer) selected in task 4.1. We will therefore briefly reiterate the key motivations for choosing this standard and information system (see also D4.1 Information system and documentation standards) in section 2. Sections 3 and 4 then continue with a discussion of the metadata elements used for documenting sources and datasets and their organisation at the top-level of the source or the dataset (i.e. the volumes or the files) and the bottom-level of the variables (i.e. the blocks of text or columns) present in the sources and datasets. Section 5 finally includes the quality assessment. For the printed sources, we establish an order of precedence of source types (e.g. official price lists or yearbooks) for various types of information (e.g. share prices). For assessing the quality of datasets, we propose a questionnaire (Appendix 1).

The data and sources documentation itself is available in the DDI 3.2-XML format and can be downloaded from the EURHISFIRM Dataverse (<https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/WLOW0K>). We recommend the free Colectica Reader software for viewing the documentation.¹ A subset of metadata elements, however, is included in Appendix 2 of this report in a more reader-friendly format.

Over 250 sources and datasets were identified during task 4.2. Producing formal documentation for all of them would not be feasible within the time allocated to task 4.4. Exhaustiveness is also unnecessary within the framework of the current design study. In the case of dataset and databases, we selected the four large databases that are also being considered for data matching and connecting in Working Package 6 (Data for Financial History or D-FIH Database, EUROFIDAI Stocks Daily Database, London Share Price Database or LSPD and Studiecentrum voor Beurs en Onderneming or SCOB Database) and three smaller datasets produced by members of the consortium. In the case of printed sources, we included a price list for each country's principal stock exchange and one yearbook. To ensure representativeness, we selected different types of yearbooks. The yearbooks for Belgium (*Recueil financier*), France (*Annuaire Desfossés*), Spain (*Anuario oficial de valores*) and the United Kingdom (*Stock Exchange Official Year-Book*) feature domestic and foreign companies listed on the stock exchanges of Brussels, Paris (*Parquet* and *Coulisse*), Madrid and London, respectively. The German (*Handbuch der Deutschen Aktiengesellschaften*) and Polish (*Rocznik Informacyjny*) yearbooks include all domestic joint-stock companies. The Dutch yearbook (*Gids bij de Prijscourant*) includes information on all securities listed on the Amsterdam Stock Exchange. We chose to document examples of price lists and yearbooks published during the interwar years. While the headings of columns in price lists or the titles of sections in yearbooks titles may change, their content was generally very stable. New columns and sections were only added with years in between and, once added, were removed rarely. During the interwar period, most price lists had obtained a very stable form. All selected yearbooks also had already been published for some time in this period, so their content had also taken a stable form. This representative sample of printed sources and datasets allows us to thoroughly evaluate the aptness of the chosen metadata standard and software for documenting sources and data in

¹ <https://www.colectica.com/software/reader/>

task 4.5 and to illustrate national traditions in the representation of company information which will feed into the elaboration of data models by Work Package 5.

2 Standards and software

2.1 Data Documentation Initiative

Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is a set of metadata standards and controlled vocabularies for documenting studies and datasets in the social sciences and economics. It has been developed within the community of social sciences data archives and is the currently preferred data documentation standard of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

In task 4.1, the DDI standard was chosen over other metadata standards for documenting research datasets. With increasing levels of detail, Dublin Core (DCMI), DataCite and da|ra contain a set of elements for describing datasets and printed sources at the study level (common elements include, for instance: identifiers, title, creator, publisher, abstract, coverage and format). Da|ra adds elements specific to the social sciences (for instance for the description of data collections), but only DDI includes elements for a detailed documentation of the individual variables contained in a dataset. This information at the variable level is crucial to the analysis of semantics and the elaboration of data models within EURHISFIRM.

Two versions of the DDI standard are available. For EURHISFIRM, we selected the more extensive DDI-Lifecycle (currently version 3.2) over the simpler DDI-Codebook (currently version 2.5) since it is more suitable for documenting historical printed serial sources (primarily because it supports a wider range of date formats, including dates in different calendars). Furthermore, DDI-Lifecycle includes the possibility to reuse content over several instances. For instance, variables and other metadata elements can be documented once and then referenced in several studies. Finally, DDI-Lifecycle incorporates Dublin Core for citation-type metadata. This means that within the DDI standard, there is the option to use Dublin Core elements instead of DDI elements for capturing basic bibliographic information about a source. Because Dublin Core is widely used, this greatly improves the interoperability of EURHISFIRM with third-party databases.

2.2 Colectica Designer

To produce and edit data documentation in the DDI 3.2-XML format, we chose Colectica Designer. Colectica Designer is a proprietary software, as there are no open source editors which support the DDI standard down to the variable level (the editable fields in Harvard Dataverse, for instance, mostly cover study level metadata). Since it is proprietary, Colectica Designer comes at a monthly licence cost of 59 USD per user. However, a licence is only required for editing. Viewing can be done with the free Colectica Reader. Furthermore, Colectica can import and export DDI-XML files so vendor lock-in is not an issue.

3 Metadata at the source or dataset level

3.1 Organisation of metadata elements

In DDI and Colectica, the Group or Series level is used to record common metadata about a set of related StudyUnits or Studies (Group and StudyUnits is DDI terminology, Series and Studies is Colectica terminology). Optionally, an intermediate level of Sub-groups or Sub-series can be inserted between the Group or Series and StudyUnit or Study levels. The first task when adding metadata about a new source to the project is choosing the right level for documenting the source. This depends entirely on the repetitive nature of the source. Yearbook series, for instance, are documented at the Group or Series level; a dataset at the StudyUnit or Study level.

In the case of EURHISFIRM, we must also consider the traditional challenge that long-running serials pose to cataloguing. Contents, as well as titles, subtitles and/or publishers can change multiple times during their lifetime. Do these changes warrant the creation of a new group or series? The Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules (AACR2), for instance, do stipulate that a new record is created each time a significant change occurs in a serial title. To avoid multiplication of records and links between records, we propose, however, to document an entire run of a serial as a single record at the Group or Series level (see also section 2.3 below on titles).

If EURHISFIRM in the future would build a data catalogue with, for instance, images of sources, it would be sensible to document each daily or annual issue of a stock exchange price list or yearbook as a separate StudyUnit or Study. In the case of daily price lists, Sub-groups or Sub-series could also be created to group all issues from a single volume (i.e. all lists published in the same year). Presently, however, we only recorded metadata for serial sources at the Group or Series level.

3.2 Metadata elements

3.2.1 Titles

Long-running serials can present a challenge with regards to title documentation, as titles can change during their lifetime. The AACR2 method for handling title changes has already been noted in section 3.1 above. The American Library Association (ALA) cataloguing rules present a different approach to serials with multiple titles. These are catalogued as a single record under their latest title with their title history in a note. We propose to follow the ALA approach, with this alteration: In the Title element, we record a conventional or uniform title. A uniform title is assigned when a work that has been published under various titles must be represented by a single title and can, for instance, include a corporate body or place of publication (between parentheses) to distinguish serials with the same titles (relevant in the case of EURHISFIRM because both the official price lists of the Paris and Brussels stock exchanges were titled *Cours authentique*).

Example: Boletín de cotización (Madrid)

Subsequent titles under which a serial was published (i.e. the title history) are recorded in the AlternateTitle element. If a publication has a subtitle, the subtitles are separated from the main title by

space-colon-space (:) (we do not use the subtitle element).² Titles are followed by a time range (first year-last year of publication under a particular title) in parentheses and separated by space-semicolon-space (;).

Example: Cotización oficial del Colegio de Agentes de Cambios (1854-1885) ; Boletín de cotización oficial de la Bolsa de Comercio de Madrid (1886-1972) ; Bolsa de Comercio de Madrid : Boletín de cotización oficial (1973-1989) ; Bolsa de Madrid : Boletín de cotización oficial (1989-1990) ; Bolsa de Madrid : Boletín de cotización (1990-1992) ; Boletín de cotización : Bolsa de Madrid (1992-2002)

3.2.2 Creator and contributor

The creator (or author) is the entity primarily responsible for making the source or dataset, whereas the role of the contributor is more limited. Creators and contributors can be both natural persons or legal entities. These fields include the names of all creators and (if applicable) contributors. In case of a natural person, we preferentially recorded the full name. Initials are given only if the first name is unknown. The name comes first, followed by a comma (,) and the first name(s) or initial(s). In case of multiple creators or contributors, names are separated by space-semicolon-space (;).

3.2.3 Publisher

The publisher is the entity (natural person or legal entity) responsible for making the source or dataset available. The Publisher element includes the place of publication and the name of the publisher. The place of publication is recorded in the native language. In case a publication is published in more than one place, cities are separated by an ampersand (&). The place of publication and the publisher are separated by space-colon-space (:). If a serial has multiple subsequent publishers, the publishers are followed by a time range (first and last year) in parentheses and separated by space-semicolon-space (;).

Example: Madrid : Colegio de Agentes de Cambio (1854-1989) ; Sociedad Rectora Bolsa de Valores de Madrid (1989-2002)

In case a serial changes its publisher very frequently, however, the first publisher followed by [etc.] must suffice.

3.2.4 Date

The date is the point in time when the source was published. In case of serial sources described at the Group or Series level, the date will include both the start and end date (i.e. the date when it was made available for the first and last time). The DDI PublicationDate and DCMI Terms Date elements can both include a time range. Colectica, however, currently only allows a single date in the Date field of the Citation section. Pending customisation of Colectica, we recorded the start date in the Date field and the end date in a custom field EndDate. Dates of daily publication (for instance price lists) are recorded with as much precision as possible (i.e. day, month and year if available). For annual publications such as yearbooks, the

² The reason for using spaces before the punctuation is double. Firstly, it is common practice in bibliographic description (see, for instance, the International Standard Bibliographic Description rules). Secondly, it serves a technical purpose. The preceding space distinguishes added punctuation from original punctuation (for instance within a title) and facilitates future parsing into multiple fields or elements.

year of publication suffices. Colectica, however, currently only allows a full date in the Date field. Pending customisations, the start date is recorded as January 1 and the end date as December 31.

3.2.5 Abstract

The Abstract field contains a short description of the content of the source or dataset.

Example: The Boletín de cotización is the official price list of the Madrid Stock Exchange (Spanish: Bolsa de Madrid). Initially, it included daily spot prices of public bonds and corporate shares and debentures and forward prices (first or opening, highest, lowest and last or closing price only) of some public bonds, their nominal value and the amount paid-up on shares. Details on the previous price (date and quote in percentages) and on dividends and interests were added in 1903. The dividends paid during the previous and the current year were reported for shares and the interest rate and the date when the next interest payment was due for bonds. The total share capital in circulation, bid and ask prices and the annual highest and lowest price were added during the interwar period (1934 at the latest). Publication was interrupted multiple times, especially during the Spanish Civil War when no official lists were published between 17 July 1936 and 4 March 1940.

3.2.6 Type and format

The Type is the nature or genre of the source. This is a DCMI terms element with a controlled vocabulary.³ The most common values will be Text for yearbooks and price lists and Dataset for datasets and databases. Further details such as the file format (in case of datasets and databases) and the extent and size (e.g. number of volumes, height and width) can be recorded in the Format element. We currently only included information about the file format of datasets and databases.

3.2.7 Coverage

Coverage refers to a set of discovery metadata which describe the temporal, spatial and topical coverage of a source or dataset. These allow other researchers to quickly assess the usability of a source or dataset for their own research.

Topical coverage can be described by subjects and keywords. In DDI, the difference between subjects and keywords is mainly in their provenance: subjects are taken from subject classifications (e.g. the Universal Decimal Classification often used in libraries); keywords from thesauri (e.g. the Art & Architecture Thesaurus from the Getty Institute). Currently, we use the subject headings (subject categories) and additional entry terms (descriptors) from the **STW Thesaurus for Economics** (ZBW Leibniz Information Centre for Economics) as subjects and keywords.⁴

Temporal coverage is described by means of dates which delineate the start and end of the period covered by the source or dataset.

Spatial or geographical coverage can be described with a lot of details in DDI and Colectica, for instance by a set of geospatial coordinates (i.e. a bounding box). We currently limited the description of the geographical coverage, however, to the names of the principal cities, regions or states to which the contents of the source or dataset pertain and ISO 3166 codes for referring to their present-day country

³ <http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms/#section-7>

⁴ <http://zbw.eu/stw/version/latest/about>

equivalents (for instance, for Prussia, this would be mainly DE, PL and RU). Names of cities, regions and states are taken from the **Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names**.⁵

3.2.8 Funding

Information about the grant and funding organisation which enabled the collection and organisation of the data was recorded when applicable. This is most relevant in the case of datasets and databases.

Example: Equipment of Excellence – EQUIPEX [source: D-FIH Data for Financial History]

3.2.9 Data collection and data sources

In the case of datasets and databases, it is also important to capture how data were collected (for instance, manual entry from printed sources). This includes a full enumeration of the sources of the data.

Example: End-of-month prices were collected manually from historical stock exchange price lists and newspapers:

Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (Berlin)
 Berliner Börsencourier (Berlin)
 Neumann's Cours-Tabellen (Berlin)
 ...

[Source: SAFE]

4 Metadata at the variable level

DDI and Colectica permit detailed documentation of sources and data up to the variable level. Variables are characteristics of the unit (e.g. a person, company or share) that is analysed. Variables are defined in DDI and Colectica as “columns in a rectangular data file” or “columns in a dataset”. The metadata elements in the Variable class define the contents of this column.

4.1 Organisation of metadata elements

4.1.1 Datasets and databases

For the organisation of metadata elements for the description of variables from datasets, we use the standard approach from DDI and Colectica. In DDI and Colectica, variables are grouped in a logical record (Data Layout in Colectica) which describes all of the variables related to a single case or analysis unit. A logical record, in turn, belongs to a physical instance (Data File in Colectica). In a relational database with three tables for issuers, securities and share prices, for instance, the variables from each table are grouped in a separate logical record.

4.1.2 Printed sources

The logic of linking variables to logical records and logical records to data files works well for the documentation of datasets, but presents a problem for the description of some printed sources. In the case of yearbooks, for instance, different analysis units (companies and their securities) are mixed. Hence, it is impossible to organise variables from printed sources in the same way as variables for datasets without

⁵ <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/>

artificially breaking down the information. We therefore developed a different approach for the organisation of variables from printed sources. We used Variable Sets and Groups to organise the metadata in accordance with the layout of the sources. A **Variable Set** was created for each printed source. Within these Variable Sets, **Variable Groups** were created if necessary. Variable Groups are groups of variables that are linked by “some factor”. In our case, this factor is the layout of the pages.

Price lists

The description of variables in price lists is straightforward and differs little from the description of variables in a dataset. Price data are generally published in a tabular form, with data organised in columns and rows. Each column in this case represents a variable and each row an issue from a particular issuer (company or public body). Price lists may, however, contain multiple tables with different columns for particular types of securities or for securities from particular types of issuers, for instance for shares and debentures (see Figure 1 and Figure 2) or for public and corporate bonds. If the source treats issuers in separate and distinct tables, different Variable Groups are created to reflect the layout of the source.

	Div11	Div12	Geschtsj.	Stücke zu	Gestriger Kurs	Hentiger Kurs
Berl. Kindl-Br. .	14	14	1/10	300 <i>M</i>	233,25 G	233,25 G
do. St.-Pr.	16	16	do.	1000 <i>M</i>	250,80 G	250,80 G
Berl. Unions-Br.	3	0	do.	200 <i>₰</i>	70,60 G	70,60 bz G
Bock kv. u. neue	6	6	do.	1000.300 <i>M</i>	105 G	105,20 G

Figure 1: Prices of shares, Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (1913)

	ZF	Z.-T.	Kurs	El. Licht u. Kraft*	104 4 1/2	1/4/10	99,30bz	
A.-G. f. Anilinfabr.	105	4	1/4/10	---	102	4	do.	90,75 G
do. do. *	103	4 1/2	1/1/7	---	102	4 1/2	v.	99,50bzG 99,50
do. do. *	102	4 1/2	do.	---	102	4 1/2	1/1/7	99,50 G

Figure 2: Prices of debentures, Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (1913)

Yearbooks

Information in yearbooks is organised in blocks of text and tables. The first block, clearly distinguished from the rest of the text by use of a larger font, bold text or capitals, is the section title which identifies the issuer (company). Well-structured yearbooks start each subsequent block of text (subsection) with a uniform subsection title (see Figure 3). Subsection titles may be omitted, however, if the content of a subsection is in a narrative form which clearly contextualises the information for the reader. The Belgian *Recueil financier*, for instance, always included the date of incorporation in a sentence (e.g. “*Cette Société a été constituée à Anvers le 4 novembre 1884*”).

Darlehnsbank Aktiengesellschaft zu Augustusburg i. Erzgeb.

Gegründet: 1./10. 1889 als A.-G. Bestand seit 1866 als Vorschussverein e. G. m. u. H. u. firmierte von 1889--1899 A.-G. Darlehnsbank zu Schellenberg.

Zweck: Betrieb von Bankgeschäften aller Art.

Kapital: M. 200 000 in 192 Inh.-Aktien A à M. 1000, 40 Aktien B auf Namen à M. 200. Im ganzen M. 186 000 eingezahlt. Der R.-F. M. 69 930 wird besonders verwaltet.

Geschäftsjahr: 1./4.--31./3. **Gen.-Vers.:** Spät. Ende Juni.

Figure 3: *Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (1913-1914)*

Yearbooks may also include tables with multiple financial variables (for instance, securities prices, dividends, profits) for several fiscal years (see Figure 4). Balance sheets and profit-and-loss accounts present another form of nested tabular information. Financial statements, however, are particularly challenging in this respect. Unless the items were harmonised by the publisher, the number of different variables is endless as there was no regulation of financial reporting for over three-quarters of the post-1815 period. We therefore only include variables in these Variable Groups if the posts were harmonised by the publisher. Otherwise, we include Variable Groups without variables to indicate the presence of these financial statements.

ANNÉES	COURS ACT.		CHIFFRE D'AFFAIRES	BÉNÉFICES BRUTS	AMORTIS. ET RÉS.	BÉNÉFICES NETS	DIVIDENDE PAR ACTION
	PL. H.	PL. B.					
1925	520	430	2.246.103	1.055.913	36.986	97.390	10
1926	557	400	»	»	»	»	»
1927	480	S.C.	»	»	»	»	»
1928	»	»	»	»	»	»	»

Figure 4: Table with financial information (e.g. share prices, net profit and dividend), *Annuaire Desfossés (1929)*

Following the approach of Working Package 7, we created Variable Groups for each level, i.e. one Variable Group for the information in the section title (level 1), one Variable Group for the information in the subsections (level 2) and as many Variable Groups as there are tables (level 3) (Adam et al., 2019). For the example in Figure 5, the Variable Group at level one includes the name of the company (i.e. *Altos Hornos de Vizcaya*). The Variable Group at level two includes (amongst others): date of incorporation (*constitución*), purpose (*objeto*), registered office address (*domicilio*), fiscal year (*ejercicio*), duration (*duración*), capital (i.e. *capital*), shares (i.e. *acciones*) and allocation of profit (*reparto de beneficios*). For the information at level three (tables), a Variable Group with the title Tax-free dividends (*Dividendos libres de impuestos*) was created in this instance. This Variable Group contains the following variables: year (*años*), type of dividend (*dividendos*), net amount (*líquido*), total amount (*total*), percent of nominal value (*tanto por 100*), coupon number (*número del cupón*) and payment date (*fecha del pago*).

Figure 5: Levels of information, Anuario oficial de valores (1925)

4.2 Metadata elements

For each individual **Variable** (from printed sources and datasets), the following four metadata elements are included: Name, Label, Description and Representation Type. The metadata elements for describing variables are the same for datasets and printed sources.

4.2.1 Name

The VariableName element (Name in Colectica) contains the column heading or section title, exactly as it is indicated in the source document or data file.

Example: SHARES_NUMBER [source: *EIUROFIDAI Stock Daily Database*]

One of the common challenges of documenting variables from printed price lists are hierarchically structured column headings. Columns may be divided into two or more sub-columns (which may be subdivided even further) (see Figure 6). The headings of these sub-columns are meaningful if they are related to the headings of columns higher up in the hierarchy.

INTÉRÊTS ET DIVIDENDES			
exercice précédent (brut)	Dernier coupon payé	Brut	Impôts à déduire

Figure 6: Example of hierarchically structured column headings, *Cours authentique (Paris)*

In this case, we chose to precede the headings of the sub-columns by the headings of columns higher up in the hierarchy. Column headings are separated by space-vertical dash-space (|).

Example: Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Impôts à déduire [source: *Cours authentique (Paris)*]

If a column or section has no heading or title, we also leave the VariableName element empty and include only the Label element.

4.2.2 Label

The Label element contains a short description (a few words) of what the variable represents. For the documentation, we either took the label from the manual describing the data or created our own label if there was no manual.

Example: Company number [Label for variable G1, source: *London Share Price Database*]

4.2.3 Description

The Description element may contain additional details on the representation of the variable, if necessary, for the correct interpretation of the variable.

Example: Total number of shares available, used to calculate the market capitalization of the firm by multiplying the number of shares by the (unadjusted) price. [Description for variable SHARES_NUMBER, source: *Eurofidai Stocks Daily Database*]

4.2.4 Representation Type

The ValueRepresentation element (Representation Type in Colectica) describes how the variable is represented, i.e. defines the possible values of a variable. It can currently take one of these four values in Colectica: Code, Date/Time, Numeric or Text. Each type includes several subtypes – for instance, Integer or Decimal in case of Numeric data. DDI has controlled vocabularies for the Date and Numeric representations.⁶ These are included in Colectica, but neither DDI nor Colectica offers a Fractional Type for numeric variables. We therefore used Other in case of fractional notation of share prices.

The Scale, Measurement Unit and Aggregation Method elements are also important elements for describing variables, for instance in the case of share prices. The Measurement Unit element is used to record the unit in which the variable is measured. In case of a share price, this may be in a particular currency or as a percentage of a nominal value. If the share price is a highest, lowest or average price, this can be indicated in the Aggregation Method element. The Scale element is used in case numbers or amounts have to be multiplied by a factor to arrive at the actual amount or number. In balance sheets, for instance, amounts are often expressed in thousands; and during hyperinflation, German share prices were expressed in millions. In these instances, Scale would respectively be 1,000 or 1,000,000.

5 Quality assessment

5.1 Printed sources

Governance, financial market and accounting information is available in various types of printed serial sources. In task 4.4, official government publications (gazettes), stock exchange price lists and yearbooks on joint-stock companies and publicly traded companies were identified as the three main sources of long-term historical company data. The authenticity and accuracy of the information, however, varies.

Official **government publications** and **stock exchange price lists** have an authoritative character. In most countries, the incorporation of a joint-stock company is possibly only realised by public deed. The authenticity of the constitutional documents is guaranteed by the notary who served both as an independent and impartial witness to and custodian of the deed of incorporation and articles of association. To ensure their availability to third-parties, constitutional documents or excerpts thereof also have to be deposited in a public business register and published in an official publication with an equally authentic character. All modifications and amendments of the constitutional documents must follow the same route. To protect shareholders and third-parties, other company information such as the appointment of directors and plenipotentiaries and financial statements also had to be published in the same or specialised official gazettes. In the case of stock exchange price lists, the accuracy of the published

⁶ DDI Alliance. (2018). DDI Controlled Vocabulary for Date Type. Accessed 09/04/2019. http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-CV/DateType_1.1.html ; DDI Alliance. (2018). DDI Controlled Vocabulary for Numeric Type. Accessed 09/04/2019. http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-CV/NumericType_1.0.html

prices is guaranteed by official brokers who were appointed or confirmed by the government and equally served as impartial intermediaries to the transaction. The official or authentic character of price lists is reflected in their title (for instance, *Daily Official List* in London, *Officiële Prijscourant* in Amsterdam, *Cours authentique* in Brussels and Paris and *Boletín Oficial* in Madrid).

While some **yearbooks** published by stock exchange authorities (for instance, the London Stock Exchange's *Official Intelligence* and *Official Year-book* and Madrid's *Anuario oficial*) also claim an official character, they do not have the same legal status as official gazettes and price lists. This is equally the case for yearbooks published by private publishers. Yearbooks were published primarily for the convenience of investors. They bring together governance, financial market and accounting information about public and private issuers of securities or joint-stock companies. This information is taken from various sources, including the aforementioned official publications and voluntary disclosures by the companies, and presented in a uniform manner. Their broad and consistent treatment of otherwise dispersed data is not only the yearbooks' greatest strength, but also a weakness because it widens the margin for errors and necessarily involves the selection and transformation of information. Yearbooks, for instance, publish only a few prices for each security per year (usually the end-of-year and/or annual highest and lowest price).

In the following subsections, the preferred types of sources for different types of information will be discussed. In general, most types of information can be found in several types of sources. The differences between source types are not so much in the type of information, but in the amount of detail and the frequency with which information is published. The preferred source type is the source with the greatest amount of detail.

5.1.1 Identification

The unambiguous identification of companies is a core issue in the development of the EURHISFIRM infrastructure. This requires complete data on the name, legal form, incorporation and dissolution dates, registered address, purpose and identification codes (if these exist) of companies. Only **government publications** can offer the necessary degree of accuracy. Names in yearbooks are often translated and Romanised, for instance, or only the locality of the registered address and the year of incorporation are given.

5.1.2 Corporate board members and officials

Identification issues (homonyms, for instance) also arise in the case of directors, supervisory board members, managers and other company officials. This equally requires that as much information as possible is collected about each individual. This includes the full name, titles, profession, domicile and, ideally, date of birth and death and sex. While no evidence of the latter was found in any source type, **government publications** again provide a more complete set of personal data for identification and disambiguation of natural persons (including first names, professions, addresses, ...). In the Belgian case, for instance, the deeds of incorporation published in the official *Recueil special* at the end of the nineteenth century consistently contain the first and last name, profession and locality of the domicile of directors whereas the yearbook *Recueil financier* initially only published the initial and name (first name and locality of domicile were included more frequently from the beginning of the nineteenth century).

5.1.3 Equity and debenture capital

The initial amount of equity or share capital and its division in shares can be found in the articles of association. Any modification (increase or decrease) of the equity capital in a joint-stock company constituted a change of the articles of association. Consequentially, it had to be approved by the shareholders and published in official government publications. Some capital operations, such as the redemption of shares, however, could be effected without intervention of the assembly of shareholders and were also not publicised. **Yearbooks** therefore may present a more complete history of share capital than official publications. The same holds true for the history of debenture capital because in some companies, the directors could autonomously decide to borrow up to the limit set by the articles of association or shareholders. The number of shares issued or the amount of a debenture loan and numbers or amounts outstanding can also be found in some stock exchange price lists. Equally important in this respect is the amount paid-up on shares. As directors could call unpaid amounts, this is also not captured by official publications. The paid-up value of shares may be reported in price lists and yearbooks, however.

5.1.4 Market prices and dividends

Stock exchange price lists are the most complete source of information on market prices of shares and bonds and dividends. Yearbooks published prices almost exclusively on an annual basis (the monthly prices in the Madrid Stock Exchange Official Yearbook are exceptional). Daily prices can be found almost exclusively in stock exchange price lists and newspapers. If price lists are available, these have preference over newspapers. Because of editorial policies, the latter may have published only a time-varying selection of securities and prices (Hannah, 2018). Dividends and coupon numbers may equally be reported both in yearbooks and price lists. Important information such as the ex-dividend or payment dates are found only in some price lists.

5.1.5 Financial statements

The quality of historical financial statements in general is difficult to assess. Because of the absence of legislation and regulation before the 1970s, there is no contemporary standard for comparison. The only possible comparison is between the company's financial statements in their own annual reports presented to shareholders at the general assembly and the financial statements disclosed to business registers and to publishers of yearbooks. In the Belgian case, the official *Recueil spécial* is regarded as "the most reliable source of Belgian financial statement data for that period". The balance sheet and profit-and-loss accounts reported in the *Recueil spécial* were identical to the ones presented in the annual report to shareholders (Van Overfelt, Annaert, De Ceuster, & Deloof, 2009). The items and amounts of the balance sheets and profit-and-loss accounts disclosed in the *Recueil spécial* were also identical to those published in the *Recueil financier*. Absent regulation, it seems reasonable to assume that companies produced only one balance sheet and profit-and-loss account for external use and that financial statements published in annual accounts, government publications and yearbooks were identical. Only the French Desfossés yearbook performed some harmonisation of the balance sheets received from 1935.

5.1.6 Activities

While the articles of association contain a description of the statutory purpose or the mission statement of the company, they remain silent about the actual activities of the company. Yearbooks to some extent

may include a short chronicle of important investments, production figures, turnover, etcetera. More details might be included in the annual reports published by the companies.

5.1.7 Geographical information

Apart from the aforementioned registered address, geographical information is found mostly in yearbooks. The location of branches and production facilities such as factories, mines and quarries can for instance only be found in articles of association if they were contributed to the company in kind at incorporation. More details about subsequent acquisitions might be included in the annual reports published by the companies.

5.2 Databases and datasets

A questionnaire (Appendix 3) has been developed for the quality assessment of databases and datasets. This questionnaire addresses technical aspects of the data (applications and file formats), the coverage of the dataset (topical, spatial and temporal), the sources of the data and details about various types of information. Also important is the inquiry into the distinction between original and transformed data. A dataset might for instance include only returns (transformed data) or also share prices and dividends (original data). The constant progress of research methods and techniques necessitates the preservation of original data for future re-examination. EURHISFIRM should therefore focus first and foremost on the integration of datasets and databases with original data. All of the large databases surveyed (i.e. SCOB, D-FIH, EUROFIDAI and LSPD) store original data alongside transformed data.

6 Conclusion

Task 4.4 produced homogenous data documentation for the principal existing datasets and databases and characterized the features of a representative sample of printed serial sources on publicly traded companies according to the Data Documentation Initiative Lifecycle standard (DDI 3.2). The data and sources documentation shows the multiplicity of models by which historical printed sources have published data about companies and securities and of the data formats used by researchers and research projects for storing this data in datasets and databases. The challenge for Working Package 5 will be the development of an over-arching, common data model that enables the harmonization and integration of data from heterogeneous datasets and sources. Going forward, EURHISFIRM can expect to integrate largely populated structured databases with long-term historical data such as the Belgian (SCOB) and French (D-FIH) databases; other databases similar in character with more recent data such as EUROFIDAI and the LSPD; and smaller, less comprehensive datasets collected by individuals or small teams. Our selection of datasets ensures a representative sample as a starting point for Working Package 5. The data formats used by comprehensive databases which store information about securities, companies and persons can inspire the elaboration of the common metadata model, but are not comprehensive in the sense that they cover mostly the Belgian and French cases. EUROFIDAI and LSPD provide additional (inter)national data models, but they mostly store information about shares. Hence, there is still a lot of information to be gleaned from printed historical sources. Most variables or data elements found in printed sources are compounded by different types of information. A registered office address, for instance, may include a locality (city), street and number. Even more complex is a debenture loan which

typically consists of a name, class, total amount, number and nominal value of bonds, interest rate, interest or coupon payment dates, date of issue, maturity date, maturity premium, method of redemption, annual draw date, outstanding numbers or amounts and prices. Working Package 5 will decompose these complex data elements, identify them as static or dynamic information and develop controlled vocabularies for some elements.

7 References

- Adam, S., Adams, R., Annaert, J., Blanco, M. A., Battilossi, S., Bouvier, S., ... Yoo, L. (2019). *First yearly progress and strategy report to the General Assembly* (Deliverable No. D1.3; p. 56). Retrieved from https://eurhisfirm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/EURHISFIRM-D1.3_FirstYearlyReport.pdf
- Hannah, L. (2018). The London Stock Exchange, 1869–1929: new statistics for old? *The Economic History Review*, 71(4), 1349–1356. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ehr.12620>
- Van Overfelt, W., Annaert, J., De Ceuster, M., & Deloof, M. (2009). Do universal banks create value? Universal bank affiliation and company performance in Belgium, 1905–1909. *Explorations in Economic History*, 46(2), 253–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2008.07.001>

8 Appendices

8.1 Database questionnaire (Appendix 1)

Applications and file formats

1. What application (database or software) has been used to construct the dataset (e.g. Excel, Access, Oracle, MySQL, ...)?
2. In which file formats are data available (e.g. .xsl, .csv, .xml, ...)?

Coverage

3. Which entities, for instance corporations, persons (e.g. directors), securities, exchange rates, commodities (e.g. gold) or macro-economic variables (e.g. inflation, GDP, population figures), are covered by the database?
4. Which countries are covered by the database?
5. Which stock exchanges and securities markets (e.g. spot market, forward market) are covered by the database?
6. For which period (start and end date) are data included in the database (please specify for each of the covered entities)?

Original and/or transformed data

7. Does the dataset contain both original and transformed data, only original data or only transformed data?
8. How are original data distinguished from transformed data?
9. Can the original presentation of the data be reconstructed from the dataset?
10. Do the sources of the data contain original data, or did the compilers of the data source already perform selections, calculations and transformations of the data? For instance: the compilers of a stock exchange yearbook (the source) often select only one or two share prices (e.g. end of year or annual highest and lowest) whereas the stock exchange daily list (the original data) contain daily prices.

Issuers/company history

11. Which categories of issuers (e.g. government/public, corporate/private, industrials, domestic, ...) are included in the dataset?
12. What is the source of the data on companies/issuers (e.g. stock exchange yearbooks, articles of association, ...)?
13. What information on issuers (e.g. name, legal form, registered address, start and end date, mergers, acquisitions, production data ...) is included in the database?
14. Are data about the investment portfolio of issuers included in the dataset?

Persons

15. Which categories of persons (e.g. directors, managers, ...) are included in the dataset?
16. What is the source of the data on persons (e.g. stock exchange yearbooks, official publications, biographical dictionaries ...)?

17. What information on persons (e.g. name, first name, initials, titles, address, function, date of birth and date) is included in the database?
18. Are persons linked to issuers/companies?

Securities

General

19. What is the source of the data on securities (e.g. stock exchange official lists, newspapers, ...)?
20. Does the database include only a selection/sample of securities (e.g. blue chip stocks, common stock only, ...) or all listed securities (e.g. bonds, debentures and shares)?
21. How can securities be identified (e.g. name or unique identifier such as ISIN)?
22. Are securities linked to their issuers?
23. Are securities classified according to sector or industry? Which sector or industry classification is used (e.g. SIC)? How is the sector or industry classification implemented (e.g. subclasses grouped into broader categories)?
24. Are securities classified according to country of origin (i.e. the country in which the issuer has its registered address)?

Securities types and classes

25. Are different types (e.g. bonds, debentures, shares) and classes of securities (e.g. fixed rate, variable rate or convertible bonds; ordinary, preference, founder's shares)
26. Are definitions of securities types and classes available?

Securities prices

27. Which prices are included in the database (e.g. opening, highest, lowest, closing)?
28. What is the frequency of the price data (e.g. daily, monthly, annual)?
29. How are prices quoted (e.g. per unit, as a percentage of nominal value)? In which currency are unit prices quoted?
30. Were prices adjusted (e.g. for corporate events)? Are unadjusted prices included in the database in case adjustments were made?

Returns

31. Is information on the amount of dividends paid and/or interest rates included in the database? Are this gross or net returns?
32. Are ex-dividend dates, dividend and interest payment dates included in the database?
33. In which currency are the amounts of dividends given? Are returns given in the same currency as prices?
34. Is information on the taxation of dividends and interest (e.g. tax rates) included in the dataset?

Number and value of stock and bonds

35. Is the number of securities issued and outstanding and/or market capitalisation included in the database?
36. Are the nominal value and the amount paid-up on securities included in the database?
37. Are trading volumes (number and/or value of shares traded) included in the database?

Capital operations

38. Is information about corporate capital operations (e.g. for stock splits, reverse splits, subscription rights, attribution rights, ...) included in the database?

Accounting data

39. Are accounting data included in the dataset?
40. Which accounting data are included? Balance sheets? Profit-and-loss accounts?
41. Are accounting data transformed, either by the publisher of the original source document or by the author of the dataset?

Macroeconomic data

42. Which macroeconomic data are included in the database?
43. What is the source of macroeconomic data included in the database?

8.2 EURHISFIRM Data and sources documentation (appendix 2)

Appendix 2 first includes the data and sources documentation proper. This section, that starts on appendix page 1 and ends on page 185, contains metadata at the source or dataset level for the sample of printed sources and datasets and variable level metadata for datasets, but not for sources (lists of possible values for Code variables can be found from appendix page 136). The description of the main data elements found in selected printed sources (i.e. the source Variables) starts on page 185 of Appendix 2. If the DDI 3.2-XML file (<https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/WLOW0K>) is viewed in Colectica Reader, the contents of Appendix 2 can easily be located using the Navigator in the left pane of the screen. The full set of metadata on printed sources and datasets can be found under “Series” (printed sources) and “Studies” (datasets). The source Variables are located in a Metadata Package.

Throughout the data and sources documentation, symbols are used to identify the class of the items being described. These symbols are explained in the table below.

Symbol	Class	Description
	Series	A group of repeated studies
	Study	A data-centric study
	Dataset	A file containing data
	Variable Set or Variable Group	A set or group of related variables
	Variable	A reusable, logical description of a column of data
	Codes	Associates a numeric or alphanumeric value with a category

Table 1: Key to symbols used in the data and sources documentation

EURHISFIRM Data and sources documentation

Creator: Poukens, Johan

Publisher: EURHISFIRM

Contributor: Buelens, Frans (SCOB Database) ; Ducros, Jérémy (D-FIH Database)

Publication date: 5/22/2019 12:00:00 AM

Identifier:

 Prijscourant (Amsterdam)

Abstract

The Prijscourant, the official list of the Amsterdam Stock Exchange, was published by various publishers on behalf of the Amsterdam Stock Exchange's governing bodies since 1796. From 1 July 1876, the newly established Vereeniging voor den Effectenhandel took over the publication. It was published two or three times per week until 1897 and daily from 1898. The official lists initially included only the type, interest rate and price of securities. Prices were quoted with wide margins in Prijscourant as the lists only mention the lowest and highest price of the day. From 1813, quotations of the previous two days were also published. The closing price was mentioned in a third column ("Gebt.", abbr. of "Gebleven koers") for the most recent day from 1829 and for every day from 1832. From 1886, the previous price was also included. This was the mean of the highest and lowest price on the last day a security was traded. One year earlier, in 1885, nominal values and coupon dates had already been included and coupon numbers were added in 1898. In the 1920s, the Vereeniging experimented with the publication of more frequent quotations for frequently traded securities. The publication of the lowest, highest and closing prices was first substituted by the publication of the opening price and subsequent prices for four timeslots on 7 November 1924. This was later expanded to five timeslots in 1925 and finally to seven in 1929. For less frequently traded securities, the price at mid-day (11:30 until 12:05) was published. The turnover (in guilders) of the previous day was included on 10 September 1940.

Alternate Title: Prys-courant der effecten (1796-1828) ; Prijscourant der Effecten (1828-1842) ; Amsterdamsch Effectenblad (1843-1876) ; Prijscourant (1876-1952) ; Officiële prijscourant (1952-2009)

Publisher: Amsterdam : N. Cotray [etc.] (1796-1842) ; T. Geers Jz. [etc.] (1843-1875) ; Vereniging voor den Effectenhandel (1876-2009)

Publication date: 8/1/1796 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Beurs van Amsterdam - Amsterdam Stock Exchange

Amsterdam Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the Amsterdam Stock Exchange

EndDate

2009-06-30

Subjects

- Bond market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Amsterdam Stock Exchange
- Securities
- Spot prices

Temporal Coverage

1796 - 2009

Spatial Coverage

Amsterdam

Country

NL

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam)

Abstract

The Gids bij de Prijscourant was published on behalf of the Vereniging voor den Effectenhandel since 1890. It focuses mainly on financial information and much less on governance information. For each security listed in the Prijscourant, the official price list of the Amsterdam Stock Exchange, the Gids includes the class (for instance common or preferred stock), the name, the location and purpose of the issuer, and sometimes the date of incorporation, and the location and names of branches and subsidiaries. In the case of shares, there are details on capital such as the amount of authorised, outstanding and listed capital; the nominal value of shares; the amount of the reserves; a chronicle of capital operations (for instance new emissions); and dividends paid during the previous years. For bonds, the Gids includes amongst other things detailed information about redemptions. For both stocks and bonds, the annual lowest and highest price during the previous years are reported (the time span of retrospective information varies, but usually ranges between three and five years). Later editions of the Gids also contain retrospective accounting information for a limited number of companies in the form of balance sheets and profit-and-loss statements. No names of directors are included in the Gids.

Alternate Title: Gids bij de Prijscourant van de Vereeniging voor den Effectenhandel te Amsterdam (1890-1982) ; Gids bij de Officiële Prijscourant van de Amsterdamse Effectenbeurs (1983-1996) ; Effectengids : Gids bij de Officiële Prijscourant van de AEX-Effectenbeurs (1997-2009)

Publisher: Amsterdam : De Bussy (1890-1996) ; Deventer : Kluwer (1997-2009)

Publication date: 1/1/1890 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Beurs van Amsterdam - Amsterdam Stock Exchange

Amsterdam Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the Amsterdam Stock Exchange

EndDate

2009-12-31

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- Stock market

Keywords

- Amsterdam Stock Exchange
- Listed company

Temporal Coverage

1890 - 2009

Spatial Coverage

Amsterdam

Country

NL

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (Berlin)

Abstract

The newspaper Berliner Börsen-Zeitung mainly published prices of securities traded at the Berlin Stock Exchange (Berliner Börse, see below), information on the mortgage market, reports on national and international industry and trade, in addition to political news with an emphasis on the national and world economy. The Berliner Börsen-Zeitung printed the complete official price list (Kurszettel) of the Berlin Stock Exchange in its evening edition. The price list included information on securities prices, interest and dividends.

Publisher: Berlin

Publication date: 4/1/1857 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Berliner Börse - Berlin Stock Exchange

Berlin Stock Exchange

Securities listed on the Berlin Stock Exchange

EndDate

1945-04-24

Related Materials

Other

- [Berliner Börsen-Zeitung](#)

Subjects

- Securities
- Bourse
- Bond market
- Stock market
- Spot market
- Derivatives market

Keywords

- Berlin Stock Exchange

Temporal Coverage

1857 - 1944

Spatial Coverage

Berlin

Country

DE

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

 Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften
Abstract

The Handbuch is a joint-stock company yearbook for Germany. Each volume of the Handbuch contains comprehensive governance and financial information about both listed and non-listed joint-stock companies (Aktiengesellschaften in German). Companies are sorted by industry. The information includes: year of incorporation, purpose, capital, a brief chronicle of important events in the company's history (for instance, acquisitions and mergers, changes in the capital structure through capital increases or reductions and the entry of major investors), general assembly date, shareholder's voting rights and information on corporate boards, including the composition of the management board (German: Vorstand) and supervisory board (German: Geschäftleitung). In addition to governance information, the Handbuch includes data on the development of the dividend paid by the company, and in the case of publicly traded companies, also on the development of stock quotes (the last quote of the year for the previous ten years was included), as well as the stock exchanges where the shares of the company are listed. Detailed accounting information is available in the form of balance sheets and profit-and-loss accounts for the previous year. In some cases, there is also information on mortgages, workers, salaries and, if applicable, liquidators.

Alternate Title: Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften : Jahrbuch der deutschen Börsen (1896-1979) ;
Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften : Das Spezial-Archiv der deutschen Wirtschaft (1980-1998)

Publisher: Leipzig : A. Schumann's Verlag (1897-1911) ; Verlag für Börsen und Finanzliteratur (1912-1923) ; Berlin & Darmstadt : Hoppenstedt (1924-1998)

Publication date: 1/1/1897 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Aktiengesellschaften (DE) - Joint-stock companies (Germany)

Joint-stock companies (Germany)

German joint-stock companies (Aktiengesellschaften)

EndDate

1998-12-31

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- Stock market

Keywords

- Joint-stock company
- Listed company

Temporal Coverage

1896 - 1998

Spatial Coverage

Deutschland ; Bundesrepublik Deutschland

Country

DE

Country

PL

Country

RU

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

 Cours authentique (Bruxelles)**Abstract**

The Cours authentique is the official price lists of the Brussels Stock Exchange (French: Bourse de Bruxelles). It was published daily. Initially, it included spot prices (or bid and/or ask prices) of mainly public bonds, in addition to nominal values and interest rates. Over time, the range of quoted securities included corporate shares and debentures as well. Detailed information on dividends was added in 1873. This included the date, amount and coupon number of the previous dividend. The previous price and the number (or amount) of shares and bonds admitted to and circulating on the stock exchange were reported from 1878. Information about taxation of corporate bonds was included from 1924. The existence of multiple voting shares was indicated by means of an asterisk, finally, from 24 March 1930 until the abolishment of multiple voting shares in 1934.

Alternate Title: Cours authentique seul officiel (1883-1905) ; Cours authentique de la Bourse de Bruxelles (1906-1940) ; Cote de la Bourse de Fonds publics et de Change de Bruxelles = Koerslijst der Fondsen- en Wisselbeurs van Brussel (1940-1989)

Publisher: Bruxelles : Commission de la Bourse

Publication date: 1/2/1832 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bourse de Bruxelles - Brussels Stock Exchange

Brussels Stock Exchange

Securities traded on the Brussels Stock Exchange

Subjects

- Bond market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Brussels Stock Exchange
- Securities trading
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1832 - 2001

Spatial Coverage

Bruxelles

Country

BE

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles)

Abstract

The Recueil financier is a yearbook with summary governance, financial market and accounting information on companies listed on the Brussels Stock Exchange. The company information in the Recueil financier is extremely detailed, but poorly structured. It includes basic governance data such as date of incorporation, registered office, balance sheet and general assembly dates and names of directors and statutory auditors. This is accompanied by financial information on capital, debt, dividends and securities prices and a recent balance sheet and profit-and-loss account. Very interesting is the chronicle of important events which focusses not only on capital and debt operations, but also on the company's activities, investments, takeovers and mergers. Most volumes are accompanied by an appendix with additional information about managers and directors (Table alphabétique des administrateurs et commissaires), listing for instance their address and occupation. In addition to company information, the Recueil financier also includes information on issues of bonds by public bodies (states, provinces and municipalities, for instance).

Subtitle: Annuaire des valeurs cotées aux bourses de Belgique

Publisher: Bruxelles : Emile Bruylant

Publication date: 1/1/1893 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bourse de Bruxelles - Brussels Stock Exchange

Brussels Stock Exchange

Securities traded on the Brussels Stock Exchange

EndDate

1975-12-31

Related Materials

Other

- [Bronnen voor de industriële geschiedenis: Gids voor Oost-Vlaanderen \(1750-1945\)](#)

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- Public debt
- Stock market

Keywords

- Listed company
- Brussels Stock Exchange

Temporal Coverage

1893 - 1975

Spatial Coverage

Bruxelles

Country

BE

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

 Stock Exchange Daily Official List (London)

Abstract

The Stock Exchange Daily Official List (SEDOL) is a daily publication of official quotations for all securities traded on the London Stock Exchange. The contents of the Stock Exchange Daily Official List are remarkably stable. For every listed security, it gives the name, the number or amount authorised and issued, the nominal value, subsequent prices paid, a closing quotation, the interest payment date (for fixed income securities), the ex-dividend or ex-interest date and the interest rate or the amount of the last dividend. During and after the First World War, the official list also included the mean price on the eve of the outbreak of the war (27 July 1914). The Stock Exchange stopped printing this value after 1921. The figures for the number of shares authorised and issued are no longer reported after 1946.

Alternate Title: London Daily Railway Share List (1844-1866) ; London Daily Stock and Share List (1867-1898) ; Stock Exchange Daily Official List (1899-1930/1948-2003) ; The Stock Exchange Daily List of Officially Quoted Securities (1931-1947)

Publisher: London

Publication date: 1/1/1844 12:00:00 AM

Sample

London Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the London Stock Exchange

Subjects

- Bond market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Securities trading
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1844 -

Spatial Coverage

London

Country

UK

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Stock Exchange Official Year-book (London)

Abstract

The Stock Exchange Official Year-book was first published in 1875 by Thomas Skinner as the Stock Exchange Year-book. In 1934, it merged with the Stock Exchange Official Intelligence (first published as Burdett's Official Intelligence in 1882) and became the official yearbook (issued under the sanction of the Committee of the Stock Exchange) for the London Stock Exchange. It contains a mixture of summary governance and financial market information, including company name, address of registered office, names of directors and other officials and service providers, date of registration (incorporation), purpose and activities, authorised and subscribed capital (including particulars of shares such as class, number, nominal value and amount called, capital operations, other exchanges where shares were listed, share prices and voting rights) and debenture loans (similar details as for shares). Accounting information is limited to the duration of the fiscal year, the date of submission of accounts, and some details on the allocation of profits and dividends paid. No financial statements are included, however. In

addition to information on listed companies, the Year-book also includes particulars on government and municipal loans.

Alternate Title: Stock Exchange Year-Book (1875-1933) ; The Stock Exchange Official Year-Book (1934-1987) ; International Stock Exchange Official Yearbook (1988-1994) ; The Macmillan Stock Exchange Yearbook (1995-1997) ; The Waterlow Stock Exchange Yearbook : Including all Companies and Securities Listed on the London & Dublin Stock Exchanges (1998-2009)

Publisher: London : Thomas Skinner & Company (1875-1987) ; Macmillan (1988-1997) ; CaritasData (1998-2009)

Publication date: 1/1/1875 12:00:00 AM

Sample

London Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the London Stock Exchange

EndDate

2009-12-21

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- Public debt
- Securities
- Stock market

Keywords

- Listed company
- London Stock Exchange

Temporal Coverage

1875 - 2009

Spatial Coverage

United Kingdom

Country

UK

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Boletín de cotización (Madrid)

Abstract

The Boletín de cotización is the official price list of the Madrid Stock Exchange (Spanish: Bolsa de Madrid). Initially, it included daily spot prices of public bonds and corporate shares and debentures and forward prices (first or opening, highest, lowest and last or closing price only) of some public bonds, their nominal value and the amount paid-up on shares. Details on the previous price (date and quote in percentages) and on dividends and interests were added in 1903. The dividends paid during the previous and the current year were reported for shares and the interest rate and the date when the next interest payment was due for bonds. The total share capital in circulation, bid and ask prices and the annual highest and lowest price were added during the interwar period (1934 at the latest). Publication was interrupted multiple times, especially during the Spanish Civil War when no official lists were published between 17 July 1936 and 4 March 1940.

Alternate Title: Cotización oficial del Colegio de Agentes de Cambios (1854-1885) ; Boletín de cotización oficial de la Bolsa de Comercio de Madrid (1886-1972) ; Bolsa de Comercio de Madrid : Boletín de cotización oficial (1973-1989) ; Bolsa de Madrid : Boletín de cotización oficial (1989-1990) ; Bolsa de Madrid : Boletín de cotización (1990-1992) ; Boletín de cotización : Bolsa de Madrid (1992-2002)

Publisher: Madrid : Colegio de Agentes de Cambio (1854-1989) ; Sociedad Rectora Bolsa de Valores de Madrid (1989-2002)

Publication date: 3/13/1854 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bolsa de Madrid - Madrid Stock Exchange

Madrid Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the Madrid Stock Exchange

EndDate

2002-04-30

Subjects

- Bond market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Futures
- Madrid Stock Exchange
- Securities trading
- Share price
- Spot market

Temporal Coverage

3/13/1854 - 4/30/2002

Spatial Coverage

Madrid

Country

ES

Study Relationships**Datasets**

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Anuario oficial de valores de la Bolsa de Madrid**Abstract**

The Anuario Oficial and its successors are the official yearbooks of the Madrid Stock Exchange and, from 1943 until 1961, also for the Barcelona Stock Exchange. They contain summary governance, accounting and financial market information in a clearly structured manner. For each listed company, the information provided in the Anuarios is: date of incorporation; purpose; registered address; fiscal year; duration; details on capital (authorised and paid-up); details on shares and bonds (number of shares issued; numbers of shares; nominal value; date of issue; number in circulation and characteristics such as common, preferred or founder shares, and to bearer or registered); statutory rules for the distribution of profits; dividends paid; date of admission of stocks and bonds to the stock exchange (by issue); a brief history of capital, reserves and profits (in a tabular form); annual highest and lowest prices; last spot and forward prices of shares and bonds for the previous five years; the same for the previous year on a monthly basis; board of directors members; and the balance sheet and profit-and-loss account for the previous year. Other information in the Anuarios consists of the lists of stockbrokers active in Madrid, Barcelona and Bilbao, and detailed information on domestic and foreign government securities traded in Madrid.

Alternate Title: Anuario de los valores admitidos a la cotización oficial de la Bolsa de Madrid (1918) ; Anuario oficial

de valores de las bolsas de Madrid y Barcelona (1943-1961) ; La Bolsa de Madrid en ... (1962-1977) ; Memoria de la Bolsa de Madrid (1978-1989) ; Informe annual (1990-1994) ; Informe del mercado (1995-2002)

Publisher: Madrid : Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa (1918-1977) ; Bolsa de Madrid (1978-2002)

Publication date: 1/1/1918 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bolsa de Madrid - Madrid Stock Exchange

Madrid Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the Madrid Stock Exchange

EndDate

2002-12-31

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- Stock market

Keywords

- Madrid Stock Exchange
- Barcelona Stock Exchange

Temporal Coverage

1918 - 2002

Spatial Coverage

Madrid ; Barcelona (1943-1961)

Country

ES

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Cours authentique (Paris)

Abstract

The arrêté of 15 pluviôse an IV (4 February 1796) bestowed the price list that was published by the Compagnie des Agents de Change since 24 September 1795 with an official status. The Cours authentique was published daily. Its structure changed significantly over time with the evolution of the Paris financial market. The early official lists at the end of the eighteenth century contained mainly gold and silver prices, foreign and domestic exchange rates, and (spot) prices of government and a few corporate securities. Then, progressively, more prices were added. Forward and repo prices were included in 1840. In addition to prices, the nominal and paid-up value of securities and the "date de jouissance" (the date at which the owner began to enjoy dividends or interest) were also published in the official list. In 1857, the closing spot and forward prices of the previous day were included. The amount of the dividend paid during the previous fiscal year was included in 1862, coupon numbers and the issue price in 1866. Thereafter, new information was added only in 1920. The most important addition was the number of securities listed on the market for each stock. The highest and lowest spot prices of the previous year were also included. Moreover, a table of subscription rights and the Avis et Décisions (the register of the decisions of the Agents de Change, previously published separately) were reported at the end of the list starting from 1920. The Avis et Décisions reported the most relevant events about the stock market and the issuers (IPOs, SEOs, payment of coupons, splits, etcetera).

Alternate Title: Cours des effets commerçables à la Bourse de Paris (1796-1831) ; Cours authentique (1832-1892) ; Bulletin de la cote (1892-)

Publisher: Paris : Compagnie des Agents de Change

Publication date: 9/24/1795 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bourse de Paris - Paris Stock Exchange

Paris Stock Exchange

Securities listed on the Paris Stock Exchange

Subjects

- Bond market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Paris Stock Exchange
- Futures
- Securities
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1796 -

Spatial Coverage

Paris

Country

FR

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Annuaire Desfossés (Paris)

Abstract

The Desfossés yearbooks provide information on the issuers of securities listed on the Paris Stock Exchange and the Cote. For listed companies, the yearbooks publish not only governance information such as legal form, purpose, registered office address and corporate governance rules on the distribution of profits and the general meetings of the shareholders (including details on voting rights of different classes of shares), but also financial market information such as a chronicle of its equity capital. This includes both the original equity capital and all subsequent capital operations (increases or reductions of capital). It also contains information on their securities. Descriptions of both shares and debentures issued by the companies are provided. They also include the names and functions of all members of the boards of directors, simplified balance sheets and profit-and-loss accounts. Additionally, these yearbooks provide information about public issuers such as states, regions, départements or municipalities (for instance their financial situation) and the securities they issued.

Alternate Title: Annuaire Desfossés : Valeurs cotées en banque à la Bourse de Paris (1907-1949) ; Annuaire Desfossés-SEF (1950-1981) ; Dictionnaire des sociétés cotées (1990-1992) ; Dictionnaire DAFSA-Desfossés des sociétés (1994-1998)

Publisher: Paris : E. Desfossés (1907-1949) ; Cote Desfossés (1950-1998) ; DAFSA (1994-1998)

Publication date: 1/1/1907 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Bourse de Paris & Coullisse - Paris Stock Exchange & OTC market

Paris Stock Exchange & OTC market

Securities traded at the Paris Stock Exchange and OTC market

EndDate

1998-12-31

Subjects

- Bond market
- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation
- OTC market
- Stock market

Keywords

- Coullisse (Paris)
- Listed company
- Paris Stock Exchange

Temporal Coverage

1907 - 1998

Spatial Coverage

Paris

Country

FR

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

Giełda Pieniężna w Warszawie (Warsaw)

Abstract

The Warsaw Money Exchange published quotations for the most important shares in its annual report. For the most frequently traded shares, these annual reports provide nominal values, daily quotations, monthly highest and lowest prices, the average price, the total number of quotations during the month and an index number. In addition to quotations, the annual reports also contain some details on all listed companies. The amount of information varies between years, but generally includes: year of introduction, name in Polish and in French, nominal value of shares and the amount of capital and number of shares circulating on the exchange. For some years, the total amount of capital and total number of shares are also mentioned. For other years, the end-of-year price and total market capitalisation at the end of the year are included.

Alternate Title: Giełda Pieniężna w Warszawie : Sprawozdanie Za Rok ...

Publisher: Warszawa

Publication date: 1/1/1922 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Giełda Pieniężna w Warszawie - Warsaw Money Exchange

Warsaw Money Exchange

Securities traded at the Warsaw Money Exchange

EndDate

1938-12-31

Temporal Coverage

1921 - 1938

Spatial Coverage

Warsawa

Country

PL

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

 Rocznik Informacyjny o Spółkach Akcyjnych w Polsce

Abstract

The Rocznik Informacyjny was a joint-stock company yearbook with summary governance, financial market and accounting information. It was published for only two years in 1929 and 1930 in Polish and French. It lists for each joint-stock company (both listed and non-listed) in the Polish Republic: the name, the year of incorporation, the registered address, the names of directors, supervisory board members and managers, the location of branches, purpose, products and annual production or turnover, details on capital (amount of authorised share capital, nominal value and type of shares, e.g. bearer or registered), the stock exchanges on which shares are listed (if applicable) and a balance sheet.

Publisher: Warszawa : Polskiej Spółki Wydawnictw Informacyjnych

Publication date: 1/1/1929 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Spółka Akcyjny (PL) - Joint-stock companies (Poland)

Joint-stock companies (Poland)

Polish joint-stock companies (Spółka Akcyjny)

EndDate

1930-12-31

Subjects

- Corporate finance
- Financial statement
- Firm development
- Firm location
- Legal forms of organisation

Keywords

- Joint-stock company
- Listed company

Temporal Coverage

1929 - 1930

Spatial Coverage

Polska

Country

BY

Country

LT

Country

PL

Country

SK

Country

UA

Study Relationships

Datasets

No specified relationship

Instruments

No specified relationship

Language

No formal relationship - not a factor of grouping

Panel

No specified relationship

Geography

No specified relationship

Time

No specified relationship

British stock market returns, 1825-1870

Abstract

This dataset includes end-of-month share prices, dividends, capitalisation data (i.e. number of issued shares, nominal and paid-up value) and returns for common equity stocks reported in the Course of the Exchange, the official price list for the London Stock Exchange.

Creator: Acheson, Graeme G. ; Hickson, Charles R. ; Turner, John D. ; Ye, Qing

Publisher: Unpublished dataset

Contributor: Qu, Lei ; Vanteeva, Nadia

Publication date: 1/1/2009 12:00:00 AM

Sample

London Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the London Stock Exchange

Related Materials

Other

- [Rule Britannia! British stock market returns, 1825-1870](#)

Subjects

- Stock market

Keywords

- London Stock Exchange
- Share price
- Dividend
- Capital market returns

Temporal Coverage

1825 - 1870

Spatial Coverage

London

Country

GB

Funding Information

RES-000-22-1391

Data Collection

British stock market returns, 1825-1870

Collection Events

Mode of Collection

Share prices were collected manually from historical sources.

Action to Minimize Losses

Each stock price series was analyzed individually so as to pick up data-inputting errors or printing mistakes in the Course of the Exchange. If a share price was substantially out of line with prices either side of it, the Course of the Exchange was double-checked, and in the event that it wasn't a data-inputting error, it was deleted and the previous reported price was used as the current month's price. This, however, was extremely uncommon.

Data Sources

Course of the Exchange

The Railway Times

 British stock market returns, 1825-1870
Variable Count

15

 companyname - Company name

Type	Text
Description	A short name for the issuing company.

 companyid - Company identification code

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A number identifying the issuing company.

 industryID - Industry code

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the industry in which the issuing company was active. The classification is taken from the Course of the Exchange.

 Date

Type	YearMonth
Description	The year and month from which the values of the share price and other variables are taken.

 Dividend paid

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	This is the annual dividend per share.

 number of shares - Number of shares issued

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The number of shares issued is used for the calculation of market capitalisation and the total paid capital.

 nominal value - Nominal value of shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	Par or face value of shares

 paid up capital - Paid-up value of shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	Amount paid-up on shares

 price - Share price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	Last share price of the month reported

 mkt cap - Market capitalisation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	This is the number of shares issued multiplied by the share price at the end of the month.

 total pd cap - Total amount of paid-up capital

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Measurement Unit	British pound
Description	This is the number of shares issued multiplied by the amount paid-up value of shares.

div yield - Monthly dividend yield

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The monthly dividend yield for a share was obtained by dividing one-twelfth of the annual dividend by the previous month's share price.

cap app - Capital appreciation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Relative change in the share price, including price changes due to changes in the paid-up value of shares.

cap app_A - Capital appreciation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Relative change in the share price, excluding price changes due to changes in the paid-up value of shares.

Total return

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The total return of a share is the sum of capital appreciation and dividend yield.

Data For Financial History Database (Paris)

Abstract

The D-FIH Database was developed within the D-FIH project (short for Données Financières Historiques in French and Data for Financial History in English). It was modeled after the Belgian SCOB Database (with significant alterations and additions to make it more appropriate for the French case). The database includes information on securities and other assets (e.g. currency exchange rates and precious metals) listed on the official Paris Stock Exchange (Parquet) and the OTC market (Coulisse), as well as on their issuers from 1795 to 1976. The database includes bi-weekly prices (cash, forward, "reports" or short-term collateralised loans, and options), dividends and other information (such as securities transactions) necessary for the establishment of homogeneous price series over time. It also charts the legal history of the company (date of foundation and evolution of the legal status), the corporate governance rules, the registered office, the directors, simplified balance sheets, etcetera as well as information on public issuers (e.g. the budgetary situation and any guarantees). The data and sources can also be visualised online (<https://dfih.fr>).

Alternate Title: D-FIH Database

Creator: Hautcoeur, Pierre-Cyrille ; Riva, Angelo

Publisher: Paris : Paris School of Economics

Publication date: 1/1/2018 12:00:00 AM

Identifier:

Sample

Bourse de Paris & Coulisse - Paris Stock Exchange & OTC market

Paris Stock Exchange & OTC market

Securities traded at the Paris Stock Exchange and OTC market

Related Materials

Other

- Collecting and storing historical financial data : The DFIH project
- [Le projet DFIH : Humanités numériques et histoire financière](#)
- Financial History Databases : Old Data, Old Issues, New Insights

Subjects

- Stock market
- Legal forms of organization
- Financial investment

Keywords

- Balance sheet
- Board of directors
- Corporate financial assets
- Dividend
- Income statement
- Listed company
- Owners
- Share
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1796 - 1976

Spatial Coverage

Paris

Country

FR

Funding Information

Équipements d'excellence - EQUIPEX

Data Collection

D-FIH

Collection Events

2010 - 2018

Mode of Collection

As far as the data entry is concerned, two technologies were employed: the IT-organized manual data entry on the one hand and, on the other, a semi-automatic process based on a specific software.

The IT organized data entry concerns at least the official lists from 1796 to 1950. This data entry has been outsourced to a specialized social firm. Various teams of operators have been specialized by type of data (i.e. cash prices, forward prices, dividends...), in order to ensure satisfactory productivity.

The semi-automatic data entry is based on specific software developed in cooperation with a service provider. The specific software combines OCR techniques and artificial intelligence to learn from its errors and insert automatically the data into the database. It is used to capture and enter into the database all the information collected from the yearbooks.

Action to Minimize Losses

In order to target an accuracy rate of 99.99%, it has been decided to adopt a "double data entry": the same data are manually entered by two operators; in case of differences, a third person check the data out.

Data Sources

Cours authentique (Paris)

Annuaire Desfossés

Annuaire des valeurs admises à la cote officielle

 D-FIH Oracle Database

Publication date: 12/31/2018 12:00:00 AM

The database is managed by the Oracle system and organized according to the relational model. It consists of a set of interconnected tables. Each table corresponds to a storage unit. To date, the database contains nearly 150 tables (only the principal tables are documented here). The information is stored in lines (called tuples) and in columns, called attributes. Because the database stores long-term data, each piece of information is defined and valid within a given period of time, with a start date and an end date. A relationship between two tables is defined from a primary key, that is, from an attribute or a combination of attributes. Relationships between tables are not

all handled in the same way. In some cases, the primary key of one of the tables is simply added in the other. This key is then called a foreign key. In other cases, a join table is created with the two primary keys of the tables to be joined.

Variable Count

296

CORPORATION - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular issuer or organisation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This identifier ("CORPORATION") is used for any organisation (corporation, state, municipality)

NAME - Name of the issuer (corporation, state, municipality ...)

Type	Text
Description	Can have different names at the same moment as this field captures also TRANSLATED names

STARTDATE - Date of incorporation

Type	Date
Description	Can have successive days for every change of the name of the company

ENDDATE - ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

Type	Date
Description	Changes whenever a new location was identified

SOURCE - Source where the information was found

Type	Text
Description	IF THE NAME CHANGES, a new tuple is added by the operator in order to capture all information in the price lists

COMMENTS - Free comments

Type	Text
------	------

CREATED_BY - Identifier of the creator of the line

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This identifier refers to the table 'DBA_users'

CREATION_DATE - Timestamp of the creation

Type	DateTime
Description	It automatically stores year, month, day, hour, minute, and second values

LAST_UPDATED_BY - Identifier of the last updater of the line

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This identifier refers to the table 'DBA_users'

LAST_UPDATED_DATE - Timestamp of the last updater

Type	DateTime
Description	It automatically stores year, month, day, hour, minute, and second values

 LOCATION_TYPE - ID of the type of location

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'LOCATION_TYPES'. Might be "siège social" (headquarters), "usines" (factories); etc.

 ADDRESS - Street name and number

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

 City

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

 DISTRICT - District

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

 Country

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

STARTDATE - Day for which this information holds

Type	Date
Description	Changes whenever a new location was identified

ENDDATE - ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

Type	Date
Description	IF THE NAME CHANGES, a new tuple is added by the operator in order to capture all information in the price lists

DISTRICT_ID - ID of the district

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'DISTRICTS'

CITY_ID - ID of the city

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'CITIES'

COUNTRY_ID - ID of the country

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'COUNTRIES'

SOURCE - Source where the information was found

Type	Text
------	------

ACTIVEPASSIVE - Identifies whether the item was an asset or liability

Type	Text
Description	Always as it was officially registered

STARTDATE - Day of the balance sheet

Type	Date
------	------

ITEM - Particular name of the asset or liability

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always as it was officially registered

AMOUNT - Amount of the item

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

UNIT - Unit in which the amount is expressed

Type	Text
------	------

COMMENTS - Free comment, including the source

Type	Text
Description	If amounts are not in BEF or in EURO this is registered here

 INFODATE - Date of publication of the source

Type	Date
------	------

 PROFITLOSS - Identifies whether the item was a cost or an income

Type	Text
Description	Always as it was officially registered

 ITEM - Particular name of the cost or income

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always as it was officially registered

 STOCK - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	CAN HAVE SUCCESSIVE TUPPLES

 NAME - NAME OF THE STOCK, BOND etc as found in the official price lists

Type	Text
Description	This field captures also additional information on the type of stock (bond ..), interest, payment days, multiple voting shares (as can be found in price lists)

 STARTDATE - IPO day of the stock or bond

Type	Date
------	------

STOCKEXCHANGE - Identifier of the stockexchange on which the stock is listed

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	It refers to the table STOCKEXCHANGE

ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

SHARETYPE - The type of security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This can be anything, also inscription rights, bonus rights

STOCKEXCHANGE - The name of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

REFERENCE_STOCK - Either "Y" or "N"

Type	Text
Description	Takes the value of 'Y', when the stock is the result of a merger between stocks.

STOCK - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

CATEGORY - Industry code

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

STARTDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and industry applies

Type	Date
------	------

ENDDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and industry applies

Type	Date
Description	ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

STARTDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and issuer applies

Type	Date
------	------

ENDDATE - Last day for which this connection between stock and issuer applies

Type	Date
Description	ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

 EX_COUPON - The day for which the coupon was detached from the stock or bond

Type	Date
Description	This is not the payment day

 COUPON - Coupon number (and additional information)

Type	Text
Description	If available; additional information can be for example "talon"

 TYPE - Type of dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Can be for example "first dividend", "second dividend" ..

 DIVIDEND - Net dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 CURRENCY - The currency in which the interest or dividend was paid

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The number of the currency refers to the table in which all currencies are stored

 YEAR1 - Accounting year for which the interest or dividend is paid

Type	Text
------	------

 YEAR2 - Accounting year for which the interest or dividend is paid

Type	Text
------	------

 SOURCE - Source where the information was found

Type	Text
------	------

 BRUTO_DIVIDEND - Gross dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 TAX - Amount of taxes paid

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Filled in when the amount appears on the official list.

 TAX_TYPE - Identifier of the tax type

Type	Text
Description	Might be 'tax on dividends', 'flat tax', etc.

 ID - Identifier of a line of the table

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NAME - Official name of the currency

Type	Text
------	------

 COUNTRY - Name of the country to which this currency belongs

Type	Text
------	------

 ISO_CODE - Iso code of the currency

Type	Text
Description	Currency designator as provided by the International Organization of Standardization (ISO 4217)

 STARTDATE - First day for which the currency exists

Type	Date
------	------

 ENDDATE - Last day for which the currency exists

Type	Date
------	------

 EXACTDATE - The day for which the exchange rate was found

Type	Date
------	------

TYPE - Type of exchange rate

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'KIND_OF_RATES'. Might be "discount"; "interest"; etc.

NAME - ID of the name of the country / city

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'EXCHANGE_NAME'. Might be for instance "Belgium"; "Geneva"; etc.

MATURITY - ID of the maturity

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table 'MATURITY'

PRICETYPE - ID of the type of price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

RB - ID of the RB

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Three modalities : "(null)" ; "R" (when the exchange rate is expressed as a 'report') ; "B" (when the exchange rate is expressed as a "deport")

NOTE - Used when the price is expressed in function of the par value

Type	Text
------	------

ETMOINS - Either 1 ("Et") or 2 ("Moins")

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	2 is used when the exchange rate includes a subtraction in percentage

FOREIGN - Rate of foreign discount

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

COMMENTS - Free comments

Type	Text
------	------

SCALE - Used when a unit is indicated

Type	Text
Description	For example : "in %"; "per month"

Price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

TYPE - The type of number or amount

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Four modalities : issued, admitted to the stock exchange, existing, in circulation

STARTDATE - The day for which this amount or number is registered

Type	Date
------	------

VALUE - Quantity

Type	Text
Description	Three possibilities : number of securities ; amount (if capital) ; rentes. (see also the variable KIND).

CURRENCY - The currency in which the total amount issued is given

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	If a "value" is given

ENDDATE - The last day for which the amount or number holds

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new amount or number applies

QUANTITYFACTOR - Number needed to adjust the quantity

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Useful when the quantity of securities is expressed as a fraction

COUPURES - Either "Y" or "N"

Type	Text
Description	It takes the value of "Y" if the value is expressed for a "coupure" (denomination)

KIND - ID of the kind of quantity

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	It could refer to : Number of securities; Total amount (of capital) ; Rentes

STARTDATE - The day for which this nominal value is registered

Type	Date
------	------

VALUE - Nominal value or number of stocks or bonds

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

CURRENCY - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular currency

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the currency identifier in the table "CURRENCY"

FRACTION - This column tells whether the column "value" has a nominal value or not

Type	Code
Description	Has to be y (yes) or n (no) -- YES means : there is no nominal value, the value of every stock is a fraction of the total amount of stocks. No means: There is a nominal value

ENDDATE - The last day for which this nominal value is registered

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new nominal value applies

VALUES_TEXT - If more than one nominal value is registered in the official price lists

Type	Text
Description	This is often the case for government bonds with different coupures (for example 5000-2000) as registered in the official price lists

CORPORATION - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this corporation to the corporation in corporation_name table

OPERATION_DATE - Precise date of the operation

Type	Date
------	------

OPERATION_TYPE - Type of operation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Refers to the table "OPERATION_TYPES". For instance: 1 (split), 2 (reverse split), 13 (reduction of capital by reimbursement of stocks)

 ADJUSTMENT_FACTOR - Factor of adjustment computed by hand for every operation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 ADJUSTMENT_CONSTANT - Constant of adjustment computed by hand for every operation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 CODETYPE - The type of code for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example: 5 (ISIN code) , 11 (Eurhisfirm code)

 STARTDATE - The first day for which this code is registered

Type	Date
------	------

 CODE - The name of the code

Type	Text
Description	For example (ISIN CODE) : BE0003499077

 ENDDATE - The last day for which this code is registered

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new code applies

 STARTDATE - The first day for which this information holds

Type	Date
------	------

 TYPE - The particular type of stock

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	All types have a numeric value, which is connected to a table STOCKTYPES (not shown)

 ENDDATE - The last day for which this information holds

Type	Date
------	------

 COMPREF - Indicates whether this stock is a common or preferred type of stock

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular person

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NAME - Name of the person

Type	Text
------	------

 STARTDATE - Birth day

Type	Date
------	------

ENDDATE - Date of death

Type	Date
------	------

GESLACHT - Man (M) or Woman (V)

Type	Code
------	------

FIRSTNAME - First name

Type	Text
Description	Used when the first name is clearly indicated on the source

ID - Unique identifier for the link between a particular security and the owner for a particular point in time

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

PERSON - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular person

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the person identifier, called "ID" in the table PERSON

PERCENTAGE - The percentage of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 AMOUNT - The amount of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NUMOFSTOCKS - The number of stocks or bonds of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 ID - Unique identifier for the period for which a stock or bond was listed in a sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 SECTOR - Sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 OLD_STOCK_ID - Former identifier of the stock

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Used after a merger of stocks. This ID is the former ID of the stock; the new one is in Stock

 STOCKEXCHANGE_ID - Identifier of the relevant stock exchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NOTATION - Unique identifier for the period for which a stock or bond was listed in a sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

 DAY - The day of trading

Type	Date
------	------

 ARGENT - Bid price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PAPIER - Ask price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 OPEN - Opening price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 CLOSE - Closing price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

MIN - Minimum price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

MAX - Maximum price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

PREVIOUS - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Last price available

DATE_PREV - Day of the previous price

Type	Date
------	------

PERCENT - Price in percent whenever this was the case

Type	Text
------	------

MARKET - The market at which this price was quoted

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Five possible modalities : forward; spot; ancient options; options; temporary forward

 SETDATE - The settlement day

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 VOLUME - The number of stocks traded

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 OPTION_VALUE - The value of the option

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 EXACT_SETDATE - The exact settlement day

Type	Date
------	------

 PRICE_YESTERDAY - The price of the day before

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 OPTION_TYPE - The type of option

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 AVERAGE - Average price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

JOB - The function within the board

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	All functions are registered in a special table "JOBS" (not show)

SOURCE - The source where this information was found

Type	Text
------	------

OLD_PERSON_ID - Former identifier of the person

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Used after a merger of persons. This ID is the former ID of the person; the new one is in Person.

ID - Unique identifier that indicates the price order registered at a certain day

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Important as it registers successive prices

PRICE - The successive prices

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

OUTSIDE - 'Y' / 'N'

Type	Text
------	------

Description	Takes the value of 'Y' , when the price has been done outside the main market (most common case : after the official trading session)
-------------	---

MARKETDATE - The day when the security was traded

Type	Date
------	------

TYPE - Refers to the different possibilities for the repomarkettype

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

SETDATE - Refers to the exact settlement date

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

EXACTDATE - The day when the security was traded

Type	Date
------	------

PRIX - The price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

CURRENCY - The currency for the repomarket

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 SIGN - Refers to the different possibilities regarding REPORT and DEPORT

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 REMARKS - Free comments

Type	Text
------	------

 PRIX2 - Additonal prices

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PRIX3 - Additonal prices

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 EUROFIDAI Stocks Daily database

Abstract

The EUROFIDAI Stocks Europe database contains daily share prices of almost 85,000 common or ordinary shares listed on 214 stock exchanges in 37 European countries (Austria, Belgium, Bosnia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and Ukraine), and share related data such as market capitalisation, trading volumes and dividend payments. It also includes limited information on issuers such as legal form, domicile and industry codes. The historical data are going back to 1977 for France, and to 1980 for other countries.

Other EUROFIDAI databases, not covered by the EURHISFIRM Data Documentaion, cover indices, mutual funds, exchange rates and corporate events.

Publisher: Paris : Eurofidai

Publication date: 7/15/2018 12:00:00 AM

Identifier: <https://www.eurofidai.org>

Sample

European stock exchanges

Securities traded on 217 stock exchanges in 37 European countries

Subjects

- Stock market

Keywords

- Capital market returns
- Dividends
- Share
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1977 - 2017

1980 - 2017

Spatial Coverage

Europe

Country

AT

Country

BE

Country

BA

Country

BG

Country

HR

Country

CY

Country

CZ

Country

DK

Country

EE

Country

FI

Country

FR

Country

DE

Country

GR

Country

HU

Country

IS

Country

IE

Country

IT

Country

LV

Country

LT

Country

LU

Country

MK

Country

MT

Country

NL

Country

NO

Country

PL

Country

PT

Country

GB

Country

RO

Country

RU

Country

RS

Country

SK

Country

SI

Country

ES

Country

SE

Country

CH

Country

TR

Country

GB

Country

UA

Funding Information

CNRS UPS 3390

Data Collection

Eurofidai

Collection Events

Data Sources

Six Financial Information

Alternate Title: SIX Telekurs (1961-2012)

Euronext

Association française de Finance

 Stocks daily database
Temporal coverage

France: 1977-2017 ; Other countries: 1980-2017

Variable Count

77

 EUROFIDAI_CODE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Unique permanent identifier assigned by EUROFIDAI to each security

 QUOTATION_DATE

Type	Date
------	------

Description	Trading date
-------------	--------------

DAY_OF_WEEK

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the calendar day

STOCK_EXCHANGE_CLOSE

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the trading status of a stock exchange, which takes a value of 1 if the stock exchange close and 0 otherwise

DAILY_RETURN

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Daily holding return adjusted for capital changes and dividend distributions

DAILY_RETURN_REMARK

Type	Code
Description	Indicates if the adjusted daily holding return has to be used with precaution

DAILY_RETURN_REMARK_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit explanation of the reason for which the adjusted daily holding return has to be used with precaution

 OPENING_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Opening price

 WEIGHTED_MEAN_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Weighted average price

 LOWEST_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Lowest price

 HIGHEST_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Highest price

 CLOSING_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Closing price

 ESTIMATED_PRICE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Description	Stock price which, according to the various situations, can be defined in a different way
-------------	---

ESTIMATED_PRICE_INDIC

Type	Code
Description	Code associated with the choice made for the estimated price

ESTIMATED_PRICE_INDIC_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit explanation of the choice made for the estimated price

ASK

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Closing ask price

BID

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Closing bid price

SHARES_NUMBER

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Total number of shares available, used to calculate the market capitalization of the firm by multiplying the number of shares by the (unadjusted) price.

 TRADING_VOLUME_SHARES

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Transaction volume (number of shares traded), not adjusted for corporate events

 TRADING_VOLUME_VALUE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Transaction volume (value of shares traded), expressed in the same currency than the closing price

 CAPITALIZATION

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Market capitalization

 CAPITALIZATION_OBS

Type	Code
Description	Indicates if the market capitalization has to be used with precaution

 CAPITALIZATION_OBS_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit explanation of the reason for which the market capitalization has to be used with precaution

 ADJUST_COEF

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Adjustment coefficient for corporate events that have an impact on the stock price, used to calculate adjusted prices for operations on capital

 NET_DIVIDEND

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Dividend distributed, expressed in the quoted price currency

 GROSS_DIVIDEND

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Gross dividend, distributed dividend plus tax credit

 QUOTED_PRICE_CURRENCY_ISO

Type	Text
Description	ISO 4217 code of the stock quoted price's currency

 DIVIDEND_CURRENCY_ISO

Type	Text
Description	ISO 4217 code of the dividend's currency

 ADJUST_SUPER_COEF

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Description	Adjustment coefficient for dividend distribution
-------------	--

MONTHLY_RETURN

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Monthly return obtained by compounding daily holding returns for a security.

LAST_MONTHLY_DATE

Type	Date
Description	Date of the last available trading day for the security.

BEGDATE_EUROFIDAI_CODE

Type	Date
Description	First date at which the EUROFIDAI code is available

ENDDATE_EUROFIDAI_CODE

Type	Date
Description	Last date for which information is available for the corresponding EUROFIDAI code

SECURITY_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Name of the security

 VALOREN_CODE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	VALOREN code of the security

 VALOREN_CODE_EXPIRATION_DATE

Type	Date
Description	Date at which the VALOREN code expired

 VALOREN_CODE_EXPIRATION_REASON

Type	Code
Description	Reason for which the VALOREN code expired

 VALOREN_CODE_EXPIRATION_REASON_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit explanation of the reason for which the VALOREN code expired.

 ISSUER_CODE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Code of the security issuer

 ISSUER_NAME

Type	Text
------	------

Description	Name of the security issuer
-------------	-----------------------------

ISSUER_WEBSITE

Type	Text
Description	Issuer's website

ISSUER_LEGAL_FORM

Type	Code
Description	Legal form of the security issuer (expressed as a code)

ISSUER_LEGAL_FORM_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the legal form of the security issuer

ISSUER_DOMICILE

Type	Text
Description	Name of the issuer's domicile, attributed by TELEKURS

ISSUER_EXPIRATION_DATE

Type	Date
Description	Date at which the issuer expired

 ISSUER_EXPIRATION_REASON_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit explanation of the reason for which the security issuer expired

 EUROFIDAI_SECTOR_CODE

Type	Code
Description	Code of the issuer's sector, provided by EUROFIDAI

 EUROFIDAI_SECTOR_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Name of the issuer's sector, provided by EUROFIDAI

 SIC_SECTOR_CODE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code

 SIC_SECTOR_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the sector SIC code

 SECURITY_STATUS

Type	Code
------	------

Description	Status of the security (expressed as a code)
-------------	--

SECURITY_STATUS_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the status of the security

STOCK_TYPE

Type	Code
Description	Code for the type of stock

STOCK_TYPE_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the type of stock

ISIN_CODE

Type	Text
Description	ISIN code of the security (note that some ISIN codes are copyrighted, particularly those with the prefix "AN", "BM", "BS", "CA", "KY "US" or "VG")

BEGDATEAV_ISIN_CODE

Type	Date
Description	First date at which the ISIN code is valid

 ENDDATEAV_ISIN_CODE

Type	Date
Description	Last date at which the ISIN code is valid

 ISIN_CODE_STATUS

Type	Code
Description	Code for the status of the ISIN code

 ISIN_CODE_STATUS_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the status of the ISIN code

 ORIG_ISSUER_CODE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Code of the original issuer

 ORIG_ISSUER_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Name of the original issuer

 ORIG_ISSUER_DOMICILE

Type	Text
------	------

Description	Domicile of the original issuer
-------------	---------------------------------

STOCK_EXCHANGE

Type	Code
Description	Code of the stock exchange

STOCK_EXCHANGE_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Name of the stock exchange

STOCK_EXCHANGE_TYPE

Type	Code
Description	Type of the stock exchange (expressed as a code)

STOCK_EXCHANGE_TYPE_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Explicit designation for the type of the stock exchange

STOCK_EXCHANGE_COUNTRY_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Country of the stock exchange

 MAIN_INSTRUMENT

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Valoren code of the main instrument a temporary instrument is attached to

 MAIN_INSTRUMENT_NAME

Type	Text
Description	Name of the main instrument a temporary instrument is attached to

 DEPENDENCY_TYPE_CODE

Type	Code
Description	Code describing how a temporary instrument depends on the main instrument

 DEPENDENCY_TYPE_DESCRIPTION

Type	Text
Description	Description of how a temporary instrument depends on the main instrument

 ASSIMILATION_DATE

Type	Date
Description	Official expiry date of a temporary instrument

 PRINCIPAL_TRADING_LINE

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Description	EUROFIDAI code of the principal trading line
-------------	--

NUMBER_OBSERVATIONS

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Number of available observations for the security

Historische Geld- und Kapitalmarktdatenbank, Deutschland 1871 bis 1914

Abstract

This dataset contains end-of-month prices of ordinary shares (Stammaktien) of German companies listed on the stock exchanges of Berlin, Frankfurt, Hamburg, Leipzig, Köln and München, in addition to the total amount of the share capital and the annual amount of dividends paid. The dataset consists of 6 Excel-files (one per exchange) with 13 tabs each (one tab per industry, i.e.), in addition to a PDF-file (Anmerkungen.pdf) with the full name of the company (company names are abbreviated in the Excel-files) and additional information on capital changes, name changes and mergers. It also includes an MS Word-file with a short description of the data and a lengthy PDF-file with a detailed more detailed description of the database.

Creator: Eube, Steffen ; Müller, Johannes ; Weigt, Anja

Publisher: Frankfurt am Main : Center for Financial Studies (Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität)

Publication date: 1/1/2008 12:00:00 AM

Sample

Stammaktien - Ordinary shares of German companies

Ordinary shares of German companies

Ordinary shares (Stammaktien) of German companies traded at the stock exchanges of Berlin, Frankfurt, Hamburg, Köln, Leipzig or München

Subjects

- Stock market

Keywords

- Berlin Stock Exchange
- Frankfurt Stock Exchange
- Hamburg Stock Exchange
- Köln Stock Exchange
- Leipzig Stock Exchange
- München Stock Exchange
- Dividends
- Share
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1871 - 1914

Spatial Coverage

Berlin ; Frankfurt ; Hamburg ; Köln ; Leipzig ; München

Country

DE

Data Collection

SAFE-Historische Geld- und Kapitaldatenbank (DE, 1871-1914)

End-of-month prices were collected manually from historical stock exchange price lists and newspapers.

Collection Events

Data Sources

Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (Berlin)

Berliner Börsencourier (Berlin)

Neumann's Cours-Tabellen (Berlin)

Öffentliches Börsen-Coursblatt (Frankfurt)

Frankfurter Zeitung (Frankfurt)

Hamburgischer Correspondent - Neue Hamburgische Börsen-Halle (Frankfurt)

Börsen-Kursblatt (Munich)

Jahresberichte der IHK München (Munich)

Leipziger Börsen-Course (Leipzig)

Kölnische Zeitung (Cologne)

 Frankfurt.xls

Spatial Coverage

Frankfurt

Variable Count

3

 JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 MONAT - Month

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).

Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)
Description	<p>In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables:</p> <p>(1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12")</p> <p>(2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77")</p> <p>(3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")</p>

Berlin.xls

Spatial Coverage

Berlin

Variable Count

3

JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

MONAT - Month

Type	Code
------	------

Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).
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 Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)
Description	In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables: (1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12") (2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77") (3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")

 Hamburg.xls

Spatial Coverage

Hamburg

Variable Count

3

 JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 MONAT - Month

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).

 Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)
Description	In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables: (1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12") (2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77") (3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")

 Koeln.xls

Spatial Coverage

Köln

Variable Count

3

 JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 MONAT - Month

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).

 Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)
Description	In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables: (1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12") (2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77") (3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")

 Leipzig.xls

Spatial Coverage

Leipzig

Variable Count

3

 JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 MONAT - Month

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).

 Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)
Description	In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables: (1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12") (2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77") (3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")

 Muenchen.xls

Spatial Coverage

München

Variable Count

3

 JAHR - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 MONAT - Month

Type	Code
Description	A coded classification of the month (1-12) of the year during which the share price was quoted, with additional codes to indicate that the data refer to the amount of share capital (77), the amount of the dividend (88) or the number of a remarks in another file, Anmerkungen.pdf (99).

 Company name (abbreviated) - End-of month share prices, share capital and dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value in case of share prices and dividends, currency (Mark) in case of share capital (scale = 100,000)

Description	<p>In this dataset, each share has its own column with an abbreviation of the company name in the heading. The full name of the company can be found in the appendix (Anmerkungen.pdf). This column contains three variables:</p> <p>(1) the end-of-month prices (as a percentage of nominal value) of common shares (Stammaktien) during the month indicated (if the value of MONAT is "1" through "12")</p> <p>(2) the total amount (in 100,000 Mark) of share capital during the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "77")</p> <p>(3) the amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the dividends paid during the the year indicated (if the value of MONAT is "88")</p>
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London Share Price Database

Abstract

The London Share Price Database (LSPD) Source File contains monthly share prices of more than 10,000 common or ordinary shares listed on the London Stock Exchange (LSE) going back to 1955, and share related data such as share capital, capital changes and dividend payments. It also contains a historical record of all changes in names and Stock Exchange Daily Official List (SEDOL) codes. From 1955–1974, it comprises a large, representative sample of all companies and IPOs. 33 percent of all companies listed in 1955 were selected randomly. For each subsequent year until 1974, a random selection of 33 percent of the newly listed companies was added to the sample. From 1975, the LSDP covers all UK equities, including junior market stocks quoted on the Unlisted Securities Market (USM, 1980-1996) and the Alternative Investment Market (AIM, from 1995). A Master Index Files contains the names and SEDOL numbers (amongst others) of all UK companies quoted on the LSE since 1955.

In addition to the Source file, LDSP also contains Returns and Archive Files with derived data. The later are not covered by the EURHISFIRM Data Documentation, but are described in detail in the LSDP Manual.

Publisher: London : London Business School

Contributor: Staunton, Mike

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Sample

London Stock Exchange

Securities traded at the London Stock Exchange

Related Materials

Other

- [London Share Price Ispm201812 & Ispd201812 Reference Manual](#)

Subjects

- Stock market

Keywords

- London Stock Exchange
- Capital market returns
- Dividends
- Share
- Share price
- Stock index

Temporal Coverage

1955 -

Spatial Coverage

London

Country

GB

Funding Information

Funding Information

The London Business School Financial Database Project was set up in October 1972 with a grant from SSRC. The SSRC funding terminated in September 1978.

Funding Information

After SSRC funding terminated in September 1978, the London Business School Financial Database Project has been supported directly by the Institute of Finance and Accounting at London Business School.

Data Collection

London Share Price Database (LSDP)

Collection Events

Mode of Collection

The data is collected from a number of recognised sources.

Action to Minimize Losses

Where possible, data is taken from more than one independent source to provide checks on its accuracy.

Data Sources

Stock Exchange Daily Official List

Financial Times

EXSHARE

Publisher: Extel

Alternate Title: G records (General Descriptive)

There is one General Descriptive section for each share. In addition to general background information on the company, it contains various key items of data necessary to interpret the number of records contained in the other sections.

Variable Count

27

G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

G2 - Number of Capital Changes

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Number of records (type-2) in the Capital Changes section.

G3 - Number of Dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Number of records (type-3) in the Dividends section.

G4 - Number of Units

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Number of records (type-4) in the Units section.

G5 - Number of Years for Prices, Share Capital, Earnings

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Number of records in the Prices, Share Capital and Earnings sections i.e. the number of calendar years for which this data is recorded. There may be some missing data during this period due to suspensions.

G6 - First Year of Data

Type	Year
Description	First calendar year for which data is recorded (format YYYY).

G7 - Date First Entered Database

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The month number when the company's ordinary share was first included in the database, where January 1900=1 (e.g. Jan 1955 = 661 and Dec 2013 = 1368).

G8 - Type of Birth

Type	Code
Description	This information is regularly collected from Extel cards or the Capital Gains Tax Book (C.G.T. book). An indication of the reason why the security first came into the database and/or was first quoted in SEDOL.

G9 - Date Last Quoted

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The month number when the security was last quoted in SEDOL, where January 1900 = 1 (e.g. December 1984 = 1020). If the security is currently quoted at the end of the period covered by the database then the month number = 2000. IMPORTANT see also G12

G10 - Type of Death

Type	Code
Description	An indication of the reason why the security ceased to be quoted in the SEDOL.

G11 - Acquiring Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	If item G10 (type of death) is set to 5 or 6 then the company number (see G1) of the acquiring company is given. If the acquiring company is not currently included in the database as a live company, then this number will be negative. There are two special cases: -1 indicates that the company was taken over by a foreign company or a company not in the database, e.g. by a private company or a management buyout; -2 indicates that the company has been nationalised.
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G12 - Death Event Date

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The month number, where January 1900 = 1, in which the death event indicated by G10 occurred. In the case of an acquisition (G10 = 5), this date may be significantly before the date last quoted (G9), if a sufficient number of shares were not acquired for there still to be a market for them. In the case of a liquidation (G10 = 7), this date may be much later than the date last quoted, as a company's listing may be suspended for a considerable time before the company goes into liquidation. In the case of a suspension (G10 = 10), this date will be the month number when the security was last quoted in SEDOL. Item G9 will remain set to 2000, to indicate that although the security is not currently quoted in SEDOL, it is still a live company.

G13 - Sample and Index Constituent Indicators

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	<p>An indication of whether this company is a member of one of the seven historic samples (RND, L55, L72, A75, L76, T76 or BRW) or is an index constituent at the date of the file (eg YYYYMM 201812). This is a binary field where:</p> <p>1 (Bit 1) = RND: Sample (random) consisting of 33% of companies quoted in January 1955 together with 33% of companies granted quotations in each successive year until start 1975 when LSPD became fully comprehensive 2 (Bit 2) = L55: Sample of 500 largest companies in 1955 4 (Bit 3) = L72: Sample of 200 largest companies in 1972 8 (Bit 4) = 250: FTSE-250 Index Companies 16 (Bit 5) = A75: Sample of all companies quoted in January 1975 when LSPD became fully comprehensive 32 (Bit 6) = L76: Sample of 1000 largest companies in 1976 64 (Bit 7) = T76: Sample of quoted companies from "Times Top 1000" 1976 – data for companies entering LSPD by virtue of being only in this sample begins from start 1971 128 (Bit 8) = FTA: FTSE All Share Index Company(see also G18) 256 (Bit 9) = SEC: Secondary shares 512 (Bit 10) = IR: Irish companies quoted in SEDOL from Jan 1978 1024 (Bit 11) = FTO: FTO 30 Index Companies 2048 (Bit 12) = ODD: Odd foreign shares 4096 (Bit 13) = USM: Unlisted Securities Market 8192 (Bit 14) = 100: FTSE 100 Index Companies 16384 (Bit 15) = SFM: Specialist Funds Market from 2007; previously Third Market companies prior to 2000 32768 (Bit 16) = OTC: O.T.C. companies 65536 (Bit 17) = SPL: Split Trusts 131072 (Bit 18) = BRW: Sample of Brewery Industry from 1955-1974 262144 (Bit 19) = NUM: Numis Smaller Companies Index 524288 (Bit 20) = FLG: FTSE-Fledgling 1048576 (Bit 21) = AIM: Alternative Investment Market 2097152 (Bit 22) = OFX: OFEX</p> <p>Note: A company may be in more than one sample or index, e.g. a company in the Random sample and an FTSE All Share Index constituent would have a value of 129.</p> <p>To test if a company is a FTSE All Share constituent, the following FORTRAN statement may be used: IF (MOD(G13/128,2).EQ.1)</p> <p>The equivalent test in Excel would be = IF (MOD(INT(G13/128),2)=1,1,0)</p>
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Type	Text
Description	The current or last SEDOL number of the company as at the date of the file where the final digit is a check digit (for recent data).

G16 - SEDOL Group

Type	Code
Description	The SEDOL group for current companies.

G17 - Stock Exchange Industrial Classification

Type	Code
Description	The current or last industrial classification as previously recorded in the Stock Exchange Daily Official List or in the back of the Stock Exchange Year Book.

G18 - Financial Times Actuaries Index Marker

Type	Code
Description	An additional marker for all companies included in the FTA (subsequently FTSEA) Classified Indices. Negative number means company also included in FT30 index.

G26 - Primary/Secondary Share Pointer

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Where a company has more than one ordinary share, this pointer will give the COMPANY number of the corresponding other share.

G28 - Birth Date

Type	Date
Description	When the type of birth is available (G8) the birth date (format YYYYMMDD) gives the first date the security was offered for sale or for tender, introduced to the Stock Exchange, placed, issued, acquired in the case of a merger, or first quoted.

G29 - Issue Price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	When the type of birth (G8) and the birth date (G28) are available, the issue price quotes the first price at which the security was offered, when available.

G31 - S E Company Issuer Code

Type	Text
Description	A unique code allocated to each company, based on codes used by the Stock Exchange containing six alphabetic characters. A seventh character has been added to all codes to provide a check sum against input errors. This code can be used to sort companies by alphabetical order. The Issuer Code may be used as a cross-reference to Extel's EXSTAT and MicroEXSTAT Company accounts databases.

G53 - Actual Number of Name Records

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Actual number of name records for this company.

G54 - Current Number of Shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000
Description	Number of shares in snapshot month (live companies only) in thousands.

 G55 - Current Net Dividend

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Forecast Net dividend yield in snapshot month (live companies only) as per EXSHARE forecast rules, held in the form of a percentage multiplied by 100. The archive records hold a time series of dividend per share.

 G56 - Current Earnings

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Net (actual) earnings in snapshot month (live companies only), held in the form of pence per share multiplied by 100.

 G57 - Current Normal Market Size

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Normal market size in snapshot month (live companies only), held as the value divided by 100.

 G59 - Current Status Marker

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Status marker at date of file (live companies only), held as SEAQ Class*10 + Trustee Status; where: Trustee status marker = 1 for narrow, = 2 for wide.SEAQ Class: 1 Alpha 2 Beta 3 Gamma 4 Delta

Alternate Title: C records (Capital Changes)

The Capital Changes section has event-driven observations. These records are stored in chronologically sequenced lists.

Variable Count

12

G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

C2 - Adjustment Factor

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	<p>Factor by which old share prices must be adjusted to allow for capital changes.</p> <p>Format = true factor * 1000 (e.g. scrip issue of 1 for 2: adjustment factor = .667 * 1000 = 667).</p> <p>If the factor = 0, then the adjustment factor has not been calculated.</p> <p>These factors are not recorded cumulatively. To calculate adjusted price series they must be multiplied together.</p> <p>If there are two capital changes on the same day then the factors should be multiplied together.</p> <p>Note: In calculating the adjustment factor the fundamental principle is that the value of the company after the capital change is the same as that before. Whenever the ordinary shareholder is given something other than ordinary shares the problem is rather more complex. There are two stages to working out the factor. Firstly, the value of “the something” must be found and secondly, this value must be exchanged back into ordinary shares. At least two prices are necessary, the ex-price of “the something” and the cum-price of the ordinary share.</p>
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C3 - Type of Capital Change

Type	Code
Description	Indication of the type of capital change

C4 - Share Type

Type	Code
Description	Other type of share involved in a capital change where C3 = 2, 7, 8, 15 or 16

C5 - Status flag

Type	Code
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C7 - Variable – 1 New Shares/Amount

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	<p>Dependent on the type of capital change (C3).</p> <p>NEW SHARES Number of new shares issued by way of scrip or rights issue in relation to a specified holding of existing shares (see C8).</p> <p>AMOUNT Value in £ of shares offered in complex rights issue.</p>

C8 - Variable – 2 Old Share

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	<p>OLD SHARES Number of old shares needed to qualify for new shares issued (C7).</p> <p>e.g. scrip issue 1 for 2, old shares = 2, new shares = 1</p>

C9 - Variable – 3 Old Par Value/Ex Price Ord

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	<p>Dependent on type of capital change (C3).</p> <p>OLD PAR VALUE Par (nominal) value of the share, before the capital change, in new pence.</p> <p>EX-PRICE Ex-price of ordinary share involved in capital changes.</p>

C10 - Variable – 4 New Par Value/Premium/Ex-price Other

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	<p>Dependent on type of capital change (C3).</p> <p>NEW PAR VALUE Par (nominal) value of the share, after capital change, in new pence.</p> <p>PREMIUM Premium offered on new shares in complex rights issue, recorded in tenths of a pence/£ unit.</p> <p>e.g. 7.5p on a £1 unit = 75.</p> <p>EX-PRICE OTHER Ex-price of the other share involved in the issue.</p>
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 C11 - Variable – 5 Par Value New Shares/Issue Price/Cap.Rep/Am't Canc

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	<p>Dependent on capital change type (C3).</p> <p>P V NEW SHARES Par value of new shares issued (see C7)</p> <p>ISSUE PRICE Issue price of new shares in a rights issue</p> <p>CAP REP Amount of capital repayment in new pence</p> <p>AM'T CANC Amount cancelled in new pence</p>

 C12 - Variable – 6 Par Value Old Shares/Cum Price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	<p>Dependent on capital change type (C3).</p> <p>P V OLD SHARES Par value of old shares held (see C8)</p> <p>CUM PRICE Cum price of share in new pence on the day before the ex-date of a rights issue</p>

 C13 - Announcement Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) that this capital change was announced (when known).

Alternate Title: D records (Dividends)

The Dividends section has event-driven observations. These records are stored in chronologically sequenced lists.

Variable Count

10

G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

D1 - Ex Dividend Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) when share went "XD".

D2 - Pay Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) dividend paid.

D3 - Net Dividend

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Pence
Numeric Details	Scale: 100
Description	Net Dividend per share in hundredths of pence.

D4 - Tax Credit

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Pence
Numeric Details	Scale: 100
Description	Tax credit per share in hundredths of pence or, 0 if the dividend is not liable for tax. Thus, the gross dividend is the sum of items D3 and the absolute value of D4.

D5 - Special Marker

Type	Code
Description	Marker to indicate the status of the dividend

D6 - Year of Dividend

Type	Year
Description	Financial year (YYYY) on which dividend is paid.

D7 - Type of Dividend

Type	Code
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Description	Marker (NN) to indicate the type of dividend. Some digits can be combined (e.g. NN = 95 = Final and Bonus). The codelist includes possible single values of N.
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D8 - Conversion Rate

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Conversion rate for non-sterling dividends. Note: Nothing useful now held in this field.

D9 - Announcement Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) that this dividend was announced (or declared). The date will be set to zero if the information is either not available or prior to February 1965. From February 1965 to 1977 this date is the declaration date shown in Moodies (now Stubbs) Taxation Service. Recent dates are these as reported by EXSHARE.

lspmU

Alternate Title: U records (Units)

The Units section has event-driven observations. These records are stored in chronologically sequenced lists.

Variable Count

4

G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.
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 U1 - Date of Change

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) that the share changed to this par value. In cases where the precise day in the month is not known, we have chosen the 15th.

 U2 - Currency of Par Value

Type	Code
Description	Currency of par value, represented by the current ISO 4217 currency code

 U3 - New Par Value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (see U2)
Description	<p>Par value of the share in local units (including 2 decimal places), where shares with no par value have the value zero. In the past, the value zero could indicate a foreign share or a par value below 1 (before we introduced decimal places).</p> <p>Note: If there is a change in the type of share but not the nominal value, then a new par value record will record the new share type with the unchanged par value.</p>

Alternate Title: P records (Prices)

Price observations are collected monthly and there will be a record for each month the security has been on the database. Prices in old pence were decimalised with some subsequent loss of accuracy. As a major proportion of prices were either whole shillings or multiples of 3d the following conversion was used:

1d = 0p

2-3d = 1p

4-5d = 2p

6-8d = 3p

9-10d = 4p

11-12d = 5p

Variable Count

9

G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

P1 - End of Month Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) of the last trading day in the month. This is the day on which prices are recorded for each month.

P2 - Low Quote/Mid-SEDOL Price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	New pence

Description	<p>Pre-1978: The price in new pence indicating the low end of the official quoted range is given in SEDOL. No quote given if share is suspended. This price is also used in the calculation of market capitalisation.</p> <p>Post 1978: The price represents a mid-SEDOL quote.</p>
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P3 - High Quote/Closing Prices

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	New pence
Description	<p>Pre-1978: The price in new pence indicating the high end of the official quoted range as given in SEDOL. No quote given if share is suspended.</p> <p>1978-6/81: The price is the closing jobbers' price as given in the Financial Times, or 0 if not given in the FT.</p> <p>7/81-now: The price is the closing price taken from EPIC (Exchange Price Information Computer, set up by Extel and the Stock Exchange), or 0 if not available from EPIC.</p>

P4 - Transaction Price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	New pence
Description	<p>The price in new pence representing the last marked price in the month.</p> <p>In March 1981, when the format of the SEDOL was altered, the sequence of marked prices ceased to be given in chronological order. Since that time a price has been selected at random from all the marked prices, without any special markers, given for the last trading day of the month.</p> <p>If no price meets these criteria then the price after 2:15 the previous day is taken or, failing this, a price at some earlier date. Wherever possible, prices with special markers are avoided.</p> <p>In October 1986, the format of the SEDOL was altered back to a chronological order. Since then, we have been taking the last price of the day, avoiding special markers if possible.</p>

 P5 - Transaction Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) of the transaction.

 P6 - Low Quote Price Marker

Type	Code
Description	Age of P2 price

 P7 - High Quote Price Marker

Type	Code
Description	Age of P3 price

 P8 - Price Status

Type	Code
Description	Indicates the status of this price record.

 lspmS

Alternate Title: S records (Share Capital)

Share Capital observations are annual and there will be a record for each observation, starting at the base year (G6) and continuing for the number of years (G5).

Variable Count

3

 G1 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

 S1 - Date

Type	Date
Description	Date (YYYYMMDD) to which share capital data refers.

 S2 - Issued Share Capital for end December Each Year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000
Description	The number (in thousands) of ordinary shares in issue at the end of the year (31 December). This data was originally collected from the "List of Quoted Securities" published monthly by Frederick Mathieson. Certain small companies were not included and, consequently, no share capital could be recorded. Missing data is indicated by a value of -1.

 IspmN

The N records contain a historical record of all changes in names and Stock Exchange Daily Official List (SEDOL) codes. Observations are event-driven and records are stored in chronologically sequenced lists.

How to Read a Names Record

I've chosen the names records for LSPD company 1598 to explain how to read them – there are no SEDOL number changes but everything else including suspensions.

G1,N1,N2,N3,N4,N5,N6,N7,N8,N9

1598,19700115,19851115,"0268303",32,52,"0000000",1,"0268303", "Diamond Stylus Co."
 1598,19851115,19891015,"0268303",32,1,"0268303",1,"0268303", "DSC Holdings"
 1598,19891015,19900915,"0268303",97,1,"0268303",2,"0268303", "Mid-States plc"
 1598,19900915,19950415,"0268303",98,2,"0268303",2,"0268303", "Mid-States plc"
 1598,19950415,20060815,"0268303",32,2,"0268303",10,"0268303", "Mid-States plc"
 1598,20061015,20081215,"0268303",95,32,"0268303",10,"0268303", "Mid-States plc"
 1598,20090515,20111115,"0268303",95,30,"0268303",1,"0268303", "Mid-States plc"
 1598,20111116,20121115,"0268303",95,1,"0268303",10,"0268303", "Aerte Group plc"
 1598,20121126,20121126,"0268303",95,35,"0268303",20,"0000000", "Aerte Group plc"

The first names record starts during January 1970 (the YYYYMM15 format indicates that this is accurate to the month only) and N5=52 is the birth marker for “data collected prior to company entering database”.

During November 1985 there was a name change from Diamond Stylus Co to DSC Hldgs as you can see by N7=1 in the first record (and N5=1 in the second record).

During October 1989 there was both a change of name from DSC Hldgs to Mid-States PLC and a contemporaneous change of SEDOL Group from 32 to 97 – there is no specific code for this combination so we use N7=1.

During September 1990 there was another change of SEDOL Group from 97 to 98, as indicated by N7=2.

During April 1995, there was another change of SEDOL Group from 98 to 32.

During August 2006, the quotation was suspended, as indicated by N7=10.

During October 2006, we have N5=32 indicating a relisting after suspension and SEDOL Group change (from 32 to 95).

During December 2008, the quotation was again suspended.

During May 2009, we have N5=30 indicating a relisting after suspension.

On 16th November 2011 there is a change of name from Mid-States plc to Aerte Group plc.

Went into administration (N7=20) on 26th November 2012.

When shares are suspended, there may be short time gaps between the N2 date on one names record and the N1 date on the next names record.

Variable Count

10

G1 - Company Number	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	A unique identification number, allocated by us in a sequence from 1, for all British registered companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955. This number was allocated to overcome the problem of changing (and sometimes re-used) SEDOL numbers.

N1 - Start Date

Type	Date
Description	The first month (YYYYMM15) for which the record is valid (e.g. the month a SEDOL number is first allocated or the month in which a company changes its name).

N2 - Finish Date

Type	Date
Description	The last month (YYYYMMDD) for which the record is valid e.g. the month a SEDOL number changes or the month a company loses its quotation. This should be the same as the date in item G9. Will be 20291215 for all live companies.

N3 - SEDOL Number

Type	Text
Description	SEDOL number (see G15).

N4 - SEDOL Group

Type	Code
Description	The SEDOL group in which the company is classified (see G16).

N5 - Reason for New SEDOL

Type	Code
Description	This marker gives an indication of the reason this record was created e.g. allocation of new SEDOL number or a change of name. When looking at the first Names record for a company, this item will contain one of the birth markers listed in item G8.

N6 - Previous SEDOL Number

Type	Text
Description	The SEDOL number of the security before the Start date of this record. This field will be set to zero in the first Names record of a company.

N7 - Reasons for New Name Record

Type	Code
Description	This item gives an indication of the reason for this record being superseded by another or for the death of the company. In the last name record, for live companies this item will have the value 0 while for dead companies this item will take one of the markers listed in G10.

N8 - Succeeding SEDOL Number

Type	Text
Description	<p>SEDOL number of the succeeding share or company e.g. when a takeover has occurred, the SEDOL number of the acquiring company will be given. If the acquiring company is not currently included in the database as a live company, then this number will be negative. There are two special cases:</p> <p>"-1" indicates that the company was taken over by a foreign company or a company not in the database.</p> <p>"-2" indicates that the company has been nationalised.</p>

N9 - Company Name

Type	Text
Description	Name of the company for the period between the Start and Finish dates.

The Master Index is a comprehensive index of the names of all UK companies quoted on the London Stock Exchange since 1955.

Variable Count

11

M1 - SEDOL Number

Type	Text
Description	Stock Exchange code number (including check digit). See G15.

M2 - Birth Date

Type	Date
Description	First month (YYYYMM15) on which the SEDOL number applied. If quoted in January 1955 then the Birth month = 19550115.

M3 - Death Date

Type	Date
Description	Last month (YYYYMM15) that this SEDOL number applied. If record is current then the Death month = 20291215.

M4 - SEDOL Group

Type	Code
Description	See G16.

 M5 - Company Name

Type	Text
Description	Full name of the company.

 M6 - Company Number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	See G1.

 M7 - Sample Marker

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	See G13.

 M8 - Reason for Birth

Type	Code
Description	See G8 and N5.

 M9 - SEDOL Number of Preceding Record

Type	Text
Description	SEDOL number of preceding record, if any. See N6.

 M10 - Reason for Death

Type	Code
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Description	See G10 and N7.
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M11 - SEDOL Number of Succeeding Record

Type	Text
Description	SEDOL number of succeeding record, if any. Also see N8.

SCOB Database (Brussels)

Abstract

The SCOB (Studiecentrum voor Beurs en Onderneming) Database includes end-of-the-month stock prices, dividends, interests, ex-dividend day and the number of stocks for all stocks ever quoted on the Brussels Stock Exchange. It furthermore contains information on (corporate) issuers and person (for instance company directors).

Creator: Studiecentrum voor Beurs en Onderneming (SCOB)

Publisher: Antwerp : University of Antwerp

Sample

Bourse de Bruxelles - Brussels Stock Exchange

Brussels Stock Exchange

Securities traded on the Brussels Stock Exchange

Related Materials

Other

- [New Belgian Stock Market Returns: 1832–1914](#)

Subjects

- Stock market

- Legal forms of organization
- Financial statement

Keywords

- Balance sheet
- Board of directors
- Corporate financial assets
- Dividend
- Income statement
- Listed company
- Owners
- Share
- Share price

Temporal Coverage

1832 - 2017

Spatial Coverage

Bruxelles

Country

BE

Funding Information

GOA-BOF UA

The initial transformation of the Official Price lists of the Brussels Stock Exchange into an Oracle Database was achieved within the project "The Cataloguing and the Digitising of the Brussels' Stock Exchange Archive" (1/1/1998-31/12/2002). This GOA (Concerted Research Actions) project received funding from the Special Research Fund (BOF) of the University of Antwerp (UA).

Data Collection

SCOB

Collection Events

Intended Frequency

Monthly updates

Data Sources

Cours authentique (Bruxelles)

Recueil financier

Moniteur belge

Moniteur des Intérêts Matériels (and other newspapers)

Société générale Annual Reports

Fluctuations de la Bourse pendant une Période de Vingt ans 1835 à 1855 ou Statistique des Fonds Publiques

Creator: Commission des Agents de Change

Publisher: Bruxelles

Publication date: 12/31/1855 12:00:00 AM

Manuel des Fonds publics et des Sociétés par actions

Creator: Courtois, A.

Publisher: Paris : Garnier Frères

Répertoire des Sociétés par Actions dont les Titres se négocient plus spécialement en Belgique

Creator: Coppin, L.

Publisher: Brussels : Librairie de l'Economiste Internationale

Les Sociétés anonymes de Belgique

Creator: Demeur, A.

Publisher: Brussels

Les Sociétés commerciales de Belgique

Creator: Demeur, A.

Publisher: Brussels

Etude Historique des Sociétés Anonymes Belges

Creator: Frère, L.

Publisher: Brussels : Desmet-Verteneuil

Industriële Naamloze Vennootschappen in België 1819-1857

Creator: Laureyssens

Publisher: Leuven : Nauwelaerts

Publication date: 12/31/1975 12:00:00 AM

Sociétés disparues depuis 1873 jusqu'au 30 juin 1927

Publisher: Brussels : Keesing

Publication date: 12/31/1928 12:00:00 AM

La bourse et les agents de change, Etudes suivies d'un aperçu sur la lettre de change et d'une notice sur toutes les valeurs cotées à la bourse de Bruxelles

Creator: Limaige, E.

Publisher: Brussels : Office de Publicité

Publication date: 12/31/1864 12:00:00 AM

De ontwikkeling van de Naamloze Vennootschapsvorm in België tot 1914

Creator: Smets, F.

Publisher: Antwerp : University of Antwerp

Collection des statuts de toutes les sociétés anonymes et en commandite par actions de la Belgique

Creator: Trioen, L.F.B.

Publisher: Brussels

Publication date: 12/31/1839 12:00:00 AM

Manuel du Financier des Opérations en Fonds Publics et des Sociétés par Actions en Belgique

Creator: Van Damme, E.

Publisher: Gent : Verhulst

Publication date: 12/31/1859 12:00:00 AM

Guide Financier, Répertoire général des valeurs financières et industrielles cotées sur les bourses Françaises et sur les principaux marchés de l'Europe, de l'Amérique et des Indes

Creator: Vitu, A.

Publisher: Paris : Hachette

Publication date: 12/31/1864 12:00:00 AM

 SCOB Oracle Database

Variable Count

138

 CORPORATION - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular issuer or organisation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This identifier ("CORPORATION") is used for any organisation (corporation, state, municipality)

NAME - Name of the issuer (corporation, state, municipality ...)

Type	Text
Description	Can have different names at the same moment as this field captures also TRANSLATED names

STARTDATE - Date of incorporation

Type	Date
Description	Can have successive days for every change of the name of the company

ENDDATE - ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

Type	Date
Description	Changes whenever a new location was identified

SOURCE - Source where the information was found

Type	Text
Description	IF THE NAME CHANGES, a new tuple is added by the operator in order to capture all information in the price lists

COMMENTS - Free comments

Type	Text
------	------

ADDRESS - Street name and number

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

City

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

Country

Type	Text
Description	Can have successive names

STARTDATE - Day for which this information holds

Type	Date
Description	Changes whenever a new location was identified

ENDDATE - ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

Type	Date
Description	IF THE NAME CHANGES, a new tuple is added by the operator in order to capture all information in the price lists

ACTIVEPASSIVE - Identifies whether the item was an asset or liability

Type	Text
Description	Always as it was officially registered

STARTDATE - Day of the balance sheet

Type	Date
------	------

ITEM - Particular name of the asset or liability

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always as it was officially registered

AMOUNT - Amount of the item

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

COMMENTS - Free comment, including the source

Type	Text
Description	If amounts are not in BEF or in EURO this is registered here

PROFITLOSS - Identifies whether the item was a cost or an income

Type	Text
Description	Always as it was officially registered

ITEM - Particular name of the cost or income

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always as it was officially registered

STOCK - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	CAN HAVE SUCCESSIVE TUPPLES

NAME - NAME OF THE STOCK, BOND etc as found in the official price lists

Type	Text
Description	This field captures also additional information on the type of stock (bond ..), interest, payment days, multiple voting shares (as can be found in price lists)

STARTDATE - IPO day of the stock or bond

Type	Date
------	------

ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

SHARETYPE - The type of security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This can be anything, also inscription rights, bonus rights

STOCKEXCHANGE - The name of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

STOCK - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

CATEGORY - Industry code

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

STARTDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and industry applies

Type	Date
------	------

ENDDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and industry applies

Type	Date
Description	ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

STARTDATE - First day for which this connection between stock and issuer applies

Type	Date
------	------

 ENDDATE - Last day for which this connection between stock and issuer applies

Type	Date
Description	ALWAYS 31/12/3999 FOR THE LAST TUPLE LINKED TO THIS IDENTIFIER

 EX_COUPON - The day for which the coupon was detached from the stock or bond

Type	Date
Description	This is not the payment day

 COUPON - Coupon number (and additional information)

Type	Text
Description	If available; additional information can be for example "talon"

 TYPE - Type of dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Can be for example "first dividend", "second dividend" ..

 DIVIDEND - Net dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 CURRENCY - The currency in which the interest or dividend was paid

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Description	The number of the currency refers to the table in which all currencies are stored
-------------	---

YEAR1 - Accounting year for which the interest or dividend is paid

Type	Text
------	------

YEAR2 - Accounting year for which the interest or dividend is paid

Type	Text
------	------

SOURCE - Source where the information was found

Type	Text
------	------

BRUTO_DIVIDEND - Gross dividend or interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

NAME - Official name of the currency

Type	Text
------	------

COUNTRY - Name of the country to which this currency belongs

Type	Text
------	------

CURRENCY - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular currency

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the currency identifier in the table "CURRENCY"

START_DATE - The day for which the exchange rate was found

Type	Date
------	------

END_DATE - The last day the registered exchange rate holds

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new exchange rate applies

THIS_CURRENCY - The amount of the foreign currency that is exchanged

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example : 100 US dollar

CORRECT_CURRENCY - The amount of the BEF or EURO for which the foreign amount can be exchanged

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example : 100 US dollar = 512 BEF

 ARGENT - Bid price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PAPIER - Ask price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 TYPE - The type of number or amount (Emitted, admitted to the stock exchange, in circulation)

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 STARTDATE - The day for which this amount or number is registered

Type	Date
------	------

 VOLUME - The number of stocks or bonds is given

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always either "volume" or "value"

 VALUE - The total amount issued (if no number of stocks or bonds is given)

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Always either "volume" or "value"

 CURRENCY - The currency in which the total amount issued is given

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	If a "value" is given

 ENDDATE - The last day for which the amount or number holds

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new amount or number applies

 STARTDATE - The day for which this nominal value is registered

Type	Date
------	------

 VALUE - Nominal value or number of stocks or bonds

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 FRACTION - This column tells whether the column "value" has a nominal value or not

Type	Code
Description	Has to be y (yes) or n (no) -- YES means : there is no nominal value, the value of every stock is a fraction of the total amount of stocks. No means: There is a nominal value

 ENDDATE - The last day for which this nominal value is registered

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new nominal value applies

 VALUES_TEXT - If more than one nominal value is registered in the official price lists

Type	Text
Description	This is often the case for government bonds with different coupures (for example 5000-2000) as registered in the official price lists

 SPLITDATE - The day of the capital operation

Type	Date
------	------

 BEFORE - The number of stocks before the operation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example: a reverse split (5 into 1) gives 5 in this column

 AFTER - The adjusted number of stocks after the operation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example: a reverse split (5 into 1) gives 1 in this column

 SOURCE - Documents the type of capital operation and gives the source where information is found

Type	Text
------	------

TOSTOCK - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

CODETYPE - The type of code for a particular security

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	For example: 5 (ISIN code) , 11 (Eurhisfirm code)

STARTDATE - The first day for which this code is registered

Type	Date
------	------

CODE - The name of the code

Type	Text
Description	For example (ISIN CODE) : BE0003499077

ENDDATE - The last day for which this code is registered

Type	Date
Description	This day is identical to the next day for which a new code applies

STARTDATE - The first day for which this information holds

Type	Date
------	------

TYPE - The particular type of stock

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	All types have a numeric value, which is connected to a table STOCKTYPES (not shown)

ENDDATE - The last day for which this information holds

Type	Date
------	------

COMPREF - Indicates whether this stock is a common or preferred type of stock

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

ID - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular person

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

NAME - Name of the person

Type	Text
------	------

STARTDATE - Birth day

Type	Date
------	------

ENDDATE - Date of death

Type	Date
------	------

GESLACHT - Man (M) or Woman (V)

Type	Code
------	------

ID - Unique identifier for the link between a particular security and the owner for a particular point in time

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

PERSON - UNIQUE IDENTIFIER for a particular person

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the person identifier, called "ID" in the table PERSON

PERCENTAGE - The percentage of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

AMOUNT - The amount of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NUMOFSTOCKS - The number of stocks or bonds of this particular security in the possession of this person or corporation

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 ID - Unique identifier for the period for which a stock or bond was listed in a sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 SECTOR - Sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 NOTATION - Unique identifier for the period for which a stock or bond was listed in a sub-sector of the stockexchange

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Connects this identifier to the stock_name identifier, called "STOCK"

 DAY - The day of trading

Type	Date
------	------

 ARGENT - Bid price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PAPIER - Ask price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 OPEN - Opening price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 CLOSE - Closing price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 MIN - Minimum price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 MAX - Maximum price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PREVIOUS - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	Last price available

 EXTERN - Prices from other sources than the official price list

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 PERCENT - Indicates whether the price is a real one or a percentage of nominal value

Type	Code
------	------

 INDICATIEF - A price proposed by the stock exchange commission

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 JOB - The function within the board

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	All functions are registered in a special table "JOBS" (not show)

 SOURCE - The source where this information was found

Type	Text
------	------

Code Lists

 Share existing (Turner et al.) - Codelist for share existing

Codelist for share existing

1	True
0	False

 Daily return remark (Eurofidai) - Codelist for DAILY_RETURN_REMARK

Codelist for DAILY_RETURN_REMARK

1	The holding return is calculated with the opening price
6	
7	The holding return is not calculated, because there are more than 10 days from the previous trading days
8	The holding return is not calculated due to missing information
9	The holding return is not calculated for non-common-stock equity securities

 Estimated price indicator (Eurofidai) - Codelist for ESTIMATED_PRICE_INDIC

Codelist for ESTIMATED_PRICE_INDIC

100	Valeur Telekurs trade
-----	-----------------------

 Capitalization observation (Eurofidai) - Codelist for CAPITALIZATION_OBS

Codelist for CAPITALIZATION_OBS

1	The market capitalization is calculated with the opening price
---	--

 Valoren code expiration reason (Eurofidai) - Codelist for VALOREN_CODE_EXPIRATION_REASON

Codelist for VALOREN_CODE_EXPIRATION_REASON

1	Rectification
2	Maturity

3	Call in of claims
4	Early Redemption
5	Other events
6	Capital reduction
7	Split
8	Reverse split
9	Merger
10	Demerger
11	Separation of units
12	Consolidation in units
13	Exchange
15	Assimilation
16	Invalidation/stopping
17	Dissolution of company
18	Reorganization
19	Change of nominal value
20	Repurchase of own securities
23	Provocative deletion
24	Issue withdrawn
25	Conversion / Exercise

 Issuer legal form (Eurofidai) - Codelist for ISSUER_LEGAL_FORM

Codelist for ISSUER_LEGAL_FORM

1	Corporation
2	Co-operative
3	Society/association
4	Contract (Mutual Funds, FCP)
5	Foundation
6	Insti.incorp.under public law

7	Co. with fixed capital (SICAF)
8	Co. with variable capital (UIT,SICAV)
12	Limited company/Limited liability company
13	No proper legal form, branch
14	No proper legal form, admin. inst.
15	Limited Partnership
16	KgaA Kommanditgesellschaft auf Aktien
17	Investment foundation (CH)
18	OEIC
19	European public limited-liability co. (SE)
99	Other type of institution

Issuer expiration reason (Eurofidai) - Codelist for ISSUER_EXPIRATION_REASON

Codelist for ISSUER_EXPIRATION_REASON

1	Rectification
2	Merger
3	Demerger
4	Reorganization
5	Forced/debt restructuring
6	Voluntary liquidation
7	Change of domicile
8	Change of name

Eurofidai Sector Code (Eurofidai) - Codelist for EUROFIDAI_SECTOR_CODE

Codelist for EUROFIDAI_SECTOR_CODE

The first two-digits of the EUROFIDAI sector codes refer to the general sector while the last two-digits indicates its sub-sector.

0100	Energy
------	--------

0134	Petroleum/Oil and natural gas
0200	Materials
0221	Mining, coal and steel
0222	Aluminium
0223	Non-ferrous metals
0226	Precious metals and precious stones
0229	Building materials and building industry
0231	Forestry, paper and forest products
0235	Chemicals
0275	Packaging industries
0300	Industrials
0341	Electrical appliances and components
0343	Aeronautic and astronautic industry
0348	Mechanical engineering and industrial equip.
0350	Vehicles
0389	Traffic and Transportation
0391	Environmental services and recycling
0396	Miscellaneous services
0400	Consumer Discretionary
0447	Watch and clock industry, jewellery
0452	Rubber and tires
0468	Textiles, garments and leather goods
0470	Photographic and optics
0471	Miscellaneous consumer goods
0472	Various capital goods
0473	Graphics, publishing and printing media
0495	Lodging and catering ind., leisure facilities
0500	Consumer Staples
0533	Agriculture and fishery
0561	Food and soft drinks

0564	Tobacco and alcoholic beverages
0576	Retail trade and department stores
0579	Miscellaneous trading companies
0600	Health Care
0637	Biotechnology
0666	Pharmaceuticals cosmetics and med. products
0688	Healthcare and social services
0700	Financials
0757	Real estate
0781	Banks and other credit institutions
0782	Mortgage and funding institutions (MBS, ABS)
0784	Financial, investment and other diversified comp.
0786	Insurance companies
0800	Information Technology
0842	Electronics and semiconductors
0844	Internet, software and IT services
0845	Computer hardware and networking
0900	Telecommunication Services
0994	Telecommunication
1000	Utilities
1092	Energy and water supply
1100	Non-classifiable
1101	Countries and central governments
1102	Cantons, federal states, provinces etc.
1103	Cities, municipal authorities
1111	Public, non-profit institutions
1115	Supranational organisations
1119	Investment trusts/funds and provisioning inst.
1120	Investment conduits (inactive)
1185	Issuance centres (inactive)

1197	Conglomerates (inactive)
1198	Non-classifiable/non-classified institutions

Security status (Eurofidai) - Codelist for SECURITY_STATUS

Codelist for SECURITY_STATUS

4	Inactive
7	In liquidation/dissolution: The instrument will be taken back following the sale of the company's or fund's assets and subsequent dissolution/liquidation.
8	Active

Stock type (Eurofidai) - Codelist for STOCK_TYPE

Codelist for STOCK_TYPE

1	Preferred stock: Shares which give their holders priority of claim over the holders of other share categories, mainly with regard to the distribution of profits or in the event of the company's liquidation and the exercise of rights. Include also preference shares.
2	Common stock: An ordinary share gives the right to its owner to share in the profits of the company (dividends) and to vote at general meetings of the company. Also includes Company shares and Capital share.
4	VVPR Share: Share with special fiscal advantages and reduced withholding taxes (i.e. in Belgium).

5	Participating share dividend: Share of a company (e.g. in Belgium) with rights only to dividend or a part of the annual benefit distributed by this one and to the reserve benefits in case of dissolution of the company. Generally emitted in a capital growth action in order to recompense the new shareholders. Usually attributed to the first subscribers, this kind of
6	Founder's share : Beneficial part often given to the founders of a company and usually give rights to only part of the benefits. They are attributed to the founders of a company for their qualities or in remuneration of immaterial contributions (knowledge, relations, etc.) and differ from the other types of shares by one or another advantage.
7	Profit-sharing certificate : Share of a company with right only to a quote-part of its assets in the event of liquidation; it also gives sometimes right to a surplus dividend. They are distributed free of charges to the stockholders of redeemed (repurchased) capital shares.
8	Deferred Share : This share provided its holders with large dividend pay outs only after all other classes of shareholders are paid. Holders of deferred shares had access to all the remaining profits after all obligations were met. Subordinate to all other classes of common and preferred stock, these shares are last in line when a company goes bankrupt and liquidates all assets.
99	Other types of equity : Other types of equities not classified and units in terms of a compound of equities.

 ISIN code status (Eurofidai) - Codelist for ISIN_CODE_STATUS

Codelist for ISIN_CODE_STATUS

1	Reserved
2	Active
3	Deleted

4	Reactivated
5	Change pending: The status 'Change pending' means that a change of the ISIN/NSIN has been announced but has not yet been carried out.

 Stock exchange (Eurofidai) - Codelist for STOCK_EXCHANGE

Codelist for STOCK_EXCHANGE

10050	Wiener Boerse
10758	Wiener Boerse AG, OTC Trades EUR
11523	Global Market, Vienna Stock Exchange AG
10418	Erste Bank Wien
10759	Wiener Boerse AG, OTC Trades FXR
16752	Euronext - Growth Brussels
16755	Euronext-Trading Facility Brussels
16754	Euronext - Access Brussels
13015	Openbare Veiling-Vente Publique
10006	NYSE Euronext Brussels
10827	Banja Luka Stock Exchange
10828	Sarajevo Stock Exchange
10308	Bulgarian Stock Exchange
11000	Bulgarian Stock Exchange OTC, BGN
10541	Zagreb Stock Exchange, OTC
11026	Zagreb Stock Exchange, MTF
10313	Zagreb Stock Exchange
10299	Cyprus Stock Exchange
10276	Prague Stock Exchange, Block Trades
10320	Prague Stock Exchange, SPAD
11142	Equity Mid Market MTF
10170	Prague Stock Exchange
10284	Prague RMS (Registracni Misto System)

11004	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Copenhagen First North
10012	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Copenhagen Equities
10303	NASDAQ OMX Tallinn Stock Exchange
11018	NASDAQ OMX Baltic Exchange, Tallinn First North
10040	Nasdaq OMX Nordic Exchange, Helsinki Equities
11007	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Finland First North
10030	BOURSE DE BORDEAUX
10032	BOURSE DE LILLE
10027	BOURSE DE LYON
10028	BOURSE DE MARSEILLE
10029	BOURSE DE NANCY
10031	BOURSE DE NANTES
10025	NYSE Euronext Paris
11118	SG SI
10399	NYSE Euronext Cash Markets and Indices
16809	Euronext - Access Paris
16808	Euronext - Growth Paris
10559	NASDAQ Deutschland
12779	Tradegate Exchange GmbH
10018	Boerse Berlin
16829	Boerse Duesseldorf AG - Quotrix
10014	Boerse Duesseldorf AG
12913	LANG and SCHWARZ Tradecenter AG and Co.KG
10377	NEWEX
10863	New Market Xetra
10864	New Market
11032	Xetra International Market
10516	Xetra US Stars
10044	Xetra

10013	Xetra Frankfurt
11395	Boerse Frankfurt - Post Trade
10021	Eurex
11394	Xetra - Post Trade
10528	Xetra European Stars
10739	Deutsche Boerse AG, OTC Trades FXR
11390	APA Post-Trade Report - Equ and Equ-like Products, Currency EUR
10738	Deutsche Boerse AG, OTC Trades EUR
10017	Hanseatische Wertpapierboerse
10019	Niedersaechsische Boerse zu Hannover
10015	Bayerische Boerse
10016	Boerse Stuttgart AG
10745	Boerse Stuttgart AG, OTC Trades FXR
10521	Boerse Stuttgart AG - EUWAX
10744	Boerse Stuttgart AG, OTC Trades EUR
13319	Baader Bank Aktiengesellschaft
10388	Athens Derivatives Market
10034	Athens Stock Exchange
13135	Quote MTF Ltd.
10213	Budapest Stock Exchange
10770	Budapest Stock Exchange, Derivatives
10370	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Iceland Equities
11014	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Iceland First North
20269	SM CO MK IRL
10747	Irish Stock Exchange, OTC Trades EUR
11522	Irish Stock Exchange OTC, Currency EUR
11033	Irish Stock Exchange Xetra
20271	NC IRLANDE
10042	Mercato dei Derivati
10773	Borsa Italiana S.p.A., External Trades

10653	Euro TLX
10640	TLX Milano
10800	Mercato Affari Italia, After-Hours Trading
10041	Mercato Telematico delle Obbligazioni
10046	Mercato Continuo Italiano
10865	NUOVO MERCATO MILANO
11017	NASDAQ OMX Baltic Exchange First North
10306	NASDAQ OMX Riga Stock Exchange
11019	NASDAQ OMX Baltic Exchange, Vilnius First North
10307	NASDAQ OMX Vilnius Stock Exchange
10047	Bourse de Luxembourg
11115	Bourse de Luxembourg un-regulated
10314	Macedonian Stock Exchange
10341	Malta Stock Exchange
10037	NYSE Euronext EQF, Equity and Index Derivatives
10878	NYSE Euronext European Eq Off-Exch Traded Reports in FC
11020	NYSE Euronext Arca Europe
11153	TOM MTF CASH MARKETS
10038	NYSE Euronext Amsterdam
10873	NYSE Euronext European Eq Off-Exchange Traded Reports EUR
17059	Euronext - Traded but not listed at Amsterdam
10853	Oslo Stock Exchange, Derivatives
10840	Oslo Stock Exchange, Axxess Alternative Equities Market
10048	Oslo Stock Exchange
10550	Norwegian Over the Counter Market
16127	Merkur Market
10750	New Connect Market (Order Driven) Boerse Warschau
10302	Warsaw Stock Exchange, Off Exchange

10243	Warsaw Stock Exchange
10345	Warsaw Stock Exchange, Derivatives
10051	NYSE Euronext Lisbon
16991	Euronext - Growth Lisbon
16992	Euronext - Access Lisbon
10883	Bucharest SE Deal Driven
10304	Bucharest Stock Exchange
11080	Bucharest SE CAN-ATS Order Driven
10884	Bucharest SE Bond Deal and Quote Driven
10753	RASDAQ Electronic Exchange SA, Order Driven, Odd Lots
10752	RASDAQ Electronic Exchange SA, Order Driven, Round Lots
10754	RASDAQ Electronic Exchange SA, Negotiation Mechanism
11089	RTS Russian Trading System, Standard Market Evening Trade
11325	Moscow Exchange, Negotiated deals with CCP
11168	Moscow Exchange, Odd Lot
11170	RTS OTC TRADES RUB
11173	RTS OTC TRADES
11031	Moscow Interbank Currency Exchange, Quote Driven Market
10566	RTS T+O and Board
10567	RTS Classic Market, Converted into RUR
10549	Moscow Interbank Currency Exchange
10301	Russian Trading System, Derivatives
11090	RTS Russian Trading System, Forts Evening Trade
10565	RTS Classic Market, USD
11122	RTS Address Trades Classica and Board Market
10829	Moscow Interbank Currency Exchange, Equities converted into USD

11124	RTS Address Trades Standard and Forts Market (Main Session)
10803	Belgrade Stock Exchange
10279	Bratislava Stock Exchange, Direct Trades
10776	Bratislava Stock Exchange MTF
11086	Bratislava Stock Exchange, Market Maker
10187	Bratislava Stock Exchange
10294	Ljubljana Stock Exchange
11028	Ljubljana Stock Exchange, OTC Foreign Currencies
10056	Bolsa de Barcelona
10057	Bolsa de Bilbao
11045	Bolsa de Madrid, Corros Electronicos
10126	MEFF Mercado Espanol Financiero de Futuros, Renta Variable
11138	Latibex - BME
10055	Bolsa de Madrid
10355	Bolsa de Madrid, Mercado de Bloques
10054	Mercado Continuo Espanol
11058	SIBE, Mercado Continuo
17024	Mercado Alternativo Bursatil
10452	AIAF, Mercado de Renta Fija
10058	Valencia Stock Exchange
10571	Nordic Growth Market
10053	Nasdaq OMX Nordic Exchange, Stockholm Equities
11010	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Stockholm First North
10874	NASDAQ OMX Exchanges, External Trades
10875	NASDAQ OMX Exchanges, External Trades other Currencies
11011	AktieTorget
11310	NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange, Stockholm NOK
10466	Berner Kantonalbank

11174	BX Berne eXchange - BX World
10005	BX Berne eXchange
11184	BX Berne eXchange - BX World OTC
10004	SIX Swiss Exchange
11356	Six Swiss Exchange, Liquidnet Service
10203	ZKB Zurcher Kantonalbank, Kurse
10349	SIX Swiss Exchange USD
11355	Six Swiss Exchange, SwissAtMid
10380	Swiss Blue Chip Segment
10351	SIX Swiss Exchange EUR
10109	Borsa Istanbul A.S.
10879	Turkish Derivatives Exchanges
11117	PFTS Stock Exchange Realtime
11027	Ukrainian Exchange
10309	PFTS Stock Exchange
10882	Chi-X Off-Exchange Trade
12891	Boerse Berlin Equiduct Trading 2nd Listing
10847	BATS CHI-X Europe 1st Listing
10851	BOAT EUR
10894	BATS CHI-X Europe 2nd Listing
10716	NASDAQ OMX Europe
11022	BATS Europe 1st Listing
11364	TRADEcho 2nd Currency
10272	SETSqx
10211	NYSE Euronext LIFFE, Equity and Index Derivatives
10594	London Stock Exchange, European Markets
10257	Turquoise 1st Listing
10036	LSE London Stock Exchange
10258	Turquoise 2nd Listing
11085	BOAT, other currency 2nd Listing

10852	BOAT, Other Currency
11363	TRADEcho
11149	SmartPool Trading Limited
10718	London Stock Exchange, International Trade Reporting Service
10361	LSE London Stock Exchange, SETS
10699	ICAP Securities and Derivatives Exchange
12795	Boerse Berlin Equiduct Trading 1st Listing
10507	IOB London International Order Book
11023	BATS Europe 2nd Listing
10383	VIRT-X GBP
10381	VIRT-X EUR
10384	VIRT-X SEK
10385	VIRT-X NOK
10386	VIRT-X DKK
10502	OFEX LONDON
10283	NASDAQ EUROPE
10182	SEAQ INTERNATIONAL, DIV MARKET MAKERS
10035	LONDON STOCK EXCHANGE (LSE), TRADED IN FOREIGN CURRENCIES
20261	IRISH MK LON
20266	LOND 3RD MKT

 Stock exchange type (Eurofidai) - Codelist for STOCK_EXCHANGE_TYPE

Codelist for STOCK_EXCHANGE_TYPE

2	Trading place/market
5	Public corporation
8	Contributor
9	Price information provider
10	Technical trading place

11	Order Book
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Dependency type code (Eurofidai) - Codelist for DEPENDENCY_TYPE_CODE

Codelist for DEPENDENCY_TYPE_CODE

1	Certificate/ depository receipt: Certificate/ depository receipt that is issued e.g. abroad, representing the original share or a specific amount of original shares
2	New share: New issue shares are usually issued on a capital increase and are not or not yet fully entitled to dividends
6	Same instrument as original: Same Instrument i.e. share corresponding with original share that is treated accordingly (e.g. foreign shares in Thailand, Hong-Kong or Bermuda registered in England or LONDON-Certificates registered in Germany)
15	Loyalty Bonus Shares: Shares issued to long time holders to benefit from special dividends or voting rights. Example: Under French law, companies may distribute bonus dividends to shareholders who have been holding their shares in registered form for a minimum period of two calendar years. The net bonus dividend due to shareholders of loyalty bonus shares may increase the net ordinary dividend by a maximum of 10%
21	Distribution right: Right given to the shareholders to receive securities during a distribution made by a company (distribution of share, warrant or other instruments)

Type of Birth (LSPD) - Codelist for G8 & M8

Codelist for G8 & M8

50	Company came into the database after its birth on (a) the entry of a new sample or (b) in a handful of cases, after recognising its eligibility at a later date
51	New company eligible for entry to the database
52	Data collected prior to company entering database
53	Placing
54	Offer for sale/Offer to public
55	Tender
56	Subscription
57	Re-introduction/Restoration of listing
58	Merger/Securities issued in Acquisition
59	Issue of new securities by way of scrip or rights issue to existing shareholders
60	Introduction to Stock Exchange/Introduction of shares/Issue to public
61	London quotation granted. Previously listed on Provincial Stock Exchange
62	Conversion (Ord converted into Dfd, Ord redesignated "B" Ord, Ord converted into different shares...)
63	Private placing
64	Demerger
65	IPO Spinoff
69	Type of birth not known either because no date was recorded in the Extel cards or C.G.T. book, or because the actual birth date was long before we started collecting data
70	Management Buy-out
71	Placing combined with an open offer to shareholders
72	Placing combined with an intermediaries offer
73	Placing combined with offer to public
74	Issued under scheme/proposal to common holders or ordinary holders

75	Spinoff from another company
76	Exchange offer (usually Investment Trust company)
77	Issued against split of units
78	Issued in acquisition
79	Acquisition combined with placing
80	Issued in capital reorganisation
81	Exchange offer combined with offer for sale
82	Placing combined with rollover from another trust
83	Rollover combined with other offer
84	Scrip issue combined with placing and other offer
85	Placing combined with other offer and rollover
86	Demutualisation combined with other offer
87	Placing combined with rights issue or open offer
48	Security existed at January 1955
49	Birth reason unknown

Type of Death (LSPD) - Codelist for G10 & M10

Codelist for G10 & M10

0	Active
5	Acquisition/takeover/merger
6	Suspension/cancellation with shares acquired later. Meanwhile, may in some cases, be traded under rule 163(2)
7	Liquidation (usually valueless, but there may be liquidation payments)
8	Quotation cancelled (maybe suspended initially) as company becomes a private company, or there is insufficient trading in the shares. Dealings continue under rule 163(2) or (3) or rule 535 or Ofex or Plus or Specialist Funds Market (in the last case, the security remains on LSPD)
9	As for 8, but no dealings under rule 163

10	Quotation suspended – if suspended for more than three years, this may lead to automatic cancellation
11	Voluntary liquidation, where value remains and was / is being distributed
12	Changed to foreign registration
13	Quotation cancelled (sometimes for reason unknown). Dealings continue under rule 163(2) or (3)
14	As for 13, but no dealings under rule 163
15	Converted into an alternative security for the same company
16	Receiver appointed/liquidation. Probably valueless, but not yet certain
17	Unitisation of an investment or financial trust
18	Nationalisation
19	Enfranchisement
20	In Administration/Administrative receivership
21	Cancelled and assumed valueless or suspended but assumed valueless

 SEDOL Group (LSPD) - Codelist for G16 & M4

Codelist for G16 & M4

0	Information not available
29	Banks
30	Breweries
31	Building Societies
32	Commercial & Industrial
33	Electric & Power
34	Financial Trust
35	Gas
36	Insurance

37	Investment Trust
38	Unit Trust
39	Iron, Coal & Steel
40	Mines – Australian
41	Mines – Miscellaneous
42	Mines – Rhodesian & East African
43	Mines – South African
44	Mines – West African
45	Mines – Diamond
46	Nitrate
47	Oil
48	Property
49	Plantations
50	Railways
51	Railways
52	Telegraphs
53	Tramways
54	Shipping
57	Utilities
58	Water Works
95	Alternative Investment Market
97	Third Market until 2000; Specialist Funds Market from 2007
98	Unlisted Securities Market
99	Other unlisted securities. This classification was created by the Stock Exchange for brokers wishing to deal in this type of securities under rule 535. The securities are not quoted, and the price figuring in the left column represents the broker's dealings. Because the dealings are occasional, companies are not obliged to report any changes (i.e. capital changes)

 Stock Exchange Industrial Classification (LSPD) - Codelist for G17

Codelist for G17

The number in parentheses are the start and end date (YYYYMM-YYYYMM) of the period during which the industry code was in use.

Prior to 1994, the Stock Exchange industrial classification system differed from the Financial Times Actuaries index classification system. Since 1994, the two systems have been unified. From Jan 2006 the ICB industrial classification system has been adopted.

09	Water Works (199001-199311)
11	Aircraft & Components (197812-197912)
11	Cold Formed Fastenings & Turned Parts (198001-198012)
11	Other Industrial Materials & Capital Goods (198101-199311)
12	Bricks & Roofing Tiles (197812-199109)
13	Builders Merchants (197812-199311)
14	Building Materials (197812-199311)
15	Cement & Concrete (197812-199109)
16	Paint (197812-199311)
17	Timber (197812-199109)
18	Contracting & Construction (197812-199311)
19	Electricals (Heavy) (197812-198012)
19	Electricals (exc Radio & TV) (198101-198312)
19	Electricals (198401-199311)
20	Boiler Makers (197812-197912)
20	Cold Formed Fastenings & Turned Parts (198001-198812)
20	Rubbers (199101-199311)
21	Founders & Stampers (197812-198812)
21	Aerospace (198907-199311)
22	Industrial Plant (197812-199311)

23	Mechanical Handling (197812-199311)
24	Pumps & Valves (197812-199109)
25	Steel & Chemical Plant (197812-199109)
26	Wires & Ropes (197812-199109)
27	Misc Engineering (197812-198003)
27	Misc Mechanical Engineering (198004-199311)
28	Machine & Other Tools (197812-199311)
29	Shipbuilding (197812-197912)
29	Misc Engineering Contractors (198001-199109)
30	Heating & Ventilating (197812-199112)
30	Education & Business Training (199201-199311)
31	Instruments (197812-199311)
32	Metallurgy (197812-199311)
33	Special Steels (197812-198712)
33	Steel (198801-199311)
34	Misc Metal Forming (197812-199311)
35	Light Electronics Radio & TV (197812-198012)
35	Electronics (198401-199311)
36	Radio & TV Rental (197812-198012)
36	Radio & TV (198101-199012)
36	Computer Software (199201-199311)
37	Floor Covering (197812-199012)
37	Broadcasting Contractors (199101-199311)
38	Furniture & Bedding (197812-198412)
38	Furniture & Furnishings (198501-199311)
39	Household Appliances (197812-199109)
39	Health Care (199201-199311)
40	Kitchen & Tableware (197812-199109)
40	Personal & Household Care (199201-199311)
41	Motor Components (197812-199311)

42	Motor Distributors (197812-199311)
43	Motor Vehicles (197812-199311)
44	Security & Alarm Services (198401-199311)
45	Breweries (197812-199311)
46	Wines & Spirits (197812-199311)
47	Hotels & Caterers (197812-199311)
48	Leisure (197812-199311)
49	General Food Manufacturing (197812-198612)
49	Food Manufacturers (198701-199311)
50	Milling & Flour (197812-198712)
51	Food Retailing (197812-198612)
51	Food Retailers (198701-199311)
52	Newspapers & Periodicals (197812-199311)
53	Publishing & Printing (197812-199311)
54	Packaging & Paper (197812-199311)
55	Department Stores (197812-199311)
56	Furnishing Stores (197812-199311)
57	Mail Order Stores (197812-199103)
57	Mail Order (199104-199311)
58	Stores Multiple (197812-199311)
59	Clothing (197812-199311)
60	Cotton (197812-199003)
60	Floor Covering (199101-199112)
60	Carpets (199201-199311)
61	Wool (197812-199311)
62	Misc Textiles (197812-199311)
63	Tobacco (197812-199311)
64	Footwear (197812-198006)
64	Footwear Manufacturers & Leather (198007-198412)
64	Leather (198501-198612)

64	Leather & Footwear (198701-199311)
65	Toys & Games (197812-198612)
65	Giftware (198701-199311)
66	Plastic & Rubber Fabricators (197812-198412)
66	Plastic & Rubber (198501-199311)
67	Drugs & Pharmacy (197812-198312)
67	Health & Household Products (198401-198712)
67	Health & Household (198801-199112)
67	Pharmaceuticals (199201-199311)
68	General Chemicals (197812-199311)
69	Office Equipment (197812-198312)
69	Office Equipment (exc Computers) (198401-199311)
70	Oil (197812-198412)
70	Oil & Gas (198501-199311)
71	Shipping (197812-198512)
71	General Traders Wholesalers & Distributors (198601-199311)
72	Transport Freight & Fuel (197812-198012)
72	Transport & Freight (198101-199311)
73	Industrial Holding Companies (197812-198312)
73	Industrial Conglomerates (198401-199311)
74	Laundries & Cleaners (197812-199311)
75	Agencies (197812-198612)
75	Consultancies & Agencies (198701-199012)
75	Support Services (199101-199311)
76	Miscellaneous (Unclassified) (197812-199311)
77	Banks (197812-199311)
78	Foreign Banks (197812-198912)
78	Media Agencies (199101-199311)
79	Discount Houses (197812-199311)

80	Hire Purchase (197812-198312)
80	Leasing & Hire Purchase (198401-199209)
81	Insurance (Life) (197812-199311)
82	Insurance (Composite) (197812-199311)
83	Insurance Brokers (197812-199311)
84	Investment Trusts (197812-199206)
84	UK Investment Trusts (199207-199311)
85	Merchant Banks (197812-199311)
86	Property (197812-199311)
87	Financial Trusts (197812-198312)
87	Miscellaneous Financial (198401-199012)
88	Utilities (198101-198311)
88	Telephone Networks (198412-198612)
89	Rubbers (197812-199012)
89	Electric Utilities (199101-199311)
90	Teas (197812-199012)
90	Property Agencies (199101-199311)
91	Copper (197812-199311)
92	Mining Finance (197812-199311)
93	Tin (197812-199012)
93	Unapproved Investment Companies (199101-199311)
94	Diamond (198001-199012)
94	Offshore Investment Funds (199101-199206)
94	Offshore Investment Funds & Companies (199207-199311)
95	Gold (197812-199311)
96	Misc Mines & Collieries (197812-199311)
97	Overseas Trade (197812-199012)
97	Currency Funds (199101-199311)
98	Foreign Currency Equity Stocks (197812-197910)

98	Electric Utilities (198601-199012)
98	Other S842 Investment Trusts (199207-199311)
99	Overseas Sterling Area Currency Stocks (197812-197910)
123	Gold Mining (199312-199902)
125	Other Mineral Extractors And Mines (199312-199902)
129	Mining Finance (199312-199902)
150	Oil Integrated (199312-199902)
162	Oil Exploration & Production (199312-199902)
165	Oil Services (199312-199902)
210	Building & Construction (199312-199711)
210	Construction (199712-199902)
213	House Building (199712-199902)
217	Other Construction (199712-199902)
222	Building Materials (199312-199902)
225	Builders Merchants (199312-199902)
232	Chemicals-Commodity (199312-199902)
234	Chemicals-Specialty (199312-199902)
236	Chemicals-Materials Technology (199312-199711)
236	Chemicals-Advanced Materials (199712-199902)
240	Diversified Industrials (199312-199902)
252	Electrical Equipment (199312-199902)
253	Electronic Equipment (199312-199902)
255	Office Machinery (199312-199902)
261	Engineering-Metallurgy (199312-199902)
262	Engineering-Fabricators (199312-199902)
263	Engineering-Specialties (199312-199512)
264	Engineering-Contractors (199312-199902)
265	Engineering-Diversified (199312-199411)
265	Engineering-General (199412-199902)

268	Engineering-Aerospace & Defence (199312-199902)
269	Instruments Tools & Mechanical Handling Equipment (199312-199512)
270	Vehicle Components & Assemblers (199312-199711)
270	Engineering-Vehicles (199712-199902)
282	Paper and Packaging (199312-199902)
284	Printing (199312-199902)
286	Stationery Products (199512-199902)
291	Clothing Manufacturers (199312-199902)
293	Wool (199312-199902)
295	Textiles-Diversified (199312-199411)
295	Textiles-Other (199412-199902)
297	Footwear & Leather (199312-199902)
299	Giftware & Costume Jewellery (199312-199512)
310	Breweries (199312-199511)
320	Spirits Wines & Ciders (199312-199511)
320	Alcoholic Beverages (199512-199902)
330	Food Manufacturers (199312-199411)
330	Food Producers (199712-199902)
333	Food Producers (199312-199711)
336	Plantations (199412-199902)
341	Clothing & Footwear (199712-199902)
342	Furniture & Furnishings (199312-199511)
342	Furniture & Household Equipment (199512-199711)
342	Furnishings & Floor Coverings (199712-199902)
344	Floor Covering (199312-199902)
345	Household Appliances & Housewares (199712-199902)
346	Household Requisites (199312-199711)

346	Household Products (199712-199902)
347	Leisure Equipment (199712-199902)
348	Personal Care & Cosmetics (199712-199902)
349	Other Textiles & Leather Goods (199712-199902)
360	Health Care (199312-199902)
364	Hospital Management (199712-199902)
366	Medical Products & Supplies (199712-199902)
367	Other Health Care (199712-199902)
370	Pharmaceuticals (199312-199902)
380	Tobacco (199312-199902)
412	Distributors Of Industrial Components & Equipment (199312-199902)
413	Vehicle Distributors (199312-199511)
413	Vehicle Distribution (199512-199902)
414	Distributors Others (199312-199902)
422	Leisure (199312-199512)
424	Hotels & Caterers (199312-199511)
424	Hotels (199512-199902)
426	Leisure Facilities (199512-199902)
428	Home Entertainment (199512-199902)
432	Media Agencies (199312-199902)
434	Broadcasting Contractors (199312-199902)
436	Publishing (199312-199902)
440	Retailers and Wholesalers Food (199312-199902)
452	Retailers Multi Department (199312-199902)
454	Retailers Chain Store (199312-199902)
470	Breweries Pubs & Restaurants (199512-199902)
481	Business Support Services (199312-199902)
482	Education Business Training & Employment Agencies (199312-199902)
484	Security Alarm Services (199312-199902)

485	Waste Control (199512-199902)
486	Laundries & Cleaners (199312-199902)
487	Computer Services (199312-199411)
487	Computer Software & Services (199412-199902)
490	Transport (199312-199902)
492	Airlines & Airports (199712-199902)
494	Rail & Road (199712-199902)
496	Shipping & Ports (199712-199902)
512	Polution Control (199312-199512)
514	Plantations (199312-199411)
516	Other Businesses (199312-199512)
620	Electricity (199312-199902)
640	Gas Distribution (199312-199902)
660	Telecommunications (199312-199902)
680	Water (199312-199902)
710	Banks (199312-199411)
710	Banks-Retail (199412-199902)
720	Banks-Merchant (199412-199611)
732	Insurance Brokers (199312-199902)
734	Insurance Composite (199312-199902)
736	Insurance Lloyds Funds (199312-199902)
740	Life Assurance (199312-199902)
750	Merchant Banks (199312-199411)
771	Banks-Merchant (199612-199902)
772	Financial Other (199312-199902)
774	Discount Houses (199312-199412)
775	Fund Managers & Stockbrokers (199412-199902)
778	Investment Companies (199312-199902)
792	Property (199312-199902)
794	Property Agencies (199312-199902)

800	Investment Trusts (199312-199902)
801	International Investment Trusts (199412-199902)
802	UK Investment Trusts (199412-199902)
804	European Investment Trusts (199412-199902)
805	Geographical Specialists (199412-199902)
806	Emerging Markets (199712-199902)
807	Venture & Development Capital (199412-199902)
808	Split Capital Investment Trusts (199412-199902)
820	Housing Income Investment Trusts (199612-199902)
840	Open-Ended Investment Companies (199612-199902)
860	Split Capital Investment Trusts (199612-199902)
880	VCTs (199612-199902)
940	Off-Shore Investment Companies and Funds (199312-199902)
970	Currency Funds (199312-199902)
980	Other S842 Investment Trusts (199312-199902)
043	Gold Mining (199903-200511)
045	Mining Finance (199903-200511)
048	Other Mineral Extractors & Mines (199903-200511)
073	Oil & Gas – Exploration & Production (199903-200511)
075	Oil – Services (199903-200511)
078	Oil–Integrated (199903-200511)
113	Chemicals–Commodity (199903-200511)
116	Chemicals–Advanced Materials (199903-200511)
118	Chemicals–Specialty (199903-200511)
131	Builders Merchants (199903-200511)
132	Building & Construction Materials (199903-200511)
134	House Building (199903-200511)
137	Other Construction (199903-200511)

153	Forestry (199903-200511)
156	Paper (199903-200511)
186	Non-Ferrous Metals (199903-200511)
188	Steel (199903-200511)
215	Aerospace (199903-200511)
216	Defence (199903-200511)
240	Diversified Industrials (199903-200511)
252	Electrical Equipment (199903-200511)
253	Electronic Equipment (199903-200511)
263	Commercial Vehicles & Trucks (199903-200511)
264	Engineering–Contractors (199903-200511)
266	Engineering Fabricators (199903-200511)
267	Engineering–General (199903-200511)
311	Automobiles (199903-200511)
313	Auto Parts (199903-200511)
317	Tyres & Rubber (199903-200511)
318	Vehicle Distribution (200112-200511)
341	Clothing & Footwear (199903-200511)
342	Furnishings & Floor Coverings (199903-200511)
343	Consumer Electronics (200212-200512)
345	Household Appliances & Housewares (199903-200511)
347	Leisure Equipment (199903-200511)
349	Other Textiles & Leather Goods (199903-200511)
415	Beverages–Brewers (199903-200511)
416	Beverages–Distillers & Vintners (199903-200511)
418	Soft Drinks (199903-200511)
433	Farming & Fishing (199903-200511)
435	Food Processors (199903-200511)
443	Health Maintenance Organisations (199903-200511)

444	Hospital Management & Long Term Care (199903-200511)
446	Medical Equipment & Supplies (199903-200511)
449	Other Health Care (199903-200511)
460	Packaging (199903-200112)
475	Household Products (199903-200511)
477	Personal Products (199903-200511)
480	Pharmaceuticals (199903-200511)
482	Biotechnology (200112-200511)
490	Tobacco (199903-200511)
514	Distributors of Industrial Components & Equipment (199903-200112)
518	Vehicle Distribution (199903-200111)
519	Distributors–Other (199903-200112)
524	Discount & Super Stores and Warehouses (199903-200511)
525	Retailers-ecommerce (200004-200511)
526	Retailers–Hardlines (199903-200511)
527	Retailers–Multi Department (199903-200511)
528	Retailers–Soft Goods (199903-200511)
532	Gaming (199903-200211)
532	Gambling (200212-200511)
535	Home Entertainment (199903-200511)
536	Hotels (199903-200511)
538	Leisure Facilities (199903-200511)
539	Restaurants & Pubs (200012-200511)
542	Broadcasting Contractors (199903-200211)
542	Television Radio & Filmed Entertainment (200212-200511)
543	Cable & Satellite (199903-200211)
543	Subscription Entertainment Networks (200212-200511)

545	Media Agencies (199903-200511)
546	Photography (199903-200511)
547	Publishing & Printing (199903-200511)
560	Restaurants Pubs & Breweries (199903-200003)
560	Restaurants & Pubs (200004-200011)
581	Business Support Services (199903-200511)
582	Delivery Services (200212-200511)
583	Education Business Training & Employment Agencies (199903-200511)
584	Environmental Control (199903-200511)
585	Funerals & Cemeteries (199903-200511)
586	Laundries & Cleaners (199903-200511)
587	Transaction & Payroll Services (200212-200511)
588	Security & Alarm Services (199903-200511)
591	Airlines & Transport (199903-200511)
596	Rail Road & Freight (199903-200511)
597	Shipping & Ports (199903-200511)
630	Food & Drug Retailers (199903-200511)
673	Fixed-Line Telecommunication Services (199903-200511)
678	Wireless Telecommunication Services (199903-200511)
720	Electricity (199903-200511)
730	Gas Distribution (199903-200211)
773	Gas Distribution (200212-200511)
775	Multi-Utilities (200212-200511)
778	Water (200212-200511)
780	Water (199903-200211)
810	Banks (199903-200511)
833	Insurance Brokers (199903-200511)
834	Insurance–Non-Life (199903-200511)

836	Insurance Lloyd's Funds (199903-200003)
837	Re-insurance (199903-200511)
839	Other Insurance (199903-200511)
840	Life Assurance (199903-200511)
850	Investment Companies (199903-200111)
850	Investment Companies - eligible for indices (200112-200511)
851	International Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
852	UK Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
854	European Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
855	Geographical Specialists–Developed Markets (199903-200112)
856	Emerging Markets (199903-200112)
857	Venture & Development Capital (199903-200112)
859	Investment Companies - not approved under S842 (199903-200112)
862	Real Estate Holding & Development (199903-200511)
864	Property Agencies (199903-200511)
867	Real Estate Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
871	Asset Managers (199903-200511)
873	Consumer Finance (199903-200511)
875	Investment Banks (199903-200511)
877	Mortgage Finance (199903-200511)
879	Other Financial (199903-200511)
890	Investment Entities – not eligible for indices (200112-200511)
892	Housing Income Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
893	Open-Ended Investment Companies (199903-200112)
894	Off-Shore Investment Companies & Funds (199903-200112)

895	Venture Capital Trusts (199903-200112)
897	Currency Funds (199903-200112)
898	Other S842 Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
899	Split Capital Investment Trusts (199903-200112)
932	Computer Hardware (199903-200511)
936	Semiconductors (199903-200511)
938	Telecommunications Equipment (199903-200511)
972	Computer Services (199903-200511)
974	Internet (199903-200511)
977	Software (199903-200511)
0533	Exploration & Production (200512-201812)
0537	Integrated Oil & Gas (200512-201812)
0573	Oil Equipment & Services (200512-201812)
0577	Pipelines (200512-201812)
0583	Renewable Energy Equipment (200803-201812)
0587	Alternative Fuels (200803-201812)
1353	Commodity Chemicals (200512-201812)
1357	Specialty Chemicals (200512-201812)
1733	Forestry (200512-201812)
1737	Paper (200512-201812)
1753	Aluminum (200512-201812)
1755	Nonferrous Metals (200512-201812)
1757	Steel (200512-201812)
1757	Iron & Steel (200803-201812)
1771	Coal (200512-201812)
1773	Diamonds & Gemstones (200512-201812)
1775	General Mining (200512-201812)
1777	Gold Mining (200512-201812)
1779	Platinum & Precious Metals (200512-201812)
2353	Building Materials & Fixtures (200512-201812)

2357	Heavy Construction (200512-201812)
2713	Aerospace (200512-201812)
2717	Defense (200512-201812)
2723	Containers & Packaging (200512-201812)
2727	Diversified Industrials (200512-201812)
2733	Electrical Components & Equipment (200512-201812)
2737	Electronic Equipment (200512-201812)
2753	Commercial Vehicles & Trucks (200512-201812)
2757	Industrial Machinery (200512-201812)
2771	Delivery Services (200512-201812)
2773	Marine Transportation (200512-201812)
2775	Railroads (200512-201812)
2777	Transportation Services (200512-201812)
2779	Trucking (200512-201812)
2791	Business Support Services (200512-201812)
2793	Business Training & Employment Agencies (200512-201812)
2795	Financial Administration (200512-201812)
2797	Industrial Suppliers (200512-201812)
2799	Waste & Disposal Services (200512-201812)
3353	Automobiles (200512-201812)
3355	Auto Parts (200512-201812)
3357	Tires (200512-201812)
3533	Brewers (200512-201812)
3535	Distillers & Vintners (200512-201812)
3537	Soft Drinks (200512-201812)
3573	Farming & Fishing (200512-201812)
3577	Food Products (200512-201812)
3722	Durable Household Products (200512-201812)
3724	Nondurable Household Products (200512-201812)

3726	Furnishings (200512-201812)
3728	Home Construction (200512-201812)
3743	Consumer Electronics (200512-201812)
3745	Recreational Products (200512-201812)
3747	Toys (200512-201812)
3763	Clothing & Accessories (200512-201812)
3765	Footwear (200512-201812)
3767	Personal Products (200512-201812)
3785	Tobacco (200512-201812)
4533	Health Care Providers (200512-201812)
4535	Medical Equipment (200512-201812)
4537	Medical Supplies (200512-201812)
4573	Biotechnology (200512-201812)
4577	Pharmaceuticals (200512-201812)
5333	Drug Retailers (200512-201812)
5337	Food Retailers & Wholesalers (200512-201812)
5371	Apparel Retailers (200512-201812)
5373	Broadline Retailers (200512-201812)
5375	Home Improvement Retailers (200512-201812)
5377	Specialized Consumer Services (200512-201812)
5379	Specialty Retailers (200512-201812)
5553	Broadcasting & Entertainment (200512-201812)
5555	Media Agencies (200512-201812)
5557	Publishing (200512-201812)
5751	Airlines (200512-201812)
5752	Gambling (200512-201812)
5753	Hotels (200512-201812)
5755	Recreational Services (200512-201812)
5757	Restaurants & Bars (200512-201812)
5759	Travel & Tourism (200512-201812)

6535	Fixed Line Telecommunications (200512-201812)
6575	Mobile Telecommunications (200512-201812)
7535	Electricity (200512-201812)
7535	Conventional Electricity (200803-201812)
7537	Conventional Electricity (200803-201812)
7573	Gas Distribution (200512-201812)
7575	Multiutilities (200512-201812)
7577	Water (200512-201812)
8355	Banks (200512-201812)
8532	Full Line Insurance (200512-201812)
8534	Insurance Brokers (200512-201812)
8536	Property & Casualty Insurance (200512-201812)
8538	Reinsurance (200512-201812)
8575	Life Insurance (200512-201812)
8633	Real Estate Holding & Development (200803-201812)
8637	Real Estate Services (200803-201812)
8671	Industrial & Office REITs (200803-201812)
8672	Retail REITs (200803-201812)
8673	Residential REITs (200803-201812)
8674	Diversified REITs (200803-201812)
8675	Specialty REITs (200803-201812)
8676	Mortgage REITs (200803-201812)
8677	Hotel & Lodging REITs (200803-201812)
8733	Real Estate Holding & Development (200512-201812)
8737	Real Estate Investment Trusts (200512-201812)
8771	Asset Managers (200512-201812)
8773	Consumer Finance (200512-201812)
8775	Specialty Finance (200512-201812)
8777	Investment Services (200512-201812)

8779	Mortgage Finance (200512-201812)
8985	Equity Investment Instruments (200512-201812)
8995	Nonequity Investment Instruments (200512-201812)
9533	Computer Services (200512-201812)
9535	Internet (200512-201812)
9537	Software (200512-201812)
9572	Computer Hardware (200512-201812)
9574	Electronic Office Equipment (200512-201812)
9576	Semiconductors (200512-201812)
9578	Telecommunications Equipment (200512-201812)

Financial Times Actuaries Index Marker (LSPD) - Codelist for G18

Codelist for G18

1	FTSE 100 Constituent
-1	FTSE 100 & FT30 Constituent
2	FTSE 250 Constituent
-2	FTSE 250 & FT30 Constituent
3	FTSE Small Cap Constituent

Type of Capital Change (LSDP) - Codelist for C3

Codelist for C3

1	Scrip issue
2	Scrip issue in another share (see C4)
3	Scrip issue then consolidation
4	Consolidation then scrip issue
5	Scrip issue then subdivision
6	Subdivision then scrip issue

7	Scrip issue in another ord. (see C4) then consolidation
8	Scrip issue in another ord. (see C4) then subdivision
9	Complex scrip issue or other event
10	Consolidation
11	Subdivision
12	Capital repayment, can be in share of another company
13	Cancel part of nominal value
14	Rights issue
15	Complex rights issue (see C4)
16	Rights issue in another share (see C4)
17	Multiple rights issue
18	Spare
19	Spinoff (rights in another company)
20	Spinoff (rights in foreign company)
21	Demerger
22	Redenomination of par value (eg into Euro)
>50	Indicates the capital change occurred on the previous day and the type of capital change = item C3-50

Share Type (LSPD) - Codelist for C4

Codelist for C4

1-10	same as for par values (see U2)
11	convertible loan stock
12	Debenture
13	loan stock
14	capital loan stock
15	income shares
16	convertible debenture stock

17	convertible unsecured loan stock
18	partly convertible loan stock
19	preference share
20	preferred income shares
21	capital stock
22	convertible preference
23	capital shares
24	redeemable preference

Status flag (LSDP) - Codelist for C5

Codelist for C5

0	Renounceable
1	Non-renounceable

Special marker (LSPD) - Codelist for D5

Codelist for D5

0	Gross dividend (pre 1978) or unset (post 1978)
1	Net of tax
2	Subject to tax
3	Cash or scrip option
4	Non-standard period
5	Payment on account of next year
6	For the year
7	For the quarter
8	Special date
9	Tricky
10	Tax free
11	Paid in 2 parts

12	Cash or scrip option + non-standard period
13	Dividend restriction + non-standard period
14	Payment on account of next year + non-standard period
15	Dividend rights waived or part of dividend waived
16	Government freeze of dividend restriction
17	Net + non-standard period
18	Payment on account of next year + net
19	Net + cash or scrip option
20	Net + government freeze or restriction
21	Combined
22	Subject to capital gains tax
23	B share dividend
24	Dividend in shares
99	Cancelled

Type of dividend (LSPD) - Codelist for D7

Codelist for D7

1	First (or quarterly) interim
2	Second interim
3	Third interim
4	Fourth interim
5	Bonus
6	Special distribution
7	Capital distribution
8	Special interim
9	Final
10	Liquidation distribution

11	Capital repayment possibly via a special dividend (maybe with tax credit) or even a dividend in shares of another company
12	B share in lieu of interim dividend
13	B share in lieu of final dividend

Currency of par value (LSPD) - Codelist for U2

Codelist for U2

AUD	Australian Dollar
CAD	Canadian Dollar
CHF	Swiss Franc
EUR	Euro
GBP	Sterling
HKD	Hong Kong Dollar
ILS	Israeli Shekel
NOK	Norwegian Krone
SGD	Singaporean Dollar
USD	US Dollar
ZAR	South African Dollar
ZMW	Zambian Kwacha

Price marker (LSPD) - Codelist for P6 & P7

Codelist for P6 & P7

0	Price from last day of month
1-31	Price is 1-31 days old
32	Price is over one month old

Price status (LSPD) - Codelist for P8

Codelist for P8

0	Not collected
1	Input and proceed normally
2	Failed validation checks of the Data Entry System but was confirmed from SEDOL
3	Price record input by database amended
4	Quotation suspended (only reliably available since 1965)
5	No third price/not found on SEDOL list
6	Flagged as missing or inconsistent with previous price but was confirmed from SEDOL
7	Obvious printing error. Correct price or date inferred
8	Suspicious price change checked against all sources (Extel cards, Capital Gains Tax Book) in 11/86 but no further information was found. When returns are greater than +/- 50% and no specific reason is found, a marker of 9 still remains.
9	Suspicious price or capital change. Because we do not have the relevant SEDOL listings for those years and because it took place before 1965 (when CGT book first appeared), those prices or capital changes should be checked against Extel cards at Extel, or against SEDOL listings at the Guildhall library.

 Reason for new SEDOL (LSDP) - Codelist for N5

Codelist for N5

1	Change of name
2	Change of SEDOL group
3	Change of SEDOL number
4	Reorganisation/Merger
30	Relisting after suspension
31	Relisting after suspension and name change

32	Relisting after suspension and SEDOL group change
33	Relisting after suspension and SEDOL number change
34	Relisting after suspension and reorganisation/merger
35	Suspension continues
36	Cancellation and relisting or cancellation followed later by re-listing
37	Discharge of administration order or successful CVA/reorganisation and re-listing, or else re-listing of company previously cancelled and deemed valueless (death code 21)
38	Suspension continues but company no longer deemed valueless
50	Company came into the database on the entry of a new sample
51	New company eligible for entry to the database
52	Data collected prior to company entering database
53	Placing
54	Offer for sale/Offer to public
55	Tender
56	Subscription
57	Re-introduction/Restoration of listing
58	Merger/Securities issued in Acquisition
59	Issue of new securities by way of scrip or rights issue to existing shareholders
60	Introduction to Stock Exchange/Introduction of shares/Issue to public
61	London quotation granted. Previously listed on Provincial Stock Exchange
62	Conversion (Ord converted in Dfd, Ord redesignated "B" Ord, Ord converted into different shares...)
63	Private placing
64	Demerger

65	IPO Spinoff
69	Type of birth not known either because no date was recorded in the Extel cards or C.G.T. book, or because the actual birth date was long before we started collecting data
70	Management Buy-out
71	Placing combined with an open offer to shareholders
72	Placing combined with an intermediaries offer
73	Placing combined with offer to public
74	Issued under scheme/proposal to common holders or ordinary holders
75	Spinoff from another company
76	Exchange offer (usually Investment Trust company)
77	Issued against split of units
78	Issued in acquisition
79	Acquisition combined with placing
80	Issued in capital reorganisation
81	Exchange offer combined with offer for sale
82	Placing combined with rollover from another trust
83	Rollover combined with other offer
84	Scrip issue combined with placing and other offer
85	Placing combined with other offer and rollover
86	Demutualisation combined with other offer
87	Placing combined with rights issue or open offer

Reasons for new name record (LSPD) - Codelist for N7

Codelist for N7

1	Change of name
2	Change of SEDOL group
3	Change of SEDOL number

4	Reorganisation/Merger
5	Acquisition/takeover/merger
6	Suspension/cancellation with shares acquired later. Meanwhile, may be traded under rule 163(2)
7	Liquidation (usually valueless, but there may be liquidation payments)
8	Quotation cancelled (maybe suspended initially) as company becomes a private company, or there is insufficient trading in the shares. Dealings continue under rule 163(2) or (3) or rule 535 or Ofex or Plus or Specialist Funds Market (in the last case, the security remains on LSPD)
9	As for 8, but no dealings under rule 163
10	Quotation suspended – if suspended for more than three years, this may lead to automatic cancellation
10	Suspension
11	Voluntary liquidation, where value remains and was / is being distributed
12	Changed to foreign registration
13	Quotation cancelled for reason unknown. Dealings continue under rule 163(2) or (3)
14	As for 13, but no dealings under rule 163
15	Converted into an alternative security for the same company
16	Receiver appointed/liquidation. Probably valueless, but not yet certain
17	Unitisation of an investment or financial trust
18	Nationalisation
19	Enfranchisement
20	In Administration/Administrative receivership
21	Cancelled and assumed valueless or suspended but assumed valueless

 Industry code (Turner et. al) - Codelist for industryID

Codelist for industryID

1	Banks
2	Bridges
3	Mines
4	Canals
5	Foreign mines
6	Docks
7	Gas, light, and coke
8	Insurance
9	Miscellaneous
10	Waterworks
11	Roads
12	Telegraph
13	Railways

 Month (SAFE) - Codelist for MONAT

Codelist for MONAT

1	Januar
2	Februar
3	Marz
4	April
5	Mai
6	Juni
7	Juli
8	August
9	September
10	Oktober

11	November
12	December
77	Amount of share capital (in 100,000 Mark)
88	Amount of dividend (as a percentage) for the current year
99	Nummer der Anmerkung

Source Variables

Prijscourant (Amsterdam) - Amsterdam Stock Exchange official price list

Amsterdam Stock Exchange official price list

The Prijscourant published only spot prices. Prices are normally quoted as a percentage of nominal value, in fractional format (denominations of one-sixteenth). In those rare cases where prices are quoted in gulden per unit (Dutch: eensgevend geld), the price, in decimal format, is preceded by the abbreviation "f." (short for florin or gulden). Prices of fixed-income securities are quoted interest excluded; variable-income securities are quoted dividend included.

Column headings were the same for all types of securities, i.e. no distinction was made between fixed- and variable-income securities.

- [No. coup. of divid. - Coupon number](#)
- [Bedrag der leverbare stukken - Nominal value](#)
- [Vervaldagen der coupons - Interest payment date](#)
- [Namen der fondsen - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Procent - Interest rate](#)
- [Vorige koers - Previous price](#)
- [Laagste koers - Lowest price of the day](#)
- [Hoogste koers - Highest price of the day](#)
- [Gebleven koers - Closing price](#)

No. coup. of divid. - Coupon number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Bedrag der leverbare stukken - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (gulden in case of demostic securities or other in case of foreign securities)
Description	Par or face value of a security. The amount is preceded by an abbreviation (e.g. f, Fr, RM, RB, Kr, Lr) or symbol (e.g. \$ or £) indicating the currency. The nominal values of domestic securities are indicated in guldens; those of foreign securities in their native currency. In case multiple denominations are available, the nominal values are separated by a dash (-).

Vervaldagen der coupons - Interest payment date

Type	MonthDay
Description	In case of fixed-income securities (e.g. bonds and debentures), the date (or dates in case interest is paid semi-annually) from which coupons can be exchanged for interest is included in this column. In case of variable-income securities (e.g. shares), the abbreviation "divid." is included in this column.

Namen der fondsen - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (company or public body) (issuer) and the type of securities (for instance, "oblig." for bonds and "aand." for shares). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class is also indicated. For bonds, the year of issue may be included. If the interest rate of a fixed-income security (e.g. bonds and debentures) is included, the issuer has suspended interest payments (defaulted security). Defaulted securities are also indicated by an asterisk (*).

Procent - Interest rate

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

Description	Annual interest rate of fixed-income securities (e.g. debentures). This column is left blank in case of (1) variable-income securities (e.g. shares) and (2) defaulted fixed-income securities (e.g. bonds and debentures). If the issuer suspended interest payments on a fixed-income security, the interest rate is included in the previous column ("Namen der fondsen").
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Vorige koers - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally gulden per unit)
Description	This is the mid price (i.e. the mean of the highest and lowest price) of the previous day the security was traded. If a security has not been traded for a month, this column is left blank.

Laagste koers - Lowest price of the day

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally gulden per unit)
Description	This is the lowest price at which a security traded during the day the official list was published.

Hoogste koers - Highest price of the day

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally gulden per unit)
Description	This is the highest price at which a security traded during the day the official list was published.

Gebleven koers - Closing price

Type	Numeric (Other)
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Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally gulden per unit)
Description	This is the last price at which a security traded on the day the official list was published.

Berliner Börsen-Zeitung (Berlin) - Berlin Stock Exchange official price list

Berlin Stock Exchange official price list

The description is based on lists from the year 1920. At the time, there was no forward market in Berlin. Hence, all published prices are spot prices.

For most securities traded on the spot market, one price per day was quoted. These quotations are accompanied by abbreviations which indicated to which degree orders were effected at the given price. For instance, if all orders have been fulfilled at the given price, the price is followed by the abbreviation "bz." which is short for "bezahlt" (a full list of abbreviations can be found in D4.3). Only a limited number of securities was quoted continuously. Their prices were quoted in a separate section ("Papiere mit variablen Kursen").

Prices are normally quoted as a percentage of nominal value. In those rare cases where the price of shares is quoted as an amount per piece (for instance, for shares which have been partially redeemed), this is indicated by the abbreviation "MpSt." (short for "Mark pro Stück" or "Mark per piece"). Shares of insurance companies were always quoted in Mark per piece and are published in a separate section.

This set has no items.

Obligationen industrieller Gesellschaften - Corporate bonds

Corporate bonds

This section includes the prices of bonds issued by industrial companies. Prices of bonds issued by banks and railway companies were published in separate sections, but the columns are the same as those of bonds issued by industrial companies.

Items

- [Berliner Börsen-zeitung \(Berlin\) First column \(Untitled\) - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Berliner Börsen-zeitung \(Berlin\) Second column \(Untitled\) - Redemption value](#)
- [Z.F. - Interest rate](#)
- [Z.-T. - Interest payment date](#)

- Heute - Price
- Gestern - Previous price

Berliner Börsen-zeitung (Berlin) First column (Untitled) - Identification of the issue	
Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). Multiple issues from the same issuer are distinguished by the year of issue. An asterisk (*) indicates that a particular issue is not secured by a mortgage ("Die mit *) versehenen Obligationen sind nicht hypothekarisch sichergestellt.")

Berliner Börsen-zeitung (Berlin) Second column (Untitled) - Redemption value	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the amount at which debentures are redeemed.

Z.F. - Interest rate	
Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the annual rate of interest for fixed-income securities.

Z.-T. - Interest payment date	
Type	MonthDay
Description	This is the date (or dates in case interest is paid semi-annually) from which coupons can be exchanged for interest.

Heute - Price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)

Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day the official list was published. [Note: Prior to the first World War, multiple prices are quoted for shares traded at the forward market (Terminmarkt).]

Gestern - Previous price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day before the day the official list was published.

 Aktien von industriellen und Bergwerks-Gesellschaften - Corporate shares

Corporate shares

Some column headings are context-specific, i.e. the years in the headings of columns with information on dividends change yearly. Shares issued by banks and railway companies were published in separate sections, but the columns are the same.

Items

- [Berliner Börsen-zeitung \(Berlin\) First column \(Untitled\) - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Div. \[y-3, e.g. 17\] - Dividend for year-3](#)
- [Div. \[y-2, e.g. 18\] - Dividend for year-2](#)
- [Div. \[y-1, e.g. 19\] - Dividend for year-1](#)
- [Geschftsj. - Start date of fiscal year](#)
- [Stücke zu - Nominal value](#)
- [Heute - Price](#)
- [Gestern - Previous price](#)

Berliner Börsen-zeitung (Berlin) First column (Untitled) - Identification of the issue	
Type	Text

Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class (e.g. Vorzugsaktien or preferred shares) is also indicated.
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 Div. [y-3, e.g. 17] - Dividend for year-3

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the amount of the dividend paid for the third last fiscal year

 Div. [y-2, e.g. 18] - Dividend for year-2

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the amount of the dividend paid for the second last fiscal year.

 Div. [y-1, e.g. 19] - Dividend for year-1

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the amount of the dividend paid for the previous fiscal year. A symbol (°) is added if the amount of the dividend has already been declared, but the payment date is not yet determined ("° bedeutet, dass die Dividende auf den angegebenen Betrag festgesetzt, Termin der Auszahlung aber noch nicht bestimmt ist").

 Geschäftsj. - Start date of fiscal year

Type	MonthDay
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 Stücke zu - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Deutsche Mark for domestic securities or other for foreign securities)
Description	This is the par or face value of shares. This column may include more than one value if multiple denominations are available. Notes in the margin indicate if the share capital has been partially redeemed.

Heute - Price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally Deutsche Mark per unit)
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day the official list was published.

Gestern - Previous price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value (occasionally Deutsche Mark per unit)
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day before the day the official list was published.

Versicherungs Aktien - Insurance company shares

Insurance company shares

Shares of German insurance companies were quoted differently from other corporate shares (i.e. in Deutsche Mark per unit) and, consequently, treated in a separate section with different columns.

Items

- [Berliner Börsen-zeitung \(Berlin\) First column \(Untitled\) - Identification of the issue](#)
- [% - Paid-up value of shares](#)
- [Div. 17 - Dividend for year-3](#)
- [Div. 18 - Dividend for year-2](#)
- [Div. 19 - Dividend for year-1](#)

- [Stücke zu - Nominal value of shares](#)
- [Heute - Price](#)
- [Gestern - Previous price](#)

 Berliner Börsen-zeitung (Berlin) First column (Untitled) - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class (e.g. Vorzugsaktien or preferred shares) is also indicated.

 % - Paid-up value of shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	Percentage of nominal value paid-up on shares

 Div. 17 - Dividend for year-3

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Deutsche Mark per unit
Description	Amount of the dividend (in Deutsche Mark per unit) for the third last fiscal year

 Div. 18 - Dividend for year-2

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Deutsche Mark per unit
Description	Amount of the dividend (in Deutsche Mark per unit) for the second last fiscal year

 Div. 19 - Dividend for year-1

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Deutsche Mark per unit
Description	Amount of the dividend (in Deutsche Mark per unit) for the last fiscal year. A symbol (°) is added if the amount of the dividend has already been declared, but the payment date is not yet determined ("° bedeutet, dass die Dividende auf den angegebenen Betrag festgesetzt, Termin der Auszahlung aber noch nicht bestimmt ist").

Stücke zu - Nominal value of shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Deutsche Mark per unit

Heute - Price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Deutsche Mark per unit)
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day the official list was published.

Gestern - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Deutsche Mark per unit)
Description	This is the price which was quoted on the day before the day the official list was published.

Papiere mit variablen Kursen - Continuously quoted securities

Continuously quoted securities

Items

- [Berliner Börsen-zeitung \(Berlin\) First column \(Untitled\) - Identification of the issue](#)

- [Letzt K. - Previous price](#)
- [Heute - Price](#)

Berliner Börsen-zeitung (Berlin) First column (Untitled) - Identification of the issue	
Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class (e.g. Vorzugsaktien or preferred shares) is also indicated.

Letzt K. - Previous price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the last price at which securities traded on the day before the official list was published. The date to which the prices in this column pertain was printed at the top of the column.

Heute - Price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	These are subsequent prices at which securities traded during the day the official list was published. Prices are separated by the letter "à".

Cours authentique (Bruxelles) - Brussels Stock Exchange official price list

Brussels Stock Exchange official price list

The description is based on lists from the year 1925. More securities were listed on the spot market, but the forward market (marché à terme) was more liquid. Spot and forward prices were reported in different sections.

This set has no items.

Spot market

The Brussels Stock Exchange official price list has different columns for fixed-income and variable-income securities listed on the spot market.

Obligations, Actions à revenu fixe - Fixed-income securities

Fixed-income securities

Prices of fixed-income securities were quoted in Belgian francs per unit, in decimal format. Interest is included in the price.

Items

- [Titres admis - Number issued](#)
- [Titres en circulation - Number outstanding](#)
- [Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Intérêts - Interest rate](#)
- [Impôts - Tax rate](#)
- [Échéances des intérêts - Interest payment dates](#)
- [Valeur nom. - Francs - Nominal value](#)
- [Dates des tirages - Draw dates](#)
- [Cours faits - Price](#)
- [Cours précédents - Previous price](#)

Titres admis - Number issued

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The total number of securities belonging to a particular issue that were initially floated on the stock exchange. The actual number outstanding might be smaller because of premature redemption.

Titres en circulation - Number outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Description	The total number of securities belonging to a particular issue that were outstanding on the day the official list was published. This number may decline over time because of premature redemption of debentures.
-------------	---

Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (issuer). Multiple issues from the same issuer are distinguished by the year of issue.

Intérêts - Interest rate

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the annual interest rate.

Impôts - Tax rate

Type	Numeric (Other)
Description	The rate of the withholding tax on interests, to be paid by the bondholder. The letter "N" means the issuer paid the tax.

Échéances des intérêts - Interest payment dates

Type	MonthDay
Description	This is the date (or dates in case interest is paid semi-annually) from which coupons could be exchanged for interest.

Valeur nom. - Francs - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Measurement Unit	Currency (in Belgian francs in case of domestic securities and other in case of foreign securities)
Description	Par or face value of securities.

Dates des tirages - Draw dates

Type	DateTime
Description	This column includes information on the redemption of debentures. The nature of the information depends on the method of redemption. There are three possibilities: (1) If debentures are being redeemed prematurely by annual drawings, the date (month) of the drawing is indicated. (2) If the redemption by drawings has not started yet, the date of the first drawing (month and year, preceded by the abbreviation "1er en") is indicated. (3) If all debentures are redeemed at maturity, the maturity date (day, month and year preceded by the abbreviation "r." is indicated).

Cours faits - Price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	These are subsequent prices at which securities traded during the day the official list was published.

Cours précédents - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	This is the last price of the previous day the security was traded.

Obligations à revenu variable, Actions - Variable-income securities

Variable-income securities

Prices of variable-income securities were quoted in Belgian francs per unit, in decimal format. Dividends are included in the price.

Items

- [Titres admis - Number issued](#)
- [Titres en circulation - Number outstanding](#)
- [Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Valeur nom. - Francs - Nominal value](#)
- [Dates des tirages - Draw dates](#)
- [Cours faits - Price](#)
- [Cours précédents - Previous price](#)
- [Coupons | Dernier paiement - Dividend payment date](#)
- [Coupons | Montant et spécification - Amount and specification of the last dividend](#)

Titres admis - Number issued

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The total number of securities belonging to a particular issue that were initially floated on the stock exchange. The actual number outstanding might be smaller because of premature redemption.

Titres en circulation - Number outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The total number of securities belonging to a particular issue that were outstanding on the day the official list was published. This number may decline over time because of premature redemption of debentures.

Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class is also indicated.

 Valeur nom. - Francs - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs in case of domestic securities and other in case of foreign securities)
Description	Par or face value of securities. Empty in case of no-par shares.

 Dates des tirages - Draw dates

Type	MonthDay
Description	This column generally included the date on which numbers of shares that would be redeemed were drawn, but may also contain other information on the redemption of shares.

 Cours faits - Price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	These are subsequent prices at which securities traded during the day the official list was published.

 Cours précédents - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	This is the last price of the previous day the security was traded.

 Coupons | Dernier paiement - Dividend payment date

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the dividend reported in the next column was payable.

 Coupons | Montant et spécification - Amount and specification of the last dividend

Type	Text
Description	This column includes additional information on the last dividend paid: (1) the amount paid (in Belgian francs for domestic securities and other for foreign securities), (2) the fiscal year (preceded by the abbreviation "div."), and (3) the coupon number (preceded by the abbreviation "c." or "coup.").

 Terme - Forward market

Forward market

In the section devoted to the forward market, no distinction was made between fixed- and variable-income securities (i.e. data was published in a single table).

Items

- [Désignation - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Cours faits au ... \[liquidation date\] | Avant 2 heures - Forward price](#)
- [Cours faits au ... \[liquidation date\] | Cours de 2 h. pour la rép. des primes - Forward price](#)
- [Cours faits au ... \[liquidation date\] | Après 2 heures - Forward price](#)
- [Cours de compensation - Settlement price](#)
- [Coupons | Dernier paiement - Dividend payment date](#)
- [Coupons | Montant et spécification - Amount and specification of the last dividend](#)

 Désignation - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the company or public body which issued the securities (issuer).

 Cours faits au ... [liquidation date] | Avant 2 heures - Forward price

Type	Numeric (Other)
------	-----------------

Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	These are subsequent forward prices quoted before 14:00 during the day the official list was published for liquidation on the date indicated in the column heading.

 Cours faits au ... [liquidation date] | Cours de 2 h. pour la rép. des primes - Forward price

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	These is the forward price quoted at 14:00 on the day the official list was published for the declaration of options.

 Cours faits au ... [liquidation date] | Après 2 heures - Forward price

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	These are subsequent forward prices quoted after 14:00 during the day the official list was published for liquidation on the date indicated in the column heading.

 Cours de compensation - Settlement price

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)

 Coupons | Dernier payement - Dividend payment date

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the dividend reported in the next column was payable.

 Coupons | Montant et spécification - Amount and specification of the last dividend

Type	Text
Description	This column includes additional information on the last dividend paid: (1) the amount paid (in Belgian francs for domestic securities and other for foreign securities), (2) the fiscal year (preceded by the abbreviation "div."), and (3) the coupon number (preceded by the abbreviation "c." or "coup.").

Stock Exchange Daily Official List (London) - London Stock Exchange official price list

London Stock Exchange official price list

The description is based on the official lists for 1920. The Stock Exchange Daily Official List had different tables for shares and bonds. Bond prices were also quoted differently.

This set has no items.

Stocks and shares

Prices and quotations of stocks and shares were reported in British pound per 100 GBP (nominal value) of stock or per unit, in fractional notation. Dividends were included in the prices of shares (dirty prices).

Items

- [Amount created - Amount authorised](#)
- [Amount in issue - Amount outstanding](#)
- [Stk. Shr. - Nominal value](#)
- [2nd 1/2-yr. 1919 - Amount of dividend for second last semester](#)
- [1st 1/2-yr. 1920 - Amount of dividend for last semester](#)
- [When x d. or x in. - Ex dividend or ex interest date](#)
- [Name - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Paid - Paid-up value](#)
- [Mean price 27 Jly 14 - Mean price on July 27, 1914](#)
- [2 o'clock quotations - Closing quotation](#)
- [Bargains done for cash - Prices](#)

Amount created - Amount authorised

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the total amount of share capital that was created by the issuer. In case the share capital was divided in shares with a nominal value, this may also be the total number of shares created.

 Amount in issue - Amount outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the total amount of share capital belonging to a particular class of shares that was outstanding on the day the official list was published. In case the share capital was divided in shares with a nominal value, this may also be the total number of shares outstanding.

 Stk. Shr. - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	Par or face value of shares. If the share capital was not divided into shares, this column included the abbreviation "Stk." for stock.

 2nd 1/2-yr. 1919 - Amount of dividend for second last semester

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Dividends may be reported as a percentage of nominal value or in currency.
Description	This is the amount of the dividends paid during the second last semester.

 1st 1/2-yr. 1920 - Amount of dividend for last semester

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Dividends may be reported as a percentage of nominal value or in currency.
Description	This is the amount of the dividends paid during the last semester.

 When x d. or x in. - Ex dividend or ex interest date

Type	Date
Description	This is the first day on which securities are traded without coupon, meaning the seller and not the buyer is entitled to the dividend or interest.

 Name - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class is also indicated.

 Paid - Paid-up value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the amount paid-up on shares.

 Mean price 27 Jly 14 - Mean price on July 27, 1914

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)
Description	This is the mean price on the day before the outbreak of the First World War (28 July 1914, the Stock Exchange closed a few days later on July 31). SEDOL stopped printing this price after 1921.

 2 o'clock quotations - Closing quotation

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)
Description	This is a two-way price quotation (bid-ask price) at 14:00.

 Bargains done for cash - Prices

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)
Description	These are the prices at which shares effectively traded. The date in parentheses is the date on which the trade at this price took place. If there is no date, these are prices made during the day the list was published.

 Bonds

Prices and quotations of bonds were reported in British pound per 100 British pound of stock (nominal value), in fractional format. Interest was included in the price of bonds (dirty price).

Items

- [Auhorised issue - Number amount](#)
- [Present amount - Number outstanding](#)
- [When x d. or x in. - Ex dividend or ex interest date](#)
- [Interest due - Interest payment dates](#)
- [Per Ct. - Interest rate](#)
- [Name - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Red. - Year of redemption](#)
- [Mean price 27 Jly 14 - Mean price on July 27, 1914](#)
- [2 o'clock quotations - Closing quotation](#)
- [Bargains done for cash - Prices](#)

 Auhorised issue - Number amount

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the total amount of debenture capital that was created by the issuer.

 Present amount - Number outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the total amount of debenture capital belonging to a particular debenture loan that was outstanding on the day the official list was published.

 When x d. or x in. - Ex dividend or ex interest date

Type	Date
Description	This is the first day on which securities are traded without coupon, meaning the seller and not the buyer is entitled to the dividend or interest.

 Interest due - Interest payment dates

Type	MonthDay
Description	This is the date (or dates in case interest was paid semi-annually) from which interest was payable.

 Per Ct. - Interest rate

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This is the annual rate of interest.

 Name - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (issuer). Multiple issues from the same issuer are distinguished by the year of issue.

 Red. - Year of redemption

Type	Year
Description	This is the year when the bonds will be redeemed.

 Mean price 27 Jly 14 - Mean price on July 27, 1914

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)
Description	This is the mean price on the day before the outbreak of the First World War (28 July 1914, the Stock Exchange closed a few days later on July 31). SEDOL stopped printing this price after 1921.

 2 o'clock quotations - Closing quotation

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)
Description	This is a two-way price quotation (bid-ask price) at 14:00.

 Bargains done for cash - Prices

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Currency (British pound)

Description	These are the prices at which shares effectively traded. The date in parentheses is the date on which the trade at this price took place. If there is no date, these are prices made during the day the list was published.
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Boletín de cotización (Madrid) - Madrid Stock Exchange official price list

Madrid Stock Exchange official price list

The description is based on the official lists for 1934. Spot and forward prices are reported in different sections. All prices are reported either as a percentage of their nominal value or in peseta per unit. In the former case, the amount is followed by a percentage-symbol (%); in the later case by by the abbreviation pt. or pta.

This set has no items.

Operaciones al contado - Spot market

Spot market

In the spot market section, prices of shares and bonds reported in different tables. There were separate sections for securities of domestic and foreign companies, but the tables (i.e. columns) are the same.

Valores de sociedades nacionales - Acciones - Shares of domestic companies

Shares of domestic companies

Items

- [Capital en circulacion - Amount outstanding](#)
- [Nominal de cada titulo - Nominal value](#)
- [Desembolsado - Paid-up value](#)
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | A cta. - Amount of interim dividend for the previous fiscal year](#)
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Fechas \[1\] - Interim dividend payment date for the previous fiscal year](#)
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Comp. - Amount of final dividend for the previous fiscal year](#)
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Fechas \[2\] - Final dividend payment date for the previous fiscal year](#)
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | A cta. - Amount of interim dividend for the current fiscal year](#)

- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Fechas \[1\]](#) - Interim dividend payment date for the current fiscal year
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Comp.](#) - Amount of final dividend for the current fiscal year
- [Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Fechas \[2\]](#) - Final dividend payment date for the current fiscal year
- [Primer cupón a pagar](#) - Number of first coupon attached
- [Acciones](#) - Identification of the issue
- [Operación precedente | Cambio](#) - Previous price
- [Operación precedente | Fecha](#) - Date of previous price
- [Ofertas | Papel](#) - Bid quote
- [Ofertas | Dinero](#) - Ask quote
- [Cambios publicados](#) - Prices
- [Cambio de compensación](#) - Settlement price
- [Durante el año | Más alto](#) - Highest price of the year
- [Durante el año | Más bajo](#) - Lowest price of the year

 Capital en circulacion - Amount outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta in case of domestic companies, other in case of foreign companies)
Description	This is the total amount of share capital belonging to a particular class of shares that was outstanding on the day the official list was published.

 Nominal de cada titulo - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	Par or face value of securities

 Desembolsado - Paid-up value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount paid-up on shares.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | A cta. - Amount of interim dividend for the previous fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount of the interim dividend paid during the previous fiscal year.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Fechas [1] - Interim dividend payment date for the previous fiscal year

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the interim dividend for the previous fiscal year was payable.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Comp. - Amount of final dividend for the previous fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount of the final dividend paid during the previous fiscal year.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio anterior | Fechas [2] - Final dividend payment date for the previous fiscal year

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the final dividend for the previous fiscal year was payable.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | A cta. - Amount of interim dividend for the current fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount of the interim dividend paid during the current fiscal year.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Fechas [1] - Interim dividend payment date for the current fiscal year

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the interim dividend for the current fiscal year was payable.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Comp. - Amount of final dividend for the current fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount of the final dividend paid during the current fiscal year.

 Dividendos liquidos | Ejercicio corriente | Fechas [2] - Final dividend payment date for the current fiscal year

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the interim dividend for the current fiscal year was payable.

 Primer cupón a pagar - Number of first coupon attached

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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 Acciones - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing company (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class is also indicated.

 Operación precedente | Cambio - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)

Description	This is the last price of the previous day the security was traded.
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Operación precedente | Fecha - Date of previous price

Type	Date
Description	This is the day on which the previous price of the security was quoted.

Ofertas | Papel - Bid quote

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is a bid price for the security.

Ofertas | Dinero - Ask quote

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is an ask price for the security.

Cambios publicados - Prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	These are the subsequent prices at which securities traded during the day on which the official list was published.

Cambio de compensación - Settlement price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
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Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
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 Durante el año | Más alto - Highest price of the year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is the highest price at which securities traded on the spot market from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Durante el año | Más bajo - Lowest price of the year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is the lowest price at which securities traded on the spot market from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Valores de sociedades nacionales - Obligaciones - Debentures of domestic companies

Debentures of domestic companies

Items

- [Total en circulacion - Amount outstanding](#)
- [Amortización | Plazo - Term to maturity](#)
- [Amortización | Compra o sorteo - Method of redemption](#)
- [Cupón bruto - Gross amount of interest](#)
- [Cupón neto - Net amount of interest](#)
- [Venimiento de las cupones - Interest payment date](#)
- [Nominal - Nominal value](#)
- [Interés - Interest rate](#)
- [Obligaciones - Identification of the issue](#)
- [Operación precedente | Cambio - Previous price](#)
- [Operación precedente | Fecha - Date of previous price](#)
- [Ofertas | Papel - Bid quote](#)
- [Ofertas | Dinero - Ask quote](#)

- [Cambios publicados - Prices](#)
- [Cambio de compensación - Settlement price](#)
- [Durante el año | Más alto - Highest price of the year](#)
- [Durante el año | Más bajo - Lowest price of the year](#)

 Total en circulacion - Amount outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the total amount of debenture capital belonging to a particular debenture loan that was outstanding on the day the official list was published.

 Amortización | Plazo - Term to maturity

Type	Duration
Description	This is the number of years to maturity, i.e. the number of years before the debenture loan is completely redeemed.

 Amortización | Compra o sorteo - Method of redemption

Type	Text
Description	This column described how debentures are redeemed (for instance, "Sorteo" in case the debenture is redeemed by drawings).

 Cupón bruto - Gross amount of interest

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	This is the amount of interest before tax. The amount is per coupon, not per fiscal year.

 Cupón neto - Net amount of interest

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This is the amount of interest after tax. The amount is per coupon, not per fiscal year.

Venicimiento de las cupones - Interest payment date

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the next coupon is payable.

Nominal - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (peseta)
Description	Par or face value of securities.

Interés - Interest rate

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	Annual rate of interest.

Obligaciones - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (issuer). Multiple issues from the same issuer are distinguished by the year of issue.

Operación precedente | Cambio - Previous price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
------	-------------------

Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is the last price of the previous day the security was traded.

 Operación precedente | Fecha - Date of previous price

Type	Date
Description	This is the day on which the previous price of the security was quoted.

 Ofertas | Papel - Bid quote

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is a bid price for the security.

 Ofertas | Dinero - Ask quote

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is an ask price for the security.

 Cambios publicados - Prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	These are the subsequent prices at which securities traded during the day on which the official list was published.

 Cambio de compensación - Settlement price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)

Durante el año | Más alto - Highest price of the year

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is the highest price at which securities traded on the spot market from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

Durante el año | Más bajo - Lowest price of the year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is the lowest price at which securities traded on the spot market from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

Operaciones a plazo - Forward market

Forward market

The prices of fixed- and variable income securities were reported in the same table, but different sections were devoted to the securities of domestic and foreign companies. The columns were the same, however.

Valores de sociedades nacionales - Securities of domestic companies

Securities of domestic companies

Items

- [Operaciones precedentes | Fecha - Date of previous forward price](#)
- [Operaciones precedentes | Cambios - Previous forward prices](#)

- Clase de efectos y plazo - Identification of issue and liquidation date
- Cambios publicados - Forward prices
- Ofertas - Papel - Forward ask quotes
- Ofertas - Dinero - Forward bid quotes

 Operaciones precedentes | Fecha - Date of previous forward price

Type	Date
------	------

 Operaciones precedentes | Cambios - Previous forward prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)

 Clase de efectos y plazo - Identification of issue and liquidation date

Type	Text
Description	The identification minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (company or public body) (issuer). If a company had more than one class of shares listed, the share class is also indicated. For bonds, the year of issue may be included. The liquidation date could be either the end of the current month ("fin corriente") or at the end of the next month ("fin próximo").

 Cambios publicados - Forward prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	These are subsequent forward prices quoted during the day the official list was published for liquidation on the date indicated in the previous column ("Clase de efectos y plazo").

 Ofertas - Papel - Forward ask quotes

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is a forward ask price.

 Ofertas - Dinero - Forward bid quotes

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value or currency (peseta)
Description	This is a forward bid price.

 Cours authentique (Paris) - Paris Stock Exchange official price list

Paris Stock Exchange official price list

The description is based on the official lists from 1925. The official lists of the Paris Stock Exchange has separate tables for securities which were listed only on the spot market and on both the spot and forward markets. No further distinction is made between fixed- and variable-income securities. Bonds and shares were quoted in French francs per unit. Prices of securities which were not paid-up in full needed to be reduced accordingly. Shares of insurance companies present an exception in this case. Insurance companies' shares were quoted using the net à payer method. The price mentioned in the official list is the actual amount that the buyer had to pay to the seller. Dividends and interest are included in the prices of shares and bonds (dirty prices).

This set has no items.

 Comptant - Cash market only

Cash market only

Items

- [Montant des emprunts admis ou nombre de titres - Total amount or number of securities issued](#)
- [Période d'amortissement - Term to maturity](#)
- [Dates des tirages effectués - Draw dates](#)
- [Taux d'émission - Issue price](#)

- Epoques de jouissance - Coupon payment dates
- Intérêts et dividendes | Exercice précédent (brut) - Gross amount of coupon paid for the previous fiscal year
- Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Brut - Gross amount of the last coupon paid
- Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Impôts à deduire - Amount of tax
- Derniers cours cotés au comptant - Closing spot price
- Clôture de la veille - Previous spot price
- Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue
- Jouissance courante - Payment date of the current coupon
- Comptant - Spot prices
- Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus bas - Lowest spot price of year
- Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus haut - Highest spot price of year

Montant des emprunts admis ou nombre de titres - Total amount or number of securities issued	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	May be currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, or other in case of foreign securities)
Description	The total amount or number of securities initially floated on the stock exchange. The actual amount or number outstanding might be smaller because of premature redemption.

Période d'amortissement - Term to maturity	
Type	Duration
Description	This is the number of years to maturity, i.e. the number of years before the debenture loan is completely redeemed.

Dates des tirages effectués - Draw dates	
Type	Date
Description	This column includes the date on which numbers of shares that would be redeemed were drawn.

Taux d'émission - Issue price	
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Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Issue price of securities

 Epoques de jouissance - Coupon payment dates

Type	Date
Description	This is the date (or dates in case interest or dividends are paid semi-annually) from which coupons could be exchanged for interest or dividends.

 Intérêts et dividendes | Exercice précédent (brut) - Gross amount of coupon paid for the previous fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the gross amount of interest or dividends paid for the previous fiscal year.

 Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Brut - Gross amount of the last coupon paid

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the gross amount of interest or dividend of the last coupon paid.

 Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Impôts à deduire - Amount of tax

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the amount of the tax on interest or dividends.

 Derniers cours cotés au comptant - Closing spot price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	This is the last price at which a security traded on the spot market on day the official list was published.

 Clôture de la veille - Previous spot price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	This is the last spot price of the previous day the security was traded.

 Designation des valeurs - Identification of the issue

Type	Text
Description	Minimally includes the name of the issuing entity (company or public body) (issuer) and the type of securities (usually abbreviated as "obl." for bonds and "act." for shares). For bonds, the year of issue may be included, in addition to the nominal value, the interest rate and redemption price. For shares, the share class may be included if a company had more than one class of shares listed, in addition to the nominal value and the amount paid-up (in case the amount is paid-up in full, the nominal value is followed by the abbreviation "t.p." for "tout payé"). This column may also include the number of the last detached coupon (preceded by the abbreviation "ex-c." for "ex-coupon").

 Jouissance courante - Payment date of the current coupon

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the current (last attached) coupon is payable.

 Comptant - Spot prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Subsequent prices at which securities traded on the spot market during the day the official list was published.

 Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus bas - Lowest spot price of year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Lowest price at which securities traded on the spot market from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus haut - Highest spot price of year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Highest price at which securities traded on the spot market made from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Comptant & terme - Cash and forward market

Cash and forward market

Items

- [Montant des emprunts admis ou nombre de titres - Total amount or number of securities issued](#)
- [Epoques de jouissance - Coupon payment dates](#)
- [Intérêts et dividendes | Exercice précédent \(brut\) - Gross amount of coupon paid for the previous fiscal year](#)
- [Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Brut - Gross amount of the last coupon paid](#)
- [Intérêts et dividendes | Dernier coupon payé | Impôts à deduire - Amount of tax](#)
- [Clotûre de la veille \(comptant\) - Previous spot price](#)

- Désignation des valeurs - Identification of securities
- Jouissance courante - Payment date of the current coupon
- Comptant - Spot prices
- Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus bas - Lowest spot price of year
- Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus haut - Highest spot price of year
- Cours du terme | Report liq. à l'autre - Repo price
- Cours du terme | Cours de compens. - Settlement price
- Cours du terme | Clôture de la veille - Previous forward price
- Cours du terme | [blank] - Settlement dates
- Cours du terme | 1er cours - Opening forward price
- Cours du terme | Plus haut - Highest forward price
- Cours du terme | Plus bas - Lowest forward price
- Cours du terme | Dernier cours - Closing forward price

 Montant des emprunts admis ou nombre de titres - Total amount or number of securities issued

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	May be currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, or other in case of foreign securities)
Description	The total amount or number of securities initially floated on the stock exchange. The actual amount or number outstanding might be smaller because of premature redemption.

 Epoques de jouissance - Coupon payment dates

Type	Date
Description	This is the date (or dates in case interest or dividends are paid semi-annually) from which coupons could be exchanged for interest or dividends.

 Intérêts et dividendes | Exercice précédent (brut) - Gross amount of coupon paid for the previous fiscal year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the gross amount of interest or dividends paid for the previous fiscal year.

Intérêts et dividendes Dernier coupon payé Brut - Gross amount of the last coupon paid	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the gross amount of interest or dividend of the last coupon paid.

Intérêts et dividendes Dernier coupon payé Impôts à deduire - Amount of tax	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic securities, other in case of foreign securities)
Description	This is the amount of the tax on interest or dividends.

Clotûre de la veille (comptant) - Previous spot price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	This is the last spot price of the previous day the security was traded.

Désignation des valeurs - Identification of securities	
Type	Text
Description	Minimally consists of the name of the issuer. If more than one type of security is listed, the type of security is also mentioned. For government loans ("emprunts"), the year of issue is always included. This field includes frequent abbreviations and heavy use of the ditto mark (").

Jouissance courante - Payment date of the current coupon	
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Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the current (last attached) coupon is payable.

 Comptant - Spot prices

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Subsequent prices at which securities traded on the spot market during the day the official list was published.

 Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus bas - Lowest spot price of year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Lowest price at which securities traded on the spot market made from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Cours extrêmes depuis le 1er Janv. 1925 au comptant | Plus haut - Highest spot price of year

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Highest price at which securities traded on the spot market made from January 1st of the year the official list was published.

 Cours du terme | Report liq. à l'autre - Repo price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)

Description	Reports or repos were collateralized borrowing instruments. They coupled a spot sale of an asset with the commitment to repurchase the same asset at the following settlement. The repo price for an asset was therefore the price paid by the forward trader to roll over its position on that particular asset from a settlement to the following one.
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Cours du terme Cours de compens. - Settlement price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)

Cours du terme Clôture de la veille - Previous forward price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	This is the last spot price of the previous day the security was traded.

Cours du terme [blank] - Settlement dates	
Type	Text
Description	Through a forward contract, two parties committed to buy or to sell an asset at a specified future date, the settlement date or delivery date. At the settlement date, forward buyers (sellers) were committed to fulfill their purchase (sale) obligation.

Cours du terme 1er cours - Opening forward price	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	First price of the day at which securities traded on the forward market on the day the official list was published.

 Cours du terme | Plus haut - Highest forward price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Highest price of the day at which securities traded on the forward market on the day the official list was published.

 Cours du terme | Plus bas - Lowest forward price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Lowest price of the day at which securities traded on the forward market on the day the official list was published.

 Cours du terme | Dernier cours - Closing forward price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	Last price of the day at which securities traded on the forward market on the day the official list was published.

 Giełda Pieniężna w Warszawie (Warsaw) - Warsaw Stock Exchange annual report

Warsaw Stock Exchange annual report

- [Nazwa sp. akc. - Name of issuer](#)
- [Wartość nominalna - Nominal value](#)
- [Kurs w ... - Share price](#)
- [Kurs najwyższy - Highest share price of the month](#)
- [Kurs najniższy - Lowest share price of the month](#)
- [Przeciętny - Average share price](#)
- [Liczba notowań - Number of quotations](#)

 Nazwa sp. akc. - Name of issuer

Type	Text
Description	This is the name of the company that issued the shares.

 Wartość nominalna - Nominal value

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Polish mark and/or ruble)
Description	This is the nominal value of shares, initially in Polish mark and/or ruble and later increasingly in zloty.

 Kurs w ... - Share price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (zloty)
Description	This is the share price on the indicated date. Only one price per day is provided. From 1925, share prices are indicated in zloty.

 Kurs najwyższy - Highest share price of the month

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (zloty)
Description	This is the highest share price during the indicated month. From 1925, share prices are indicated in zloty.

 Kurs najniższy - Lowest share price of the month

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (zloty)

Description	This is the lowest share price during the indicated month. From 1925, share prices are indicated in zloty.
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Przeciętny - Average share price	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (zloty)
Description	This is the average share price during the month indicated. From 1925, share prices are indicated in zloty.

Liczba notowań - Number of quotations	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This is the number of days on which a price was quoted during the month indicated.

Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (Germany) - German joint-stock company yearbook

German joint-stock company yearbook

This set has no items.

Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (Germany) Untitled - Section title

Section title

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften \(Germany\) Untitled - Company name](#)
- [Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften \(Germany\) Untitled - Registered office address](#)

• [Zweigstelle - Locality of branches](#)

Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (Germany) Untitled - Company name	
Type	Text

Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (Germany) Untitled - Registered office address	
Type	Text
Description	Locality or street address where the registered address of the company is located.

Zweigstelle - Locality of branches	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the localities where branches of the company are located (if applicable).

Handbuch der deutschen Aktiengesellschaften (Germany) Untitled - Subsections	
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Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Gegründet - Entity history](#)
- [Zweck - Purpose](#)
- [Kapital - Share capital](#)
- [Anleihen - Debentures](#)
- [Geschäftsjahr - Fiscal year](#)
- [Gen.-Vers. - General assembly of shareholders](#)
- [Stimmrecht - Shareholder's voting rights](#)
- [Gewinn-Verteilung - Allocation of profit](#)
- [Bilanz - Balance sheet](#)
- [Gewinn- und Verlust-Konto - Profit-and-loss account](#)
- [Kurs - End-of-year share prices](#)

- [Dividende - Dividends](#)
- [Direktion - Management board](#)
- [Aufsichtsrat - Supervisory board](#)
- [Zahlstellen - Financial service providers](#)

 Gegründet - Entity history

Type	Text
Description	Generally includes the date of incorporation (i.e. the deed of incorporation, sometimes the date of registration is also given), but may also included additional information on predecessors, changes in legal form, former registered addresses, names of founders, dates of changes in the articles of incorporation, start date and duration of concessions, etcetera.

 Zweck - Purpose

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the statutory purpose or object of the company. It may also include additional information on production sites (factories, mines, tram- and railway networks, etcetera), machinery, production figures, number of employees etcetera.

 Kapital - Share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the current and historical capital of the company. First, the current total amount of share capital, the number of shares and the nominal value of shares is given. This is followed by a chronicle of capital operations from incorporation. It may also include information on principal shareholders (name, location, ...).

 Anleihen - Debentures

Type	Text
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Description	This subsection contains information on debenture loans, i.e. the date (year) of issue, the amount, the interest rate, the redemption price, the date of approval by the general assembly, the available denominations (nominal values), coupon (interest) payment dates, the maturity date, the method of redemption, the annual draw date (if applicable), the number or amount outstanding ("noch in Umlauf"), the cashiers ("Zahlstelle"), the stock exchanges where bonds were listed, the date of first listing, the introduction price and the end-of-year prices for previous years.
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Geschäftsjahr - Fiscal year	
Type	Timespan
Description	Start and end date of the company's fiscal year.

Gen.-Vers. - General assembly of shareholders	
Type	Other
Description	This is the date of the annual general assembly of shareholders. It is generally expressed in very general terms, e.g. "Im I. Quartal" (During the first quarter) or "I. Geschäftshalbj." (During the first half of the fiscal year).

Stimmrecht - Shareholder's voting rights	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of shareholder's voting rights at the general assembly. This may include the number of votes per share (of different denominations and/or classes if applicable), the maximum number of votes a shareholder can cast etcetera.

Gewinn-Verteilung - Allocation of profit	
Type	Text

Description	This subsection contains a description of the statutory rules for the allocation of profit between shareholders (of different classes if applicable), managers (Vorstand), supervisory directors (Aufsichtsrat), reserves, etcetera.
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Bilanz - Balance sheet

Type	Text
Description	This subsection included a balance sheet of the fiscal year ending at the indicated date. The balance sheet is presented as two paragraphs of text, assets ("Aktiva") and liabilities ("Passiva"). There was no standardisation of items. Subtotals are included.

Gewinn- und Verlust-Konto - Profit-and-loss account

Type	Text
Description	This section contains a profit-and-loss-account for the fiscal year ending at the indicated date. The profit-and-loss account is presented in several paragraphs. Each paragraph includes a section from the account. There was no standardisation of items. Subtotals are included.

Kurs - End-of-year share prices

Type	Text
Description	Contains a comma-delimited series of annual end-of-year prices of shares of different classes (if applicable) at different stock exchanges in Germany (if applicable) during the period indicated. The prices are reported as a percentage of nominal value.

Dividende - Dividends

Type	Text
Description	Contains a comma-delimited series of annual dividends paid to shareholders of different classes (if applicable) during the period indicated. The amount of the dividends is reported as a percentage of nominal value.

 Direktion - Management board

Type	Text
Description	This section contains information on the members of the management board. Included are the first and last name of directors, their profession and the locality of their residence.

 Aufsichtsrat - Supervisory board

Type	Text
Description	This section contains information on the members of the supervisory board. Included are the first and last name of supervisory directors, their profession and the locality of their residence.

 Zahlstellen - Financial service providers

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the names and locations of financial service providers, i.e. banks where share- and bondholders could cash their coupons.

 Stock exchange official year-book (London) - London Stock Exchange yearbook

London Stock Exchange yearbook

This set has no items.

 Stock Exchange official year-book - Section title

Section title

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Stock Exchange official-yearbook \(London\) Untitled - Company name](#)

Stock Exchange official-yearbook (London) Untitled - Company name	
Type	Text
Description	This is the name of the company. For sorting purposes, the publisher may have altered the order of words in the company name (last name always comes before first name, for instance, so "Edward Sharp & Sons, Limited" becomes "SHARP (EDWARD) & SONS, LIMITED". The official name, however, is always included in square brackets ("[...]").

Stock Exchange official-yearbook (London) Untitled - Subsections	
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Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Office - Registered office address](#)
- [Directors - Names of directors](#)
- [Secretary - Name of company secretary](#)
- [Auditors - Name of company auditor](#)
- [Solicitors - Name of company solicitor](#)
- [Bankers - Name of company bank](#)
- [Stock Exchange official-yearbook \(London\) Untitled - Date of registration](#)
- [Stock Exchange official-yearbook \(London\) Untitled - Purpose and activities](#)
- [Capital - Share capital](#)
- [Voting - Shareholder's voting rights](#)
- [Director's borrowing powers - Debenture loans](#)
- [Accounts & dividends | Accounts to... - Last day of fiscal year](#)
- [Accounts & dividends | Submitted in... - Date of submission of last annual accounts](#)
- [Accounts & dividends | Recent dividends - Amount of dividends in previous years](#)
- [Accounts & dividends | Untitled - Balance sheet items](#)
- [Transfers, &c. - Transfer and registration of shares](#)

 Office - Registered office address

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the street address and locality of the company's registered office, as well as other contact information such as telegraphic addresses and telephone numbers.

 Directors - Names of directors

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a comma-delimited list of names of directors. Included are the first name (or initials), last name and function of each director. The function (e.g. chairman, managing, ...) is included in brackets ("(...)") after the last name. The shareholding qualification for the directors (this is the minimum number or amount of shares required by the articles of association for holding the position of director in a particular company) is also included in brackets ("(...)") after the subsection title if applicable.

 Secretary - Name of company secretary

Type	Text
Description	First name (or initials) and last name of the secretary of the company.

 Auditors - Name of company auditor

Type	Text
Description	First name (or initials) and last name of the auditor(s) of the company.

 Solicitors - Name of company solicitor

Type	Text
Description	First name (or initials) and last name of the solicitor(s) of the company.

 Bankers - Name of company bank

Type	Text
Description	Name of the company's bank(s).

 Stock Exchange official-yearbook (London) Untitled - Date of registration

Type	Date
Description	This is the date of registration of the company by the Registrar of Companies. This subsection may also include a history of name changes, reconstitutions etcetera if applicable.

 Stock Exchange official-yearbook (London) Untitled - Purpose and activities

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a short description of the company's purpose and principal activities. Particular reference is made to production and distribution facilities (e.g. factories, plantations, branches, outlets, ships, ...) and their location, acquisitions and companies controlled by the company (i.e. portfolio).

 Capital - Share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes information on the current and historical capital of the company. First, the current total authorised and issued amount of share capital and the number, nominal value and paid-up amount of shares of various classes is given. This is followed by a chronicle of capital operations from incorporation. It further includes a description of the rights of preference shares to dividends and the liquidation balance (if applicable) and information on quotations. The latter includes the classes of shares and sometimes also the serial numbers of shares admitted to the Official List, the highest and lowest price ("price range") of shares during the previous year (at the London Stock Exchange), and the localities of other exchanges where shares were listed.

 Voting - Shareholder's voting rights

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on shareholder's voting rights at the general assembly. For each class of shares, it gives the number of votes per share.

 Director's borrowing powers - Debenture loans

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes information on company debt. It starts with a description of the statutory borrowing powers allocated to the directors by the articles of association. If applicable, it continues with an overview of subsequent debenture loans. For each debenture loan, it includes the name and interest rate; the total amount authorised, issued and outstanding; the date of issue and the price at issue (in percent of par value); information on the trust deed (date, names of trustees, description of the collateral); information on the redemption of the loan (e.g. date of maturity, method of redemption and redemption premium); interest payment dates; form (e.g. registered) and nominal value of bonds. If bonds were publicly traded, the subsection is concluded with information on the quotations of bonds (e.g. markets at which they were listed and highest and lowest prices during the previous year).

 Accounts & dividends | Accounts to... - Last day of fiscal year

Type	MonthDay
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 Accounts & dividends | Submitted in... - Date of submission of last annual accounts

Type	YearMonth
------	-----------

 Accounts & dividends | Recent dividends - Amount of dividends in previous years

Type	Numeric (Other)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

Description	This subsection included the amount of dividends (as a percentage of nominal value) paid to different classes of shares (if applicable) during the years indicated.
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Accounts & dividends Untitled - Balance sheet items	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes information on certain items from the balance sheet, particularly the amount carried forward to the next fiscal year and the amount of reserves (general and special).

Transfers, &c. - Transfer and registration of shares	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description on the formalities and fees for the transfer and registration of shares.

Anuario oficial de valores (Madrid) - Madrid Stock Exchange yearbook

Madrid Stock Exchange yearbook

This set has no items.

Anuario oficial de valores (Madrid) Untitled - Section title

Section title

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Anuario oficial de valores \(Madrid\) Untitled - Company name](#)

 Anuario oficial de valores (Madrid) Untitled - Company name

Type	Text
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 Anuario oficial de valores (Madrid) Untitled - Subsections

Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Constitución - Incorporation](#)
- [Objeto - Object](#)
- [Domicilio - Registered office](#)
- [Ejercicio social - Fiscal year](#)
- [Duración - Duration](#)
- [Capital - Share capital](#)
- [Acciones - Shares](#)
- [Reparto de beneficios - Distribution of profit](#)
- [Inclusión en la cotización - Date of first listing](#)
- [Consejo de administración - Board of directors](#)
- [Balance de situación - Balance sheet](#)
- [Cuenta de pérdidas y ganancias - Profit-and-loss account](#)

 Constitución - Incorporation

Type	Date
------	------

 Objeto - Object

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the statutory object or purpose of the company.

 Domicilio - Registered office

Type	Text
Description	Street address and locality of the company's registered office. This subsection also includes the locality of branches if applicable.

 Ejercicio social - Fiscal year

Type	Timespan
Description	This subsection includes the start and end date of the company's fiscal year.

 Duración - Duration

Type	Duration
Description	This subsection includes the number of years for which the company has been incorporated, or it may alternatively include the date of expiration.

 Capital - Share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the current and historical capital of the company. First, the current total authorised and issued amount of share capital is given. This is followed by a chronicle of capital operations from incorporation.

 Acciones - Shares

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes information on the company's shares. It includes the total number and nominal value of shares, the number of shares issued (Spanish: en circulacion) and unissued (Spanish: en cartera), and the amount paid-up on shares.

 Reparto de beneficios - Distribution of profit

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the statutory rules for the allocation of profit.

 Inclusión en la cotización - Date of first listing

Type	Date
Description	This is the date from which the company's shares were listed on the Madrid Stock Exchange.

 Consejo de administración - Board of directors

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the full names (first name or noble title and last name) and functions of the members of the board of directors and of managers of the company.

 Balance de situación - Balance sheet

Type	Text
Description	This subsection included a balance sheet of the fiscal year ending at the indicated date, usually the end of the previous fiscal year. The balance sheet is presented in two paragraphs of text: assets ("activo") and liabilities ("passivo"). There was no harmonisation of items. Item are separated by horizontal dashes ("-"). Subtotals are included.

 Cuenta de pérdidas y ganancias - Profit-and-loss account

Type	Text
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Description	This subsection contains a profit-and-loss-account for the fiscal year ending at the indicated date, usually the previous fiscal year. The profit-and-loss account is presented in two blocks of text: expenses ("debe") and earnings ("haber"). There was no standardisation of items. Item are separated by horizontal dashes ("-"). Subtotals are included. After the profit-and-loss account, the distribution of profit for the last fiscal year is given (i.e. the actual amounts distributed to shareholders, directors, etcetera).
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 Anuario oficial de valores (Madrid) Untitled - Tables

Tables

Type

Level 3

 Cotizaciones de quinquenio - Table of annual share prices during the past five years

Table of annual share prices during the past five years

This tables includes the highest, lowest and end-of-year price of shares during the past five years on an annual basis. In case shares are also listed on the forward market, an additional table with forward prices is included. The forward price table includes the maturity dates ("fin corriente" and "fin proximo") in the first column (Años - Year), but is otherwise identical to the spot price table.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Años - Year](#)
- [Más alto - Annual highest price of shares](#)
- [Más baja - Annual lowest price of shares](#)
- [Ultima del año - End-of-year price of shares](#)

 Años - Year

Type	Year
------	------

Más alto - Annual highest price of shares	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	As a percentage of nominal value

Más baja - Annual lowest price of shares	
Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	As a percentage of nominal value

Ultima del año - End-of-year price of shares	
Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

Cotizaciones por meses en [year] - Table of monthly share prices during the previous year	
---	--

Table of monthly share prices during the previous year

This tables includes the highest, lowest, end-of-month and average price of shares during the past year on a monthly basis.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Messes - Month](#)
- [Más alta - Monthly highest price of shares](#)
- [Más baja - Monthly lowest price of shares](#)
- [Ultimo de mes - End-of-month price of shares](#)
- [Cambios medios - Monthly avarage price of shares](#)

 Messes - Month

Type	Month
------	-------

 Más alta - Monthly highest price of shares

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

 Más baja - Monthly lowest price of shares

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

 Ultimo de mes - End-of-month price of shares

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

 Cambios medios - Monthly average price of shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Dividendos - Table of dividends paid during previous years

Table of dividends paid during previous years

This table includes information on coupon numbers, gross and net amounts, and payment dates of dividends during previous years.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Años - Year](#)
- [Número del cupón - Number of the coupon](#)
- [Dividendos - Tanto por 100 - Gross amount of dividend](#)
- [Integro - Pesetas - Gross amount of dividend](#)
- [Descuentos - Pesetas - Amount of tax](#)
- [Liquido - Pesetas - Net amount of dividend](#)
- [Fecha de pago - Dividend payment date](#)

 Años - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 Número del cupón - Number of the coupon

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Dividendos - Tanto por 100 - Gross amount of dividend

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value

 Integro - Pesetas - Gross amount of dividend

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Pesetas

 Descuentos - Pesetas - Amount of tax

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Pesetas

 Liquido - Pesetas - Net amount of dividend

Type	Text
Measurement Unit	Pesetas

 Fecha de pago - Dividend payment date

Type	Date
------	------

 Capital, reservas y utilidades - Table with capital, reserve funds and profit during previous years

Table with capital, reserve funds and profit during previous years

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Años o ejercicios - Year or fiscal year](#)
- [Capital - Pesetas - Total amount of share capital](#)
- [Desembolso total - Pesetas - Total amount of paid-up capital](#)
- [Fondus de reserva | Estatutario - Pesetas - Amount of statutory reserves](#)
- [Fondos de reserva | Extraordinario - Pesetas - Amount of extraordinary reserves](#)
- [Utilidades liquidas - Pesetas - Amount of net profit](#)

 Años o ejercicios - Year or fiscal year

Type	Year
------	------

 Capital - Pesetas - Total amount of share capital

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Pesetas

 Desembolso total - Pesetas - Total amount of paid-up capital

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Peseta

 Fondus de reserva | Estatutario - Pesetas - Amount of statutory reserves

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Peseta

 Fondos de reserva | Extraordinario - Pesetas - Amount of extraordinary reserves

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Peseta

 Utilidades liquidas - Pesetas - Amount of net profit

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Peseta

 Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) - Paris Stock Exchange and Coullise yearbook

Paris Stock Exchange and Coullise yearbook

This set has no items.

 Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) Untitled - Section title

Section title

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Annuaire Desfossés \(Paris\) Untitled - Company name](#)

Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) Untitled - Company name	
Type	Text
Description	The name of the company, romanised and translated to French.

 Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) Untitled - Subsections

Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Annuaire Desfossés \(Paris\) Untitled - Information on incorporation](#)
- [Objet - Purpose](#)
- [Siège - Registered office](#)
- [Capital - Share capital](#)
- [Parts de fondateur - Founder shares](#)
- [Emprunt par obligations - Debenture loans](#)
- [Conseil d'administration - Board of directors](#)
- [Assemblée générale - General assembly of shareholders](#)
- [Répartition des bénéfices - Allocation of profits](#)
- [Service financier - Financial service provider](#)
- [Inscription à la côte - Markets on which securities were listed](#)
- [Année sociale - Fiscal year](#)
- [Bilan - Balance sheet](#)

Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) Untitled - Information on incorporation	
Type	Text

Description	This untitled subsection includes information on the incorporation of the company, i.e. the legal form, the date of incorporation ("constitution") and the duration or expiry date of the company.
-------------	--

Objet - Purpose

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the statutory purpose of the company. An enumeration of the locations of production sites may also be included.

Siège - Registered office

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the locality and street address of the company's registered office.

Capital - Share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the current and historical capital of the company. First, the current total amount of share capital, the number of shares and the nominal value of shares is given. This is followed by a chronicle of capital operations from incorporation.

Parts de fondateur - Founder shares

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	This section includes the number of founder shares.

Emprunt par obligations - Debenture loans

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a chronicle of debenture loans, i.e. the total number and nominal value of bonds, the interest rate, the date of issue, the number outstanding ("en circulation"), the maturity date, the method of redemption, the annual draw date (if applicable) and coupon (interest) payment dates.

Conseil d'administration - Board of directors

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the board of directors of the company. First, general information on the minimum and maximum number of directors, the duration of their term and shareholding qualifications for directors is given. This is followed by a list of the initials and last names of the directors.

Assemblée générale - General assembly of shareholders

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains general information on the general assembly and voting rights of shareholders, i.e. the date of the annual meeting, the number of votes per share, the maximum number of votes per shareholder and the number of days before the meeting securities have to be consigned to participate and vote at the general assembly ("dépot des titres").

Répartition des bénéfices - Allocation of profits

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the statutory rules for the allocation of profit.

Service financier - Financial service provider

Type	Text
------	------

Description	Names (and sometimes locations) of financial service providers, i.e. banks where share- and bondholders could cash their coupons.
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Inscription à la côte - Markets on which securities were listed

Type	Text
Description	This section includes the markets where the different types and classes of securities issued by the company were listed (e.g. "marché en banque, au comptant: actions").

Année sociale - Fiscal year

Type	MonthDay
Description	This subsection includes the end date of the company's fiscal year.

Bilan - Balance sheet

Type	Text
------	------

Description	<p>This subsection includes a balance sheet for the company on the date indicated in the subsection heading (for instance, "Bilan au 30 septembre 1919"). Balance sheet items are presented in two columns: assets ("Actif") and liabilities ("Passif"). There was no harmonisation of items before 1936. Subtotals are included.</p> <p>From 1936, efforts were made to introduce a certain homogeneity in the presentation (see the note on pages V and VI of the 1936 edition). In particular, liabilities started being divided into five items (labelled A to E) and assets were divided into four items (labelled F to I). Liability items are sorted in ascending order of payability and the active liquidity positions by increasing order:</p> <p>Liabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capital, Issue premiums ("primes d'émission" in French), Reserves (of all kinds, legal, extraordinary, deferred profits), Provisions. - Consolidated Debt, Bonds, Debt securities, any term debts. - Floating debt: all debts due. - Dividends and bonuses, including, if applicable, advances paid. - Accounts of order, if any. <p>Assets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-current assets: Formation expenses, Reimbursement premiums, Buildings, Plants, Concessions, Equipment, etc. with deduction of the corresponding depreciation, Supply (when it is materiel to be immobilized), Securities and equity securities (when equity securities have some permanence or may be deemed as non-current). - Realisable assets: Stocks, Debtors, Securities (when they are temporary investments), Notes receivable, etc. - Available assets: Banks and cash. - Order accounts if applicable (i.e. if the nature of the accounts is not specified). <p>Possible losses.</p> <p>This pattern is still in use until the 1953 edition, except for the balance sheets of companies that have adopted the presentation of the "Plan comptable". In this case, the latter applies (see the note on page 12 of volume 2 of the 1953 edition).</p> <p>(Source: D-FIH Wiki, Balance sheets. https://wiki.dfi.fr/wiki/Balance_sheets)</p>
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Type

Level 3

 Annuaire Desfossés (Paris) Untitled - Table of financial information

Table of financial information

This table includes information on share prices, profit, reserves and dividends during past years.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Années - Year](#)
- [Cours des actions | Plus haut - Annual highest price of shares](#)
- [Cours des actions | Plus bas - Annual lowest price of shares](#)
- [Bénéfices | Bruts - Gross amount of profit](#)
- [Bénéfices | Nets - Net amount of profit](#)
- [Amortissements réserves - Depreciation and reserve funds](#)
- [Dividende | Totaux - Total amount of dividends](#)
- [Dividende | Par action - Amount of dividend per share](#)

 Années - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 Cours des actions | Plus haut - Annual highest price of shares

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	If the company issued multiple securities (e.g. shares and debentures), additional columns with the annual highest prices of other securities are included.

 Cours des actions | Plus bas - Annual lowest price of shares

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs)
Description	If the company issued multiple securities (e.g. shares and debentures), additional columns with the annual lowest prices of other securities are included.

 Bénéfices | Bruts - Gross amount of profit

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic companies and other in case of foreign companies)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000

 Bénéfices | Nets - Net amount of profit

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic companies and other in case of foreign companies)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000

 Amortissements réserves - Depreciation and reserve funds

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic companies and other in case of foreign companies)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000
Description	Alternative names: "Amortissements".

 Dividende | Totaux - Total amount of dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
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Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic companies and other in case of foreign companies)
Numeric Details	Scale: 1000

Dividende | Par action - Amount of dividend per share

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (French francs in case of domestic companies and other in case of foreign companies)

Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) - Polish joint-stock company yearbook

Polish joint-stock company yearbook

This set has no items.

Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) Untitled - Section heading

Section heading

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Rocznik informacyjny \(Poland\) Untitled - Company legal name](#)
- [Rocznik informacyjny \(Poland\) Untitled - Year of incorporation](#)
- [Rocznik informacyjny \(Poland\) Untitled - Company translated name](#)

Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) Untitled - Company legal name

Type	Text
Description	The legal name ("raison sociale") of the company (in Polish).

 Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) Untitled - Year of incorporation

Type	Year
Description	The year of incorporation is included in parentheses () after the legal name. In case two years are given, the first year refers to the year of establishment as a firm and the second year to the incorporation as a joint-stock company.

 Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) Untitled - Company translated name

Type	Text
Description	A translation of the legal name in French.

 Rocznik informacyjny (Poland) Untitled - Subsections

Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Adres Zarząd - Adresse de l'Administration - Registered office address](#)
- [Adres przedsiębiorstwo - Adresse de l'entreprise - Head office address](#)
- [Adresse télégraphique - Telegraphic address](#)
- [Rada Nadzorcza - Conseil d'Administration - Supervisory board](#)
- [Zarząd - Administration - Management board](#)
- [Dyrektor - Directeur - Managers](#)
- [Oddziałom - Succursales - Branches](#)
- [Przedm przedsiębiorstwo - Purpose \(PL\)](#)
- [Objet de l'entreprise - Purpose \(FR\)](#)
- [Produkcja - Production \(PL\)](#)
- [Production - Production \(FR\)](#)
- [Capital - Share capital](#)
- [Giełdy - Bourses - Stock exchanges](#)
- [Dividende - Amount of last dividend](#)
- [Bilan - Balance sheet](#)

 Adres Zarząd - Adresse de l'Administration - Registered office address

Type	Text
Description	Address of the registered office ("adresse de la direction")

 Adres przedsiębiorstwo - Adresse de l'entreprise - Head office address

Type	Text
Description	Address of the head office of the company

 Adresse télégraphique - Telegraphic address

Type	Text
------	------

 Rada Nadzorcza - Conseil d'Administration - Supervisory board

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the members of the company's supervisory board. The names and functions of the members of the supervisory board are given. The name includes the first and last names. The functions of president and vice-president are indicated by abbreviations in parentheses (respectively "prés." and "v.-prés."). Per the Joint-Stock Company Law of 1928, only companies with a capital of 5,000,000 zloty were obligated to establish a supervisory board.

 Zarząd - Administration - Management board

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the members of the company's management board. The names and functions of the members of the management board are given. The name includes the first and last names.

 Dyrektor - Directeur - Managers

Type	Text
Description	Name(s) (first and last name) of the manager(s) of the company. Specific functions are indicated by abbreviation in parentheses (for instance "dyr. zarz.-dir. en chef" in case of the general manager).

 Oddziałom - Succursales - Branches

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the localities where branches of the company are located (if applicable).

 Przedm przedsiębiorstwo - Purpose (PL)

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the purpose of the company in Polish. Special attention is given to the resources used by to company to achieve its purpose. This includes the localities of production plants (factories, mines, ...). The same information is also available in French.

 Objet de l'entreprise - Purpose (FR)

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the purpose of the company in French. Special attention is given to the resources used by to company to achieve its purpose. This includes the localities of production plants (factories, mines, ...). The same information is also available in Polish.

 Produkcja - Production (PL)

Type	Text
------	------

Description	This subsection includes a description of the production in Polish. The description generally consists of a list of products manufactured by the company and the total value (in zloty) of the production during the period indicated (usually a year). Production figures may also be expressed as the number of units produced. For non-manufacturing companies, the value (in zloty) of the annual turnover is given. The same information is also available in French.
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Production - Production (FR)	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the production in French. The description generally consists of a list of products manufactured by the company and the total value (in zloty) of the production during the period indicated (usually a year). Production figures may also be expressed as the number of units produced. For non-manufacturing companies, the value (in zloty) of the annual turnover is given. The same information is also available in Polish.

Capital - Share capital	
Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes information on the current share capital, i.e. the total amount of share capital and the number and nominal value of shares of different classes at the time of publication.

Gielyd - Bourses - Stock exchanges	
Type	Text
Description	Stock exchanges on which the company was listed.

Dividende - Amount of last dividend	
Type	Text
Description	Year and amount (as a percentage of nominal value) of the last dividend

 Bilan - Balance sheet

Type	Text
Description	The balance sheets are in French only. The balance sheet date is included in the subsection heading (for instance, Bilan au 31 Décembre 1927). Items are presented in two columns: assets ("Actif") and liabilities ("Passif"). There was no harmonisation of items. The currency is zloty.

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) - Brussels Stock Exchange yearbook

Brussels Stock Exchange yearbook

This set has no items.

 Recueil Financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Section title

Section title

Type

Level 1

Items

- [Recueil Financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - Company name](#)
- [Siège social - Registered office address](#)
- [Siège administratif - Administrative office address](#)

 Recueil Financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Company name

Type	Text
Description	The section title contains the romanised and translated name of the company in French.

Siège social - Registered office address	
Type	Text

Siège administratif - Administrative office address	
Type	Text

 Recueil Financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Subsections

Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Recueil Financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - Directors, statutory auditors and managers](#)
- [Bilan - Balance sheet date](#)
- [Assemblée - General assembly date](#)
- [Service financier - Financial service provider](#)
- [Untitled - Incorporation](#)
- [Untitled - Purpose](#)
- [Capital - Share capital](#)
- [Emprunts - Debenture loans](#)
- [Recueil financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - Summary of annual report](#)
- [Répartition - Profit allocation](#)
- [Liquidation - Distribution of the liquidation balance](#)
- [Assemblées - Shareholder's voting rights](#)
- [Bilan - Balance sheet](#)
- [Profit et pertes - Profit-and-loss account](#)

Recueil Financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Directors, statutory auditors and managers	
Type	Text
Description	<p>This subsection contains the names, domicile and function of directors ("administrateurs"), statutory auditors ("commissaires") and managers ("directeurs"). First, the first name (or initials) and last name are given. These are followed by the locality of their domicile and the title of their function.</p>

 Bilan - Balance sheet date

Type	MonthDay
Description	This subsection contains the date as of which the information in the annual balance sheet is stated. This is also the last day of the fiscal year.

 Assemblé - General assembly date

Type	MonthDay
Description	This subsection contains the date and sometimes time of the annual general assembly of shareholders.

 Service financier - Financial service provider

Type	Text
Description	Names (and sometimes locations) of financial service providers, i.e. banks where share- and bondholders could cash their coupons.

 Untitled - Incorporation

Type	Text
Description	The subsection contains information about the incorporation of the company, i.e. date and locality of incorporation. It may also include former names, dates of modification of the articles of incorporation and information about the legal form of the company. For companies in dissolution, the date of the decision of the general assembly to liquidate the company is given. For reconstituted companies, the date of the reconstitution is given.

 Untitled - Purpose

Type	Text
------	------

Description	The subsection contains a description of the statutory purpose or object of the company.
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Capital - Share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on the current and historical capital of the company. First, the current total amount of share capital, the number of shares and the nominal value of shares of different share classes is given. This is followed by a chronicle of capital operations from incorporation.

Emprunts - Debenture loans

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains information on debenture loans. First, general information about directors borrowing powers is given. This is followed by a chronicle of debenture loans, i.e. year of issue, total amount borrowed, number and nominal value of bonds, interest rate, tax rate, interest (coupon) payment dates, draw dates, maturity premium, maturity date, method of redemption and issue price.

Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Summary of annual report

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a short summary of the annual reports from previous years. The information is highly diverse. Recurrent topics include a discussion of activities, results and investments in factories and machinery. It may also include lists of securities in the company's investment portfolio.

Répartition - Profit allocation

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the statutory rules for the allocation of profit.

 Liquidation - Distribution of the liquidation balance

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the distribution of the liquidation balance.

 Assemblées - Shareholder's voting rights

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of shareholder's voting rights at the general assembly, i.e. the number of votes per share and the maximum number of votes per shareholder

 Bilan - Balance sheet

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a balance sheet for the company on the date indicated in the subsection heading (for instance, "Bilan au 31 décembre 1918"). Balance sheet items are presented in two columns: assets ("Actif") and liabilities ("Passif"). There was no harmonisation of items. Subtotals are included.

 Profit et pertes - Profit-and-loss account

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a profit-and-loss-account for the fiscal year ending at the indicated date, usually the previous fiscal year. The profit-and-loss account is presented in three columns. The first column includes earnings, the second depenses and the last the profit or the loss carried forward. Subtotals are included.

 Recueil Financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Tables

Tables

Type

Level 3

Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Summary table of profit-and-loss accounts

Summary table of profit-and-loss accounts

This table contains a number of items from the profit-and-loss accounts of previous years.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Excercises - Fiscal year](#)
- [Bénéfices - Gross amount of profit](#)
- [Frais - Amount of expenses](#)
- [Amortissements et réserves - Amount of depreciations and reserves](#)
- [Tantièmes - Amount of director's fees](#)
- [Dividendes - Amount of dividends](#)
- [A nouveau - Amount carried forward](#)

Excercises - Fiscal year

Type	Year
------	------

Bénéfices - Gross amount of profit

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

Frais - Amount of expenses

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The amount of specific expenses such as interest payments may also be given in separate columns.

 Amortissements et réserves - Amount of depreciations and reserves

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Tantièmes - Amount of director's fees

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Dividendes - Amount of dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 A nouveau - Amount carried forward

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Summary table of balance sheets

Summary table of balance sheets

For some companies, the Recueil financier published their own summaries of the balance sheet (résumé des bilans). The method of calculation is explained in detail the Preface of the edition for 1911.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Actif net, coupon payé - Amount of net realisable assets](#)
- [Immobilisé, réserves déduites - Amount of immobilised assets net of reserves](#)
- [Capital-actions en circulation - Amount of share capital outstanding](#)
- [Obligations en circulation - Amount of debenture capital outstanding](#)

 Actif net, coupon payé - Amount of net realisable assets

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Immobilisé, réserves deduites - Amount of immobilised assets net of reserves

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Capital-actions en circulation - Amount of share capital outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Obligations en circulation - Amount of debenture capital outstanding

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Table of dividends

Table of dividends

This table contains the amount of dividends paid on shares of different classes during previous years.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Exercice clos en - Fiscal year](#)
- [Recueil financier \(Bruxelles\) untitled - Share class](#)
- [Divid. - Amount of dividends](#)
- [Coupons n° - Coupon number](#)

 Exercice clos en - Fiscal year

Type	Year
------	------

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) untitled - Share class

Type	Text
------	------

 Divid. - Amount of dividends

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs in case of domestic companies, other in case of foreign companies)

 Coupons n° - Coupon number

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Cours 31 décembre - Table of end-of-year share prices

Table of end-of-year share prices

This table contains the share price on December 31 for shares of different classes during previous years.

Type

Level 3

Items

- [Recueil financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - Year](#)
- [Recueil financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - Share class](#)
- [Recueil financier \(Bruxelles\) Untitled - End-of-year share price](#)

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Year

Type	Year
------	------

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - Share class

Type	Numeric (Integer)
------	-------------------

 Recueil financier (Bruxelles) Untitled - End-of-year share price

Type	Numeric (Decimal)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Belgian francs)
Description	Share price on December 31

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) - Amsterdam Stock Exchange yearbook

Amsterdam Stock Exchange yearbook

This set has no items.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Section title

Section title

Items

- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Company name](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Security identification](#)
- [Gevestigd te - Registered office address](#)
- [Hk - Number of corner where securities are traded](#)

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Company name

Type	Text
Description	The name of the company is included in the section heading. Names in foreign languages are sometimes (although not always) translated and romanised.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Security identification

Type	Text
Description	The class of shares of the debenture loan is included in the section title. Debenture loans are identified by the interest rate, the initial term to maturity, the type of debenture (for instance convertible bonds), the year of issue and sometimes the total amount.

 Gevestigd te - Registered office address

Type	Text
Description	If a company is mentioned for the first time, the locality where the registered office of the company is located is included in the section title after the name of the company (preceded by the Dutch phrase "gevestigd te").

 Hk - Number of corner where securities are traded

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Description	The number of the corner at the Amsterdam Stock Exchange where this security can be traded is indicated in the section title in parentheses (preceded by the abbreviation "Hk", short for the Dutch "hoek").

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Subsections

Subsections

Type

Level 2

Items

- [Genoteerd - Listed share capital](#)
- [Coupure - Nominal value of listed securities](#)
- [Kapitaal - Authorised share capital](#)
- [Geplaatst - Issued share capital](#)

- [Uitstaand - Outstanding amount of debentures](#)
- [Coupon - Interest payment date](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Reserves](#)
- [Opgericht - Date of incorporation](#)
- [Duur - Duration](#)
- [Doel - Purpose](#)
- [Deelnemingen - Interests in other companies](#)
- [Trustee - Trust office](#)
- [Betaalkantoren - Financial service providers](#)
- [Koersen - Securities prices](#)
- [Dividend over - Dividends](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Location of subsidiaries, branches, factories etcetera](#)
- [Boekjaar - Fiscal year](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Chronicle of corporate events](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Redemption of debenture loan](#)
- [Gids bij de Prijscourant \(Amsterdam\) Untitled - Collateral of debenture loan](#)

 Genoteerd - Listed share capital

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Dutch guildens or other)
Description	This is the amount of listed share capital.

 Coupure - Nominal value of listed securities

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Dutch guildens or other)
Description	This subsection includes the nominal value of listed securities (i.e. the available denominations).

 Kapitaal - Authorised share capital

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the total amount of authorised share capital, the number and nominal value of shares.

 Geplaatst - Issued share capital

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Dutch guildens or other)
Description	This subsection includes the amount of share capital issued to shareholders.

 Uitstaand - Outstanding amount of debentures

Type	Numeric (Integer)
Measurement Unit	Currency (Dutch guildens or other)
Description	This subsection includes the outstanding amount of debentures on the date indicated.

 Coupon - Interest payment date

Type	MonthDay
Description	This is the date (or dates) from which interest was payable.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Reserves

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the amounts in the company's various reserve funds (e.g. general reserves, statutory reserves, reserves for dividends, ...) on the date indicated.

 Opgericht - Date of incorporation

Type	Date
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 Duur - Duration

Type	Duration
Description	This subsection includes the number of years for which the company has been incorporated.

Doel - Purpose

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes a description of the statutory purpose or object of the company.

Deelnemingen - Interests in other companies

Type	Text
Description	This subsection lists the companies in which the company has an interest, as well as the total amount and the percentage of shares of each company owned.

Trustee - Trust office

Type	Text
Description	This subsection includes the name of the trust office which guarantees the debenture loan.

Betaalkantoren - Financial service providers

Type	Text
Description	Names (and sometimes locations) of financial service providers, i.e. banks where share- and bondholders could cash their coupons.

Koersen - Securities prices

Type	Numeric (Other)
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Measurement Unit	Percentage of nominal value
Description	This subsection includes the lowest and highest securities prices on an annual basis during the years indicated (e.g. Koersen 1963-1965: 182-257 1/2 ; 165 1/4-228 ; 129-190).

 Dividend over - Dividends

Type	Text
Description	This subsection lists the amount of dividends (as a percentage of nominal value) and the numbers of the coupons paid during the years indicated.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Location of subsidiaries, branches, factories etcetera

Type	Text
Description	This subsection lists the localities where subsidiaries, branches, factories, etcetera are located.

 Boekjaar - Fiscal year

Type	Timespan
Description	This is the start and end date of the fiscal year.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Chronicle of corporate events

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a chronicle of corporate events such as conversions of shares, issues of new shares, etcetera.

 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Redemption of debenture loan

Type	Text
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Description	This subsection includes a description of the redemption of a debenture loan, i.e. the method of redemption, scheme for the redemption of debentures, draw dates, maturity premium etcetera. In case of convertible bonds, it also includes additional information on the conversion.
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 Gids bij de Prijscourant (Amsterdam) Untitled - Collateral of debenture loan

Type	Text
Description	This subsection contains a description of the collateral of a debenture loan.